

Book of Abstracts

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Preface

This book of abstracts contains 71 Nordic and international contributions presented at the Nordic Fire & Safety Days 2024 in Lund. We are proud to be able to show strong scientific and also societal relevance areas of fire and safety engineering in the Nordic countries. The NFSD follow up on challenges with respect to safety dealing with aspects of energy, biomaterials as wood, fire and as well as human behaviour and risk management. This year's keynotes and panel discussions deal with issues concerning the rescue service.

The days are organised by RISE, Research Institutes of Sweden and the NFSNergy in collaboration with Lund University, the Technical University of Denmark, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, University of Stavanger, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Luleå University of Technology and Iceland University as well as VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd, the Danish Institute of Fire and Security Technology and Aalborg University in Copenhagen. The NFSNergy network is supported by the Nordic Energy Research.

Anne Dederichs, RISE Research Institutes of Sweden (conference chair)

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¹RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

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¹Lund University

²DBI

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A Method for The Early Detection of Large Scale Lithium-ion Battery Fires

Joseph McDonald
Newcastle University
Newcastle upon Tyne,
United Kingdom
J.McDonald5@ncl.ac.uk

Dr. Simon Lambert
Newcastle University
Newcastle upon Tyne,
United Kingdom
Simon.Lambert@ncl.ac.uk

Dr. Wojciech Mrozik
Newcastle University
Newcastle upon Tyne,
United Kingdom
Wojciech.Mrozik@ncl.ac.uk

Prof. Volker Pickert
Newcastle University
Newcastle Upon Tyne
United Kingdom
Volker.Pickert@ncl.ac.uk

Prof. Paul Christensen
Newcastle University
Newcastle upon Tyne,
United Kingdom
Paul.Christensen@ncl.ac.uk

Keywords:

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Introduction

When heated to a critical temperature, lithium-ion batteries (LIB's) undergo a chain reaction of exothermic reactions in a process known as thermal runaway (TR). During TR, LIB's reach extreme temperatures which can result in major safety hazards including vapour cloud, fire, and explosion [1].

LIB's generate heat during normal operation from both the internal electrical resistances and chemical reactions. The total heat generation is increased with the charge and discharge rates. If these rates are too high, or the heat dissipation is too low, LIB's can be heated beyond the critical temperature of TR under normal conditions.

Similarly, the critical temperature of TR can also be exceeded through unintentional abuse of the LIB. Examples of unintentional abuse are overcharge and over-temperature. The LIB is protected from abuse by a battery management system (BMS) which monitors the key characteristics (voltage, temperature, current etc.) of the battery and can control safety mechanisms if the abuse condition thresholds are reached.

Problem Statement

Current BMS's fall short when attempting to detect abnormal temperatures in battery packs as they typically rely on discrete temperature sensors such as thermocouples or thermistors. In large scale battery packs, it is not feasible to monitor each cell with a discrete sensor due to the high number of cells and large surface area. For example, the Tesla Model 3 (standard range) battery pack contains 2,976 LIB cells with an estimated total cell surface area of $15.8m^2$. Using a sensor for each cell would be extremely expensive and would require extensive

computing power and I/O hardware. Sensors such as thermocouples only measure the temperature at a single point, leaving the majority of the cell surface area unmonitored. Battery pack designers typically compromise by using a single sensor to monitor a group of cells [2]. However, this solution is flawed as a cell undergoing abnormal temperatures can go undetected if it occurs in a cell which is not directly sensed. If no prevention strategy is implemented, the heated cell can trigger TR which can propagate throughout the pack, leading to total failure and extreme safety hazards.

Proposed Method

The methodology involves formulating a smart coating which is applied directly to each cell in the battery pack. The coatings contain an 'agent material' which is designed to release a detectable gas when it is heated to a critical temperature corresponding to dangerous LIB surface temperatures.

By detecting the released gas, a single gas detection system can be used to identify abnormal temperatures occurring at any cell in the pack. The data from the system can be used by auxiliary systems to raise an alarm or activate a suppression system. Figure 1 displays a block diagram outlining the method.

Figure 1. Block diagram outlining the operation of the proposed method.

Smart Coating

The main criterion for the smart coating is that it emits a detectable gas at a LIB surface temperature corresponding to the onset of TR. Through literature and firsthand experiments this temperature was deemed to be 60-80 °C depending on the exact LIB chemistry [1][3].

As there is no exact onset temperature that works for all LIB chemistries it was decided that the smart coating must be tune-able to activate at different temperatures. Micro-encapsulation was a technology that was identified that could meet the criteria. Micro-encapsulation involves entrapping droplets or particles of a material in a thin shell film to create capsules on the micro scale. The properties of the film material can be altered to give enhanced control over the release mechanism of the entrapped material [4].

Through experimentation, microcapsules with a poly(methyl-methacrylate) (PMMA) shell wall were found to have a thermo-responsive release of a volatile oil core at temperatures in the region of the general offset temperature range of LIB's. The release temperature can also be tuned using PMMA with different molecular weight. Figure 2 shows a microscope image of the manufactured microcapsules.

Figure 2. Microscope image of manufactured microcapsules with a PMMA wall and volatile oil core.

Smart Coating Testing

A method to assess the activation temperature of the capsules was developed. The apparatus involves gradually heating the capsules on a programmable hotplate, placed inside an airtight container. The released gasses were sensed by a custom gas sensor array consisting of eight MOS sensors. The sensor response and plate surface temperature were recorded on a National Instruments USB-6211 data acquisition system at a sampling rate of 5 Hz.

Figure 3 shows the results from a test using a microcapsule sample with a ramped heating rate of 5°C/s. The graph shows how the gas sensors (y-axis) respond to the increase in temperature (x-axis).

Figure 3. Graph showing the sensor response to the PMMA microcapsules under on a ramped hotplate profile.

The different plots show the sensor response from the eight TGS MOS sensors which are designed to detect different gasses in different concentrations. The combination of the gas sensor responses allows different core materials to be sensed for prototype capsules.

The graph shows that the microcapsules release a detectable gas at around 55°C with the first sensor response from the TGS 2602 sensor. With a large response corresponding to a temperature of >80 °C. These release temperatures fit the general temperature range of the critical onset temperature of TR.

Conclusion

This study identifies a novel method for the early detection of TR in large-scale battery packs based on a microcapsule based smart coating. The testing of the microcapsules succeeded in providing a 'proof of concept' for the method.

The smart coating will be tested on real LIB's undergoing TR in March 2024. This testing will determine if the coating is suitable for real LIB applications and heating rates.

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Energy production and storage in buildings

Fire safety challenges with Photovoltaics and Li-on battery systems.

Cristina Sanfeliu Meliá
Civil and Environmental
Engineering, Norwegian
University of Science and
Technology, (NTNU),
Trondheim, Norway
cristina.s.melia@ntnu.no

Reidar Stølen
Civil and Environmental
Engineering, Norwegian
University of Science and
Technology (NTNU) and
RISE Fire Research,
Trondheim, Norway

Brynhild Garberg Olso
Architecture, Materials and
Structures,
SINTEF Community
Trondheim, Norway

Anne Steen-Hansen
Civil and Environmental
Engineering, Norwegian
University of Science and
Technology, (NTNU), and
RISE Fire Research,
Trondheim, Norway

Keywords: *Li-ion batteries, Photovoltaics, Fire safety, Sustainability*

Introduction

Operation of buildings account for 30% of global energy use and electricity is the most used energy carrier [1]. Renewable energy can be produced on buildings and may compensate for the carbon footprint of the building and allows for so called zero emission buildings. Several different technologies can be used to generate or store energy in buildings [2], and among these, photovoltaic (PV) installations and lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are the most used.

PV can be installed on any building surface that receives sunlight to produce electricity. However, the production is depending on the amount of sunlight reaching the surface of the PV modules and varies over time. As the time of electricity production may not correspond to the time of electricity demand, technology to store electric energy is needed. LIBs can be built into battery energy storage systems (BESS) to allow storage of electric energy according to varying production and demand over time.

Rapidly increasing installation of PV and batteries challenge the current standards and regulations for fire safety in buildings. The fire regulations concerning PV installations in buildings are not clear and the fire safety design is depending on the knowledge and experience of the fire safety engineer [3]. A rapidly increasing demand for PV installations also challenges the capacity of competent installers and make room for unqualified or unexperienced installers.

The fire safety challenges of PV installations and batteries can be divided into three categories.

- Increased risk of ignition
- Changed fire dynamics and increased fire spread
- Obstructions and hazards for firefighters

Figure 1. Fire test in PV modules (Left). Battery installation (Right).
Photos made by RISE Fire Research, NTNU and SINTEF.

Fire safety challenges with PV installations

As other electric installations, the PV installations can cause ignition from overheating or electric arcs in case of electric faults. Many fires in PV installations start during the first year of operation indicating that poor workmanship during the installation has contributed to many fires [4]. A high frequency of faults in PV installations is also supported by more recent studies [5–7]. A fault tree analysis of fires in PV installations has been carried out by Mohd Nizam Ong et al. where the PV connectors were the main contributors with 17% of the PV related fires [8]. The same study also calculated an annual frequency of PV related fires to 29 per installed GW based data available from 4 countries.

Most PV installations on flat roofs, sloped roofs and façades include a ventilated cavity behind the PV modules. The cavity contains electric connections which introduce an ignition source and might increase the risk of ignition. In addition to that, the cavity can contribute to rapid spread of fire. This effect has been studied for flat roofs [9–11], sloped roofs [12] and vertical façades [13]. With an increasing risk of fire propagation and an increasing thermal exposure to the building surface, the fire resistance of the building envelope is challenged.

Firefighters are faced with difficult decisions when they are approaching a fire in a building with PV installations. PV installations generate electricity if they are exposed to light and can represent a severe hazard of electric shock if firefighters touch damaged components directly or indirectly through other conductive material. To avoid this hazard, they need to know where the PV modules are installed on the building and where the electric cables are routed. This may not be a trivial task, especially with an increasing number of PV installations that are designed to not look like traditional PV modules. With limited possibility to get access to the building surfaces behind the PV modules, it can be a challenging task to fight the fire effectively and this may increase the total fire damage.

Fire safety challenges with batteries in buildings

In recent decades, fire accidents have occurred in BESS [14]. Most of these BESS installations are placed in a container or in a standalone structural room. The reported fire incidents have caused significant damage to the storage facilities and surroundings and an acute threat to human safety.

BESS contain battery modules of several cells, electrical connections, inverters, and a battery management system (BMS). LIB cell components (Cathode and electrolyte) contain flammable chemical substances, susceptible to abuse or internal faults. When a cell cannot dissipate the internal heat generation, internal pressure and temperature may increase, beginning exothermic reactions and leading to thermal runaway (TR) [15,16]. The energy is released as heat and flammable and toxic gases [17]. Cells are self-sustained with oxygen, challenging the extinguishment of fire. The probability of a battery cell fire is low; however, the fire consequence can be severe. Electrical connections of BESS components also increase the risk of ignition.

Cell safety valve may vent hot gases before TR is achieved. During and after TR, the cell generates combustible gases, flaming and smoke. The fire growth of LIBs is rapid. Early fire detection and adequate extinguishing agents are important to control the earliest stage of fire growth. The risk of explosion during gas release challenges the design of room ventilation. A cell under TR may spread heat to adjacent cells, contributing to module fire spread. The limitation of fire spread inside the module is challenging due to the difficulty of accessing inside the module case. The fire dynamics of a LIB module consists of several heat release peaks, which depends on the number of cells under TR, challenging the fire extinguishing systems. The high energy release of LIBs may demand for specific thermal barriers in fire compartmentation and structural resistance.

Fires involving LIBs has challenges for firefighters. Installation size (Wh), location in the building, fire extinguishing systems and compartmentation of the room are essential information for them. Severity of potential explosion hazard increase when a LIB is under TR without burning, or TR propagates without flaming. To know about the hazard, they need to evaluate the battery gas venting, the formation of vapor clouds, damages in the door/compartmentation and in the structure [18].

Preventing disasters with PV and battery systems

The research on fire safety of PV and battery systems needs to be applied in design of new and existing buildings. It is crucial that new knowledge is transferred from researchers to the fire safety engineers that designs the overall fire safety strategies of buildings, as well as electrical engineers, architects and other professionals involved. Another important aspect that needs to be improved is the transfer of knowledge to the building owners, which are responsible for maintenance and safe operation of the fire safety measures installed. Hence, it is crucial that new knowledge is applied to regulate risks associated with PV and LIBs when regulations, standards and guidelines are developed.

Understanding how different elements interact, like PV modules and roofing membranes, or batteries and ventilation systems is crucial to make sure that the overall safety is acceptable. The key aspects to for PV installations are:

- Ensuring high quality installations without faults.
- Prevent fire propagation and ensure sufficient fire resistance for underlying building constructions.
- For firefighters:

- o Information regarding the specific PV installation, including size and location of the system components.
- o Targeted training on risks associated with extinguishing efforts for PV installations.

The key aspects to consider for batteries in buildings are:

- Use batteries that have passed safety standards for Energy storage systems and Equipment, such as UL-9540A:2019, UL-9540:2020 (All system levels: cell, module, pack and system [19]).
- Gas detectors intended for LIBs. Efficient extinguishing system that controls fire propagation module-to-module.
- Install the battery system in a fire compartment.

If these aspects are carefully considered and implemented in the building fire safety design, these technologies could be safely used and can contribute to reducing the fire incidents.

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Guidelines for the fire protection of BESS

Marcus Rasmussen	Jonna Hynynen	Oskar Grönlund	Maria Quant	Ola Willstrand
Fire Safe Transport, RISE	Fire Safe Transport, RISE	Fire Safe Transport, RISE	Fire Safe Transport, RISE	Fire Safe Transport, RISE
Borås, Sweden	Borås, Sweden	Borås, Sweden	Borås, Sweden	Borås, Sweden
Presenting author marcus.rasmussen@ri.se				

Keywords: (5 key words)

Lithium-ion, battery, battery energy storage system, fire safety, guideline

Abstract

Energy storage is essential for enhancing the stability, efficiency, and sustainability of the modern energy supply chain. Lithium-ion battery energy storage systems (BESS) currently stand as the predominant technology for this purpose.

However, until recently, Sweden lacked national guidelines for designing BESS concerning fire safety. This absence led each municipality and local fire and rescue service to devise their own ad hoc advice, resulting in costlier solutions and inconsistencies in fire protection measures. Through the project, guidelines were formulated into three application categories (AK) based on user needs: AK1 for single-family homes, AK2 for multi-dwelling blocks and businesses, and AK3 for larger commercial applications. These guidelines were crafted through literature searches, review of relevant laws, regulations, and standards, examination of international guidelines, workshops, information gathering from project partners, and analysis of lessons learned from past incidents, including major accidents in Arizona, USA [1], and Beijing, China [2].

Figure 1. Image depicting a battery energy storage system (BESS) on fire. Figure by RISE.

Laws, regulations, and standards

Several laws, regulations and standards are relevant when looking at the fire protection of BESS. Relevant EU directives include Product Safety, Low-voltage and Electromagnetic Compatibility. In Sweden, The Swedish Electrical Safety Authority have a framework regulation based on electrical installations being designed according to “good electrical safety technical practice”. However, this practice does not contain any technical requirements, which is instead detailed in standards, such as the electrical installation regulations (SS 436 40 00). [3] Additionally, Boverkets Building Regulations (BBR) also contain mandatory provisions and general recommendations regarding buildings. While BESS are not explicitly mentioned, the description of several sections can be interpreted to fit BESS. The result is varying solutions and inconsistencies in fire protection measures.

Risks associated with lithium-ion batteries

The gravest safety risk posed by lithium-ion batteries is their susceptibility to thermal runaway. Thermal runaway entails the uncontrolled conversion of stored energy into heat through a series of chemical chain reactions within the battery cell. In addition to heat, toxic and flammable gases are produced [4–5].

In enclosed spaces, where flammable gases can accumulate, this poses a risk for explosion. Although the number of accidents involving explosions is exceedingly low, their consequences can be devastating. A notable example is the severe accident that occurred at a battery energy storage facility in McMicken in Arizona, USA, in 2019. [1] It commenced with a cell undergoing thermal runaway. The heat from the cell propagated, leading to intense smoke generation within the facility. When the fire and rescue service opened the door to access the facility, the smoke mixed with oxygen, causing the gas mixture to become flammable and ignite. Four firefighters sustained serious injuries in the incident. A similar accident occurred in Dahongmen in central Beijing, China. [2] Thermal propagation following a short-circuit resulted in gases being transported to a secondary building through an underground cable trench where they ignited, causing an explosion. Tragically, two firefighters and an employee lost their lives in the accident.

Fire safety guidelines for BESS

The research underscores the importance of adhering to manufacturer installation requirements and carefully considering BESS placement to ensure safety. BESS should not obstruct escape routes or be placed in living quarters. Moreover, placement should consider the safety of fire and rescue teams and protect against mechanical impact and external fires. Key aspects of fire safety include provisions for fire gas ventilation, fire alarms, and signage to provide crucial information for first responders.

The developed guidelines aim to be a valuable resource for fire consultants, fire rescue services, insurance companies, private individuals, and other stakeholders when installing new BESS or evaluating the fire protection of existing installations. The goal is to make the work of fire protection for BESS more consistent, cost-effective, and, above all, to maintain a higher level of safety. Through continued collaboration among stakeholders involved in BESS and dissemination of information to users, we can ensure that installations are safe.

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Don't quit your day-job.

Part-time fire fighters in rural fire departments.

Petter G. Almklov
Norwegian University of
Science and Technology,
NTNU
Trondheim, Norway
Petter.almklov@ntnu.no

Gudveig Gjøsund
NTNU Social Research
Trondheim, Norway
gudveig.gjosund@samforsk.no

Torgeir Haavik
NTNU Social Research
Trondheim, Norway
torgeir.haavik@samforsk.no

Keywords: (5 key words)

Fire fighters, rural communities, problem-solving networks, flexibility, adaptive capacity.

Abstract

While his colleagues try to secure a collapsed building after a landslide and watch out for new landslides, a school teacher, on a 2% contract as a part time fire fighter, and his colleagues (plumbers, a janitor and carpenters) have dug their way through the mud, rubble and furniture-remains, secured a tunnel-like entrance into the devastated building, and now carefully use an electric saw to safely free a toddler that has been stuck in the remains of the building for hours. This is what emergency response can look like in Norway.

In Norway, two thirds of the fire fighters are employed in part-time positions. For a majority of these, part time positions mean that they are basically only paid for some hours of training each year, a sum for agreeing to be on call at all times, and then in addition, for any call-outs that they respond to. They are people with other day-jobs, carrying a call-out radio with them at all times. In districts and rural areas, the backbone of the emergency response apparatus still is these part-timers belonging to small services where typically only a couple of firefighters, the fire chief and some other key personnel, have full-time positions. Still, these services are often first on site, before the ambulance and the police, and before backup arrives from other areas, in a variety of emergencies. Experience from several incidents has shown that they tend to perform impressively in these situations. Deeply embedded in the communities they serve, highly motivated, and staffed with people from a variety of occupations, they seem to have a flexibility and adaptive capacity that is effective both in emergencies and while developing their services.

Ongoing and planned consolidation of the fire services will change the role of part time firefighters (PTFFs), but effective fire and rescue services will still depend on them. And, as they are “volunteers” in the sense that the money they are paid for their work is quite small, and hardly the main motivating factor, it will be an important challenge to preserve this resource.

PTFFs are quite rarely studied. That has earlier been the case for us as well. In our own research in the sector, they have typically played a peripheral role. The typical interviewee would, in most projects, be full time personnel talking *about*

the PTFFs. In most cases, these stories would be positive discussions of their resourcefulness and motivation.

Our presentation is based on research in the sector over more than a decade but focuses mainly on a recent study of two rural fire departments. We discuss how such organizations, and their employees, seem to have some particular qualities that make them more effective than a quick glance on an organizational map, their equipment inventory and not least their budgets would suggest.

A key motivation of the paper is to fill what we perceive as an empirical gap in the literature when it comes to understanding the part-time firefighters and the services they work for.

In terms of analysis our presentation discusses the following:

- The importance of personal networks, within the service, but particularly in relation to the communities they serve.
- The motivation among the personnel, its sources and its importance for task resolution.
- How the heterogeneity of backgrounds and skills among the fire fighters can be a resource. Particularly, we will discuss the importance in many cases of skills (and networks) acquired in their day-jobs.

These phenomena can be seen as results of a what we call a social and material *embeddedness* of the FRS in the communities they serve. This embeddedness partly comes from the close-knit nature of social networks in small communities, but it is strengthened by the fact that the PTFFs have other occupations and thus more expansive networks in the communities. The material aspect of the embeddedness highlights how their networks are shaped also by geography and industrial make-up of the community, e.g. the availability of equipment and expertise.

Though our interview-based study is a snapshot of the current state of the services we have studied, our data also allows us to speculate on the *emergence* of this embeddedness. To us it seems that the services grow organically over time as extensions of the local communities. They are results of a history of adaptation to local circumstances, both in terms of resources available and the threats the community typically face. The uniqueness of each service can be traced through a trajectory of previous

adaptations. Thus, we propose, the heterogeneity of small fire services, is in many ways a result of a history of adaptive choices. This heterogeneity is a source of concern, as it makes them less governable and also dependent on key individuals and their personal networks. But also, this home-grown resilience, in which the part-time firefighters are cornerstones, or lynchpins, might be a key source of their effectiveness.

Firefighter training in Virtual Reality

- A zero smoke exposure supplement to hot-fire training?

Josefina Berglund

Western Norway
University of Applied
Science (HVL),
Haugesund

Synne Heggøy Fjeldberg

Western Norway
University of Applied
Science (HVL), Haugesund

Arjen Kraaijeveld

Western Norway
University of Applied
Science (HVL), Haugesund
Arjen.kraaijeveld@hvl.no

Cecilia Hammar Wijkmark

Western Norway
University of Applied
Science (HVL), Haugesund
Cecilia.hammar.wijkmark@hvl.no

Keywords: *Virtual Reality, firefighter training, exposure, smoke, cancer, occupational health*

Introduction

In 2022 the firefighting profession was classified as 'carcinogenic to humans' by IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer) [1]. Like many countries, the Norwegian 'Guidance on smoke and chemical diving' (last update 2005) demands at least one 'hot' smoke diving training for firefighters annually [2]. These training sessions are carried out in steel ship containers or an abandoned house ready for demolition, i.e., involving exposure to smoke. A study conducted by the Swedish Defense Research Agency (FOI) during firefighter training at the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) revealed increased levels of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH) in the firefighters' urine even after 20 hours. The study concluded that smoke diving training in hot smoke contributes to exposure to carcinogens, e.g., PAHs [3].

Fire brigades in Norway are becoming more aware of preventive measures to reduce exposure. The Swedish concept 'Friska brandmän' [4] has inspired to reduce exposure and introduce preventive measures. Firefighters, often part-time employees, seldom perform smoke diving in an actual fire situation, but they must be prepared for the task at any time. The major smoke exposure thus relates to training, not actual fire events

Virtual Reality (VR) has become accepted to provide safe and effective training in different fields where practice-based training is necessary. Still, training in real settings is associated with risk, e.g., forklift training [5] and operation room training [6], but VR promises new possibilities in the areas [6,7]. The possibility of using VR for firefighter training has also been studied [8, 9, 10, 11], concluding in accepting the new training format as a supplement for hot fire training [12, 13]. Possible benefits include training in unusual fire scenarios, repetitive training, specific procedures, and more pre-training before hot fire training [11].

The aim of this study was to investigate whether the IARC classification has influenced firefighters' risk awareness related to smoke exposure and if they perceive VR training as a possible supplement to, or partial replacement of, hot fire training.

The study-design

The study was performed using mixed methods in col-

laboration with the fire brigades "Haugaland Brann og redning" and "Haugesund Brannvesen". Documented routines and procedures related to smoke diving training and exposure prevention were examined. VR training was conducted, allowing 35 experienced firefighters to perform in three fire scenarios. A pre- and post-training questionnaire were developed based on previous validated questionnaire batteries [8, 9, 13], adjusted to the local setting, and questions related to smoke exposure were added. The pre-training questionnaire included questions about the participants' awareness of long-term health risks related to smoke exposure, expectations about the VR training, and whether they thought VR training could (partly) substitute hot fire training. The post-training questionnaire included questions related to their experience in VR, their willingness to train using VR, and their opinion on whether VR can replace or supplement hot fire training. The questionnaires allowed the investigation of possible changes of opinions after gaining experience with the technology. The training lasted approximately 20 minutes and consisted of three scenarios varying from residential fires to traffic accidents.

The VR technology (Figure 1) used in the study is a highly immersive VR, FLAIM trainer [14], with a mounted

Figure 1. A firefighter training in VR.

display (visual and audio), a harness and air bottle (to provide a realistic weight), a real nozzle, and hose (providing the real nozzle functions, the weight of pulling the hose, and haptic feedback when opening the nozzle), heat vest (the vest reacts to the distance to the virtual fire), and a thermal camera.

Results

The result shows that 75% of the firefighters experience increased concern about possible negative health impacts related to their work. In the study, 46% of the participants were also hot fire training instructors, exposed to more than the obligatory training.

85% of the firefighters had no previous experience with VR training. Before training, 61% consider VR training to be a good supplement to hot fire training. After VR training, when asked to consider the negative aspects of hot fire training exposure, 83% of the firefighters were willing to replace some of the hot training with VR training. Regarding the realistic experience in the virtual fire situation, 97% of the firefighters perceived the flames as realistic enough for training, 91% found the smoke and the water appearance and behavior to be sufficiently realistic for training [15].

Conclusion

There is an increasing awareness and concern among firefighters about the health risks of hot fire training. A substantial amount of the firefighters' work exposure is caused by hot fire training, especially considering the instructors. The study shows that neither hot fire training nor VR training is experienced as realistic simulations compared to incidents. However, VR flames, smoke, and water are considered realistic enough for training. Experienced firefighters are willing to replace some hot fire training after experiencing VR training.

Recommendation

In Norway, the 'Guidance on smoke and chemical diving' published by Arbeidstilsynet (The Norwegian Labour Inspection Authority) should be updated to VR training, replacing current hot fire training in containers, to a certain extent, to reduce smoke exposure.

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Reducing fire disaster risk through dynamic risk assessment and management (DYNAMIC)

Firefighting Engineering-

Fire brigade intervention model in Danish fire safety design

Vladyslav V. Bogatyry
DTU Civil and Mechanical
Engineering, Technical
University of Denmark
Lyngby, Denmark
Email:
vlad2016@hotmail.com

Michael Beck Meincke
DTU Civil and Mechanical
Engineering, Technical
University of Denmark
Lyngby, Denmark
Email:
michaelbmeincke@gmail.com

Anne S. Dederichs
RISE, Research Institutes of
Sweden &
Technical University of
Denmark
Lyngby, Denmark
Email: Anne.Dederichs@ri.se

Keywords: *Fire Brigade Intervention Method, Performance based Codes, Electrical vehicle, Carpark.*

Abstract

As the performance-based approach was first defined in Australia and New Zealand in the 1980s and 90s, the fire departments were included in the decision-making process of the fire regulation. This enabled the development of the Fire Brigade Intervention Model (FBIM). The model was introduced to account for the actions of the rescue service. In the current study, FBIM was applied to a Danish case to define the procedure and methodology required to apply FBIM method. The intervention in a fire of an electrical vehicle (EV) in a carpark was used as a test case. Through the process of applying the FBIM method, several key issues and limitations were identified for the Danish case from which a procedure and methodology was developed and validated. When comparing the times for initial fire control (IFC), the intervention of two firefighting teams was 7.45% higher than for four firefighting teams.

Introduction

In the 1980s, the performance-based approach made its entrance into the world of Fire Safety Engineering. In most countries, fire safety engineers were the chosen disciplines to define the new nonprescriptive requirements, aiming at providing prediction on evacuation and fire dynamics [1]. Australia and New Zealand, however, included the rescue services into the decision-making process on performance-based fire regulations [2]. This led to the development of a tool; the Fire Brigade Intervention Model (FBIM) enabling accounting of the intervention activities of the fire brigade when evaluating the performance of a building design with respect to fire safety [3]. The present version of FBIM relies on data from Australia and New Zealand. In FBIM, the intervention processes are quantified; the trip from the fire station to the curbside, walking speed from the engine to the fire central, establishing a tactic, connecting hoses, etc. All such actions are mapped and described by 16 flowcharts and represented with specific time values, providing a total time schedule of the processes for almost any scenario. However, the user is required to adapt a specific chain of events suited for the given situation, i.e. defining the order to which the flowcharts are applied. Hence, the user needs a knowledge of

the applied intervention strategies and activities. The focus of this project is to evaluate the suitability of FBIM in a Danish context.

Method

Two hypothetical cases in an existing geometry were used to evaluate FBIM. The cases and their detailed processes were defined with support from Copenhagen Airport Rescue and Firefighting. The FBIM procedure for the cases were developed in iterative steps. Through this process, the case-definitions evolved, allowing the chain-of-events to be mapped and simulated by FBIM. By drawing on the experience of Fire and Rescue Brigades (FRB), the suitability of FBIM is investigated. Observations made in the process of evaluation are documented. Additionally, several scenarios, varying the number of staff and locations of the fire, has been simulated to illustrate different uses and capture different perspectives. In this document, only one case is presented.

The Case: The selected case is a fire in a parking cellar on -2nd level and involves a fire in an EV. The fire is detected by an ABA-system and shortly after, confirmed by CCTV. The case describes the process of intervention, from dispatch to suppression and to the removal and transportation of the vehicle to a safe place where it can safely burn out. Scenario 1: *first callout* of two fire appliances and four smoke-helmet teams (SHT), Scenario 2: *first callout* of one fire appliance and two SHT's. The resulting chain-of-events used in scenario one is presented in Figure 1 and shows all the steps that the officer in charge (OIC) and the four SHTs are going through. According to the Danish Standard Operation Procedures (SOP) [4] an EV fire can be controlled with one c-attack¹ and two c-attacks are required to ensure the extinguishing. Finally, it is stated that the extinguishing will take one to three hours.

Results and Discussion

An initial intervention process was set according to the FBIM method. It was iteratively adjusted according to the feedback from the FRB. The total intervention is subdivided into intervention stages (marked as triangles), consisting of several detailed steps with individual times. The accumulated time steps give the duration of the scenario. The durations of the stages are used for comparative and validation purposes. The stages are listed and defined as shown in Table 1. It is

¹ The use of a c-hose with 200 l/mina

seen that the intervention with four SHTs is 7.45% faster than the intervention with two SHT's, when comparing the initial fire control (IFC) of the fire² i.e. when the first fire attack is initiated. However, it should be noted that these results are heavily dependent on the assumptions behind the processes. For instance, the only reason for obtaining such a fast IFC for scenario 2, is that all SHT's are deployed towards the fire, without having anyone to relieve them – until the requested backup arrives. Thus, in scenario 2, all available resources are deployed without redundancy, while in scenario 1, the resources can be spared and spent from a more long-term perspective implying a more resilient and safe intervention.

Table 1: Stages of the process and corresponding times in [mm:ss]

Stages	2 SHT	4 SHT
t ₀ – FRB initiated	03:25	03:25
t ₁ – FRB Arrival times (the first on scene)	11:25	11:25
t ₂ – SHT's deployed	16:13	16:13
t ₃ – Requisition of additional resources	16:13	N/A
t ₄ – Water Supply established (to SHT 1)	21:55	21:55
t ₅ – Water Supply established (to SHT 3)	N/A	23:59
t ₆ – Attack one initiated (beginning of fire control) and first SHT in BA (t ₆ ≥ t ₄)	28:47	26:41
t ₇ – Second SHT in BA (t ₇ ≥ t ₅)	22:41	23:39
t ₈ – Attack two initiated (beginning of fire extinguishment)	39:50	40:49

It was observed that EV fires can spread to an adjacent car after 20 minutes and 30 seconds, disregarding the effects of the sprinkler system **Error! Reference source not found.**, indicating the need for early intervention and fire control. In the current case it can be seen how the number of SHT's may affect a possible flame spread. Through this process, several key issues and important concepts have been identified and gathered in the effort to ensure realistic and valid FBIM simulations by establishing a common understanding of the intervention processes.

Observations: The difference in paradigm between engineers and FRB was identified. This is seen as the most critical issue of the FBIM application, indicating the need for refined guidelines on the matter. Furthermore, the SOPs of the Danish FRB's was found to differ in several points from strategies implemented in FBIM. Not one fire or intervention will ever be the same, and all interventions are based on how the incident is 'read' by the OIC, which illustrates the great challenge of FBIM.

Conclusion

The suitability of FBIM in a Danish context was investigated. It was found that the high level of generalization within the FBIM flow charts meant the need for adaptation to describe a real case. The intervention times for IFC showed the effect of involving four SHT's instead of two, implying a more likely flame spread. FBIM has its limitations, but the method still proved valuable as it forces the engineer and the FRB's to ask the right questions and provides the means to predict, document and present challenges in fire safety, and can serve as an important baseline for pre-planning. The necessity for a

common terminology among engineers and firefighters was observed. A digital tool simulating the FBIM would be useful and the requirement for such has been identified.

Figure 1: Chain-of-events for scenario one.

Acknowledgements

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² The IFC was used as the fire dynamics of the extinguishing of the fire are out scope and is not considered here.

Wind turbine tower made of wood exposed to a campfire

Anna Sandinge
Fire and Safety
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
Borås, Sweden
anna.sandinge@ri.se

Robert McNamee
Fire and Safety
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
Lund, Sweden
robert.mcnamee@ri.se

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Wood tower, wind turbine, fire damage, flame spread

Background

The demands on using sustainable energy from renewable sources increase, and the usage of wind and solar energy becomes more common and requested. As a result, new wind turbines must be built. The towers are commonly built in steel and concrete, resulting in a heavy construction with very large parts. The transportation of these parts is often difficult. However, there are other options on construction materials. Recently, wind turbine towers have been constructed in wood [1]. The tower is built with laminated wood in modules. Benefits from using wood as the construction material are e.g. material is from a renewable source, the tower can be transported in modules, which makes the transport easier and more difficult terrain can be accessible. The material is lightweight, the weight of a wooden tower is approximately 1/3 of the weight of a steel tower.

As for all wood constructions, the fire safety is an important aspect since the material is combustible. In a recently finished research project [2], the fire performance of the wood tower was evaluated. The aim of the fire testing was to evaluate the fire behavior (spread) and fire resistance (damage) by simulating a campfire and pyromantic vandalism at the foot of the tower.

Method

The fire testing was conducted in a medium scale setup, using panels with laminated wood from the production of wooden towers in size 1x1 m. The thickness of the test samples was 100 mm, approximately 1/3 of the end use thickness. The panels were tested with two set ups, one with untreated panels and one where the panels were treated with a surface protective coating. The coating should protect the tower from weathering. No further information regarding the coating was given.

Three fire sources were used, a 30 kW burner, a 100 kW burner and a wood crib (size 300x300x300mm). The wood crib was ignited using a fibre board soaked in methanol. The exposure time for the 30 kW burner was 30 min and for 100 kW burner 60 min. The test with the wood crib was terminated when the crib was assessed as combusted, approximately after 70 min.

During the test, visual inspection was made regarding ignition, flame spread and burning behavior. Temperature

measurements were made at several locations at the panel surface using thermocouples, thin skin calorimeters and plate thermometers, see Figure 1. The thermocouples were mainly used to estimate the flame spread at the surface. The fire testing was conducted in two test rounds, where the position of the thermocouples was modified from the first round. In addition, the Heat Release Rate (HRR) was measured using oxygen consumption calorimetry. After the test, the charring depth was measured.

Figure 1. Position of thermocouples in the set-up of the two test rounds.

Result and discussion

Untreated wood panel

The panels tested with the burners, both 30 kW and 100 kW, showed the same result regarding flame spread. There was no flame spread in the panel outside of the flame exposed area. There was charring with a depth of 8 mm and 27 mm respectively in the area with constant flame exposure. In the surrounding area, the surface was slightly charred and covered with a soot layer. Outer parts of the panels were unaffected.

During the first 30 min in the wood crib test, there was only charring in the part of the panel very close to the crib, see Figure 2. There was mainly soot discoloring in the panel vertically above the crib. After 45 min of test time, there was a flame spread on both sides of the crib, horizontally. However, there was only burning in the surface and the charring was only in the upper part of the specimen. Maximum depth of the char was 11 mm.

The HRR for the panel tested with the 30 kW burner showed a production between 4-13 kW during the test time. The 100 kW test showed a HRR of 10-20 kW throughout the test. In the test with the wood crib, three peaks were observed

in the HRR, with the first peak at 50 kW and the following two at approximately 20 kW. Noticeable is that the HRR from the wood crib is included in these results.

Figure 2. Fire development of unprotected wood panel when exposed to a burning wood crib.

Panel with coating

In all three tests of the panels with the protective coating, there was a flame spread at the surface. In the test with the 30 kW burner, there was a flame spread all over the surface. In the tests with the 100 kW burner and with the wood crib, there was a flame spread all over the surface with exception for the upper right corner. During these tests, there were some slight side winds in the lab and the flame source leaned towards the left side of the panel.

In the tests with the burners, the charring depth was 20-22 mm. For the wood crib test, the char depth was 25 mm in the area close to the wood crib. The charring vertically from the wood crib was 7-11 mm.

Figure 3. Fire development of wood panel with coating when exposed to a burning wood crib.

Regarding the HRR, in the 30 kW test, three peaks were observed between 80-100 kW. In the 100 kW burner test, only one peak was observed at 170 kW, then a steady HRR at approximately 25 kW. In the wood crib test, four peaks were observed between 35-145 kW. However, this HRR includes the contribution from the wood crib.

For the panels treated with the coating, there was a slower flame spread in the wood crib test compared to the tests with burners. It took longer time for the wood crib to have a high fire load.

The HRR show a variation in the tests and the maximum measured value is presented in Table 1. The peak HRR is significantly higher for the panels with the coating.

The char depth of the panel, for the unprotected wood, showed a higher value for the 100 kW burner. This is expected as the fire source is higher. For the panels with the coating, the char depth is similar for all fire sources.

Table 1. Fire development of unprotected wood panel when exposed to a burning wood crib.

Panel	Ignition source	HRR _{max} (kW)	Depth of char* (mm)
Untreated wood	Burner 30 kW	13	8
	Burner 100 kW	37	27
	Wood crib	52**	11
Panel with coating	Burner 30 kW	108	20
	Burner 100 kW	181	22
	Wood crib	149**	25

* The maximum observed depth of the char into the panel, close to the fire source.

** The HRR from the wood crib is included in the results.

Conclusions

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect from a fire to the wood tower, outside of the tower. The main fire scenario was identified as a campfire very close to the tower, or someone consciously trying to cause damage by igniting a fire at the foot of the tower.

The testing showed that, for the unprotected wood panel, there was no significant flame spread and the burnt damage was in the area of the fire sources. For the panels with the applied coating, a flame spread was observed all the way to the top surface of the specimen, resulting in a higher HRR. The burning behavior and the flame spread are directly related to the properties of the coating. From these tests, it is not possible to conclude if there will be a flame spread upwards the full tower so when using this type of coating products further investigation is needed.

The depth of the char is highest close to the fire source, with the highest value of 27 mm. A fire of around one hour, like the ones used in the study, is not likely to cause severe damage in depth of the wood construction.

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Timber joist storey partitions

A theoretical and experimental determination and comparison of the fire resistance of a load bearing floor construction subjected to the standard temperature-time curve

Rasmus Brylle

Scandi Supply a/s

Vissenbjerg, Denmark

rb@scandisupply.dk

Keywords:

EN 1365-2, Medium-rise-buildings, Fire-resistance, Combustible-storey-partitions, Sustainability.

Abstract

Timber joist storey partitions (from here on mentioned as "TJSP"), defined as a floor construction of timber joists (see Fig. 1), originated within the Scandinavian building tradition as storey partitions for medium-rise buildings, and was the predominant type of horizontal storey partition in Danish construction for more than 300 years (see Fig. 2), where the construction type was known as "træbjælkelag" [literally translated as "Timber joist layer"].

TJSP were historically classified with a fire resistance rating of BD60 by the 2. Danish building code, *Bygningsreglement 1966*[1], according to the national *Danish Standard DS 1052.1* [2], prior to the implementation of the European classification system in 2002, where the previous national classification of BD60 correlates reasonably well with the European performance criteria of (R)EI60 (as defined in EN 13501-2[3]).

Figure 1 - Timber joist storey partition

The fire rating properties of TJSPs have been questioned by fire safety professionals[4] prior to its implementation in *Bygningsreglement 1966*[1], but despite the criticism, the rating of BD60 remains for TJSPs. Likewise, determining the historical roots of the BD60 classification has proven difficult, and thus gaining access to any relevant test-data used for the classification. As terminating the use of already commissioned TJSPs is unfeasible, more empirical data was needed to qualify if additional fire protection measures should be considered when renovating buildings with TJSPs.

To acquire more data and to assess the capabilities of the TJSP construction, a TJSP test specimen was constructed and subjected to a fire test in accordance with the standard temperature-time curve (ISO 834-1[5]). The findings from the test showed that fire protrudes from the unloaded test specimen prior to the 60 minutes mark. Additionally, the discovery of the impact of the cavities in the TJSP on the heat transfer through the structure was noted as interesting. Equally significant, the test revealed that smoke transfer is an issue of concern that must be further emphasized and addressed.

Historical context of TJSP in Denmark

Storey partitions are a crucial element of hindering fire from propagating upwards internally in a building. By the early 19th century non-combustible structures were considered more fireproof and storey partitions using steel, cast-iron and concrete began emerging in the USA and Europe, whereas the TJSP was still the prevalent structure used in Denmark until the 1960s (see *SBI rapport 142*[6]) -shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Timeline of prevalence of storey partitions

Despite the historical prevalence of the TJSP construction well within the 20th century, there are only few main sources relating to its classification as BD60: (list not exhaustive)

I: The earliest source found is *Brandværnshåndbogen af 1929-31*[7] supplemented by *Brandtekniske meddelelser, Fortryk Nr.-[8]* in 1933, both stating that:

“Such a floor separation is, if not fireproof, nevertheless very resistant and burns through rather slowly, where it is not a particularly violent fire”.

II: *Brandsikring, Bygningsmæssige foranstaltninger*[4] mentions actual tests carried out by ”statsprøveanstalten” and the author, Børge Johannes Rambøll, herein mentions knowledge of numerous accounts of actual fires penetrating a BD 60 classified storey partition, where the actual fires resulted in the structures failing significantly faster compared to the results from the test lab. The results from the tests are not available.

III: Vidar Stenstads PhD, *Eldre murgårdar og brann*[9] mentions the Norwegian structure “Stubbloft”, which is similar to the TJSP structure, as having a fire resistance of 40-60 minutes. Likewise, a test conducted in 1953 for “Stubbloft” exposed to the ISO 834[5], resulting in the termination of the test at $t=29$ min, is mentioned in *Eldre murgårdar og brann*[9].

IV: *Brandtekniske fejl og mangler i bygninger*[10] mentions the timber joist structure with an assumed fire resistance of approximately one hour in reference to “normalbrandprøven”, with no further reference. Since the globally acknowledged temperature-time curve was introduced in 1917 and published by the National Bureau of Standards in 1921, it is reasonable to assume that “normalbrandprøven” correlates to the standardized ISO 834-1[11] temperature-time curve.

The above cited sources are all inconclusive regarding the testing of TJSPs in relation to BD60, why a test specimen was prepared with the purpose of performing an actual test of the TJSP in relation to the standardized ISO 834-1[11] temperature-time curve.

The test specimen

The test specimen was built according with the specifications given in *Byggelov af 29. Marts 1939*[12] (see Figure 3), as the specifications includes the majority of structures that are still currently implemented in buildings, mainly in Copenhagen but as well across Denmark, as of today.

The test specimen was 2000*2010 mm. The test was conducted without a working load. The test used a furnace smaller than the minimum size required for an accredited *EN 1365-2*[13] test.

Figure 3 - Timber joist structure layout.

Test results

At $t=58$ minutes, fire was protruding from the test specimen, and the test was terminated (see Figure 4).

The results gained from the test are conditional to the test-specimen and the test-setup, which utilised a furnace smaller than specified for an accredited test.

The deviation in the size of the furnace in the described test setup compared to the larger furnace in an accredited test, would result in a higher degree of turbulence in the larger furnace, which would stress the test-specimen further due to the increased turbulence inside the cavities of the test-specimen.

Figure 4 - Eradication of layers over time

Conclusion

As such, it seems reasonable to assume that a test-specimen would need to be able to excessively withstand the durability criteria beyond the 60 minutes in the smaller furnace, if the specimen was to comply with the 60 minutes criteria in the full-scale test scenario (regarding both the E and I criteria), as the turbulence effect would be more pronounced in the larger furnace, as well as the addition and impact of the required working load.

Therefore, it is concluded that the particular timber joist structure is not able to withstand 60 minutes of exposure to the standard temperature-time curve (ISO 834[5]).

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Comparing Empirical Ignition Models for Wood-Based Materials with Cone Calorimeter Experiment

Vikas Shettihalli
Anandreddy
Dept. of Fire and Safety
RISE Research Institutes of
Sweden (RISE),
Borås, Sweden

Johan Anderson
Dept. of Fire and Safety
RISE Research Institutes of
Sweden (RISE),
Borås, Sweden

Robert McNamee
Dept. of Fire and Safety
RISE Research Institutes of
Sweden (RISE),
Borås, Sweden

Lund University (LTH),
Lund, Sweden

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Ignition time, Cone calorimeter, Wood-based materials, Empirical models.

Abstract

This study assesses multiple empirical models designed to predict the ignition time of combustible materials. It specifically examines their performance by comparing them to cone calorimeter results for four distinct wood-based materials: medium-density fiberboard, particleboard, oriented strand board, and plywood. Main finding is that none of the models accurately predict ignition times at a heat flux of 20 kW/m² for any of the materials. However, at elevated heat flux levels of 35 and 50 kW/m², most models demonstrate a low Mean Absolute Error, with only a few exceptions.

Materials

The different wood-based materials used in this study is presented in Table 1. All materials were conditioned in a climate of 23°C and RH 50 % for a period of over four weeks before the test. Average density measured at the time of the cone test and the moisture content was estimated by weight determined by drying to equilibrium at 105°C are presented in the table.

Table 1. Material density and moisture content.

Materials	Density (kg/m ³)	Moisture (%)
MDF	793	5.9
Particleboard	705	7.1
OSB	787	6.8
Plywood	491	6.9

Experiments

The Cone Calorimeter experiment, following ISO 5660-1 standards, was conducted to assess the response of different materials to varying heat flux levels (20 kW/m², 35 kW/m², and 50 kW/m²). These tests were conducted in triplicate, and the results showed a high degree of consistency across all trials for each material. During these experiments, various parameters were recorded, including heat release rate, ignition time, mass loss rate, and several other relevant factors.

In addition to the Cone Calorimeter tests, Transient Plane Source (TPS) measurements were performed. These measurements aimed to determine the thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity of the materials.

Ignition models

Several studies in the literature include investigations of piloted ignition of wood-based materials. From these, a subset of equations for validation is collected. The selected equations are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Ignition models.

Models	Equations
Tewarson [1]	$t_{ig} = \frac{\pi (k\rho C)(T_{ig} - T_0)^2}{4 (q_e'' - q_{cr}'')^2}$
Quintiere [2]	$t_{ig} = \frac{\pi (k\rho C)(T_{ig} - T_0)^2}{4 (q_e'')^2}$
Babrauskas [3]	$t_{ig} = \frac{130\rho^{0.73}}{(q_e'' - 11.0)^{1.82}}$
Hallman [4]	$t_{ig} = \frac{1035(k\rho C)^{0.75}(T_{ig} - T_0)^{1.04}}{(\alpha_s q_e'')^2}$
Wickström [5]	$t_{ig} = \frac{\pi(k\rho C)}{4} \left[\frac{T_{ig} - T_0}{\varepsilon(q_e'' - 0.8\sigma T_{ig}^4) - 0.8h_{con}(T_{ig} - T_g)} \right]^2$

Where, t_{ig} is time for ignition, $k\rho C$ thermal inertia, product of thermal conductivity (kW/m²K), density (kg/m³), specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K), T_{ig} ignition temperature (K), T_0 ambient temperature (K), q_e'' external heat flux (kW/m²), q_{cr}'' critical heat flux (kW/m²), h_{con} convective heat transfer coefficient (W/m²K).

For all models except Quintiere's, the thermal inertia was determined at room temperature. However, for Quintiere's model, the thermal inertia was derived from cone experiment data using the slope of the line representing heat flux versus $t^{0.5}$. At lower heat flux levels (20 kW/m²), the ignition temperature (T_{ig}) was set at 250 °C, while at higher heat flux levels (35, 50 kW/m²), temperatures of 400 °C, 422 °C, 368 °C, and 364 °C

were assigned for MDF, particleboard, OSB, and plywood respectively, as specified in [6]. The heat transfer coefficient was assumed to be 11 (W/m²K) [10].

Results and Discussion

A comparison between the ignition times obtained from cone calorimeter tests and the predicted ignition times from various ignition models along with the mean absolute error are presented in Table 3. The mean absolute error (MAE) for each cone test result is calculated as follows:

$$MAE = \frac{abs|t_{ig1} - M| + abs|t_{ig2} - M| + abs|t_{ig3} - M|}{3}$$

Where t_{ig1} , t_{ig2} , t_{ig3} , represent the ignition times from three cone calorimeter tests, and M denotes the predicted ignition times. The MAE is chosen because it gives the average magnitude error in the same units as the original data and is less sensitive to outliers compared to other error metrics.

The total smoke production from the cone experiments, recorded from the start to ignition are shown in Table 4.

Table 3. Comparison of average ignition time values between cone calorimeter experiment (Cone) with standard deviation between tests, and ignition models with mean absolute error (MAE)

Material	Model	Ignition time (s)		
		20 (kW/m ²)	35 (kW/m ²)	50 (kW/m ²)
MDF	Cone	187 (16)	59 (2)	32 (2)
	Tewarson	326 (139)	55 (3)	29 (3)
	Quintiere	220 (32)	72 (13)	35 (3)
	Babrauskas	331 (124)	52 (6)	21 (10)
	Hallman	218 (30)	59 (1)	34 (3)
	Wickström	95 (92)	53 (5)	31 (3)
Particleboard	Cone	178 (5)	59 (1)	29 (2)
	Tewarson	295 (117)	56 (2)	26 (3)
	Quintiere	198 (19)	65 (5)	31 (2)
	Babrauskas	286 (107)	48 (11)	19 (9)
	Hallman	202 (24)	55 (4)	32 (2)
	Wickström	86 (92)	56 (2)	28 (3)
OSB	Cone	234 (26)	52 (2)	26 (2)
	Tewarson	370 (136)	51 (2)	32 (6)
	Quintiere	126 (107)	41 (10)	20 (5)
	Babrauskas	310 (76)	52 (2)	21 (2)
	Hallman	240 (23)	65 (13)	38 (12)
	Wickström	107 (126)	48 (3)	26 (3)
Plywood	Cone	306 (88)	36 (3)	20 (2)
	Tewarson	161 (145)	22 (13)	13 (6)
	Quintiere	109 (197)	35 (3)	17 (3)
	Babrauskas	220 (100)	37 (2)	15 (6)
	Hallman	124 (181)	33 (3)	19 (2)
	Wickström	45 (261)	25 (10)	15 (8)

The table provides valuable insights. Primarily, all models demonstrate generally close predictions of ignition times at high heat flux levels, with a low mean absolute error, barring a few exceptions (8 out of 40).

However, at low heat flux level, there is a discrepancy as the models tend to overpredict ignition time compared to experimental values. Notably, Wickström's model deviates from this trend by underpredicting ignition time at 20 kW/m². Additionally, the Quintiere model underestimates ignition time for OSB at the same heat flux level.

The deviation observed at low heat flux levels could be attributed to several factors. As mentioned in [7], the ignition

process of wood differs notably from that at high heat flux, likely due to increased charring of the materials before ignition, as evident from Table 4, showing higher total smoke production at 20 kW/m² compared to high heat flux levels. Additionally, Babrauskas [3, 6] noted that the prediction of ignition times tends to be close to the root mean square of 64%. In addition to the factors mentioned, it's worth considering that the surface finish of the material could also influence ignition time.

Interestingly, for plywood, all models consistently underpredict ignition time at low heat flux. The experimental ignition times for plywood vary widely, ranging from 198 to 414 seconds, with a standard deviation of 88 seconds, highlighting a significant range of values at low heat flux levels. Despite plywood's lower thermal conductivity, specific heat, and density, it ignites later than other materials at low heat flux. Furthermore, Table 4 indicates notably higher total smoke production from plywood at 20 kW/m² compared to other materials. Conversely, at high heat flux levels, plywood ignites earlier than other materials, contrary to its behavior at low heat flux, a trend also reflected in the total smoke production data.

Table 4. Average total smoke production (m²/m²) from start to ignition in cone calorimeter tests for all materials at different heat flux levels (values represent average of three tests)

Material	20 kW/m ²	35 kW/m ²	50 kW/m ²
MDF	38.87	14.47	5.93
Particleboard	32.30	13.60	6.93
OSB	52.10	9.17	4.63
Plywood	106.90	7.67	5.90

Conclusions

The ignition models studied, generally, show poor prediction of ignition times at a heat flux of 20 kW/m². However, at elevated heat flux levels of 35 and 50 kW/m², most models gave close predictions. It was further noticed that Plywood demonstrated significant differences in ignition behaviour compared to the other wood products studied.

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Marine Transportation of Energy Storage Systems

Hazard Assessment and Regulatory Analysis

Jonatan Gehandler, Joanne Ellis, Anna Kralsson, and Maria Quant
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB
Borås/Göteborg, Sweden

Guy Colonna
FSL Consulting, LLC
Maine, USA

Victoria Hutchison
Fire Protection Research
Foundation (FPRF)
Quincy, USA

Keywords: *energy storage systems, battery, hazard, marine transportation*

Abstract

To leverage renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, to their full potential, efficient solutions for storing this energy for use at a later time are required. Systems that are capable of storing energy from renewable energy sources are called energy storage systems (ESS), defined as an energy storage device consisting of an outer casing containing a large-format power cell (e.g., battery) as well as the necessary ancillary subsystems for physical support, protection, thermal management, and control. As many of these systems are manufactured overseas, they will likely be transported globally as cargo aboard marine vessels. Given the confined nature of a vessel's cargo hold, the restricted access or inaccessibility of some areas by response personnel, and the reduced number of response resources at sea compared to on land, safety measures must be followed or applied to ensure identified safety issues or concerns are mitigated.

Thus, this study, contracted by Transport Canada, was initiated to conduct a hazard assessment of ESS in enclosed cargo spaces during marine transport. An enclosed space means any space within which, in the absence of artificial ventilation, the ventilation will be limited and any explosive atmosphere will not be dispersed naturally.

Commercially available ESS types and related regulations have been reviewed and summarized based on the available literature, and data about the physical and chemical characteristics and behaviour of these systems under various conditions has been collected and analysed. Applicable regulatory requirements, including United Nations (UN) regulations, when available, have been identified for marine transport of the various ESS types identified. Additionally, vessel types used for marine transport have been identified, as well as the safety and response systems required for dangerous goods transport for each type of vessel. The ESS types within the scope of this study include the following:

- Lithium ion batteries (LIBs)
- Sodium ion batteries (SIBs)
- Lead-acid and nickel-, zinc-, and sodium-based batteries (excluding SIBs)
- Flow batteries
- Electro-chemical capacitors
- Phase change materials (PCM)
- Thermo-chemical heat storages (TCHS)

A hazard assessment (HAZID) for ESS in marine transport has been conducted. The purpose of the HAZID was to account for credible hazardous scenarios by identifying possible failures and their potential consequences, as well as to review safeguards designed to mitigate the relevant risk for the identified hazardous scenarios. Eight initiating conditions or scenarios were derived and used as what-if scenarios to guide the hazard identification process, including, for example, exposure to extreme temperatures or salt water. The input received from the HAZID workshop, interviews with subject matter experts, and insights from those with experience shipping ESS via marine vessels, and gap analysis resulted in the following key findings:

1. The state of charge (SOC) is an important risk factor for many types of BESS. The higher the SOC, the more sensitive and reactive the BESS will be. Some types of BESS can be transported at 0 % SOC without being damaged, which lowers the hazards and risks they pose considerably. Despite this fact, the SOC is not currently regulated for transport in the IMDG Code. However, targeting an SOC of approximately 30 % for LIBs is a common best practice, and it is mandatory for aviation transport via the International Civil Aviation Organization Technical Instructions (ICAO TI)
2. While the IMDG Code permits stowing BESS under deck, interviews with manufacturers and shipping operators revealed that the preferred practice for shipping LIBs is on deck for containerships [see (a) below for additional context] or in a ro-ro space [see (b) below for additional context]. Justification for this position is provided in the following points,

which were expressed during the HAZID, interviews, knowledge gap and regulatory analysis of this project:

- a) The crew is typically not allowed in containership cargo holds, which means that they cannot inspect the cargo or take any manual action in case of emergency apart from discharging the available fixed fire-extinguishing systems, most commonly carbon dioxide systems, which might not be effective on battery fires and represent a one-shot mitigation approach.
 - b) Ro-ro spaces and cargo spaces on deck can be inspected, making manual mitigation measures possible. Fixed fire-extinguishing systems, most often water-based systems, are also available in ro-ro spaces.
 - c) If a BESS goes into failure mode, many will vent gases, including hydrogen and methane, which can accumulate in enclosed spaces and create an explosive atmosphere.
3. The detection of ESS failures and onboard firefighting response capabilities that meet the current minimum requirements are insufficient for the challenges that ESS represent. Based on interviews with vessel operators, it has been determined that enhanced means for the detection and evaluation of hazardous conditions within cargo containers or cargo spaces could be considered. Such means include fixed and manual gas detection, Infrared (IR) cameras, and similar tools. Firefighting response tools are not currently regulated for specific ESS cargoes, so additional tools and practices should be considered, see Figure 1.
 4. There is uncertainty regarding the requirements for the outer housings of large-format LIB ESS. The outer housing of ESS transported under UN 3536, "Lithium batteries installed in cargo transport unit: lithium ion batteries or lithium-metal batteries," might not necessarily comply with the same requirements as a freight container, and the regulations for outer housings are ambiguous.
 5. Shipping lines expressed concern with transporting used or recycled batteries.

Figure 1. Manual firefighting and cooling of container. Photo: permission granted by Evergreen.

Battery Explosion SAFETY for first responders (BESAFE)

Elena Funk

Danish Institute of Fire and Security Technology (DBI),
Department of Energy and Transport,
Hvidovre, Denmark
efu@dbigroup.dk

Ana Sauca

Danish Institute of Fire and Security Technology (DBI),
Department of Fire Engineering Buildings,
Hvidovre, Denmark

Blanca Andres

Danish Institute of Fire and Security Technology (DBI),
Department of Energy and Transport,
Hvidovre, Denmark

Konrad Wilkens

Lund University (LTH),
Division of Fire Safety Engineering,
Lund, Sweden

Keywords: *battery fire safety, battery fire, battery explosion, firefighting tactics*

Abstract

DBI, in partnership with firefighters and key stakeholders including Rednings- og SikkerhedsCenter (RESC), Hovedstadens Beredskab (HBR), Østjyllands Brandvæsen, and Stena Recycling A/S, has launched a project titled BESAFE (Battery Explosion SAFETY). This initiative aims to address safety concerns related to fire and explosion hazard due to batteries. The main goal is to generate data for size-up and tactical decisions for firefighters during residential fires. Additionally, the project will address water and air pollution risks from battery fires. These goals will be achieved by a series of tests performed using second-life batteries. The first tests series will characterize the off-gas composition. The second test series will assess the explosion hazard in closed compartment and serve as a platform for testing and assessing different firefighting tactics. The main outcome of these tests will be recommendations for the size-up and tactical decisions for a battery fire in a residential setting.

Introduction

In early 2023, DBI performed a series of large-scale Electric Vehicle (EV) fire tests at RESC where two out of three EVs underwent deflagration [1]. The battery off-gassed into a car cabin, and after some time, the accumulated gases ignited, causing an explosion (deflagration) that not only forced open the car compartment but also damaged a nearby wall. While it was generally understood that confining a battery fire could lead to a gas explosion, witnessing the event brought its gravity to the forefront. Such an incident prompted firefighters and DBI to consider whether current knowledge and strategies are adequately equipped to handle a similar hazard in a residential setting, leading to the inception of this project.

Over the past decade, battery technology has advanced, expanding the range of battery applications, feeding the increased consumer demand. Uncertified second-life batteries are increasingly found in places like homes and waste facilities, posing risks to emergency services. The

public's access to batteries, including second-hand ones through online platforms [2], enables unregulated construction of Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) without essential safety measures. Hence, a scenario choice for the large-scale tests is a second-life battery failure in a closed compartment.

The project engages a technical advisory board to receive support and input, ensuring the incorporation of firefighting tactics and battery fire dynamics knowledge from other research groups and firefighters from different countries. The project is internally funded by each of the partners.

State of the art

A number of accidents involving batteries as the cause of explosions have been reported [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. Firefighting services have responded to these incidents at different stages with some instances of injuries, death [3], [8] or near-misses [15]. These reports show the breadth of firefighting tactics used when responding to such fires, from active gas measurements and opening the compartment [3] to passive defensive tactics [5] and an exchange of gas in the fire compartment with nitrogen [4]. Recent and past studies on firefighting tactics considerations made by UL, FSRI provide valuable learnings for this study [3], [16].

A review of firefighting guidelines in the Nordic countries for battery fires has been performed. Denmark's BRS has issued a guideline on fighting fires in EVs [17] but is missing recommendations on battery fires in other settings. The Norwegian guideline on risk assessment for battery fires for first responders is considered state of the art and contains a lot of useful information [18]. In Sweden current knowledge on the topic has been disseminated in form of an educational video [19]. Meanwhile, the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) is in the process of drafting a battery guideline, which will include a dedicated chapter on explosions. Finland's firefighter's guideline Tokeva 2021 [20] includes instruction T9b on lithium-ion batteries. This instruction is divided into several parts: tasks and organization of the rescue formation, risk factors, hazard zone, PPE, means and procedures. When it comes to

explosion hazard Tokeva 2021 recommends removal of ignition sources and ventilation.

Lithium-ion fires have been reported to have distinct fire dynamics when it comes to smoke stratification at the start of thermal runaway [16]. There is currently no way to determine when arriving at a fire scene in a residential setting whether the ongoing fire includes a battery, and no clear recommendations on how to assess an explosion risk in that situation. The visual, thermal imaging and gas meter indicators were reported to be of no use in the latest study [16]. Recommendations include wearing full PPE when performing size up and avoiding approach to a building for performance of gas measurements where a battery is suspected to be present.

Research goal and objectives

Based on the literature review, the primary goal of this project is to increase the knowledge on emergency response strategies for battery fires in residential settings, in particular where an explosion risk is present. To achieve this, DBI, in collaboration with other partners (National Research Center for Working Environment, Lund University), will develop and conduct a series of battery fire tests. These tests will be specifically designed to study the explosion hazards that batteries pose to firefighters.

The research objectives include examining and quantifying various aspects related to battery explosions. These aspects encompass assessing the risks for firefighters associated with battery explosions in closed compartments, evaluating firefighting tactics such as ventilation and water suppression to mitigate explosion hazards, identifying the presence of water pollutants in the run-off water following a battery fire, and measuring the exposure of firefighters to hazardous gases, aerosols and particles during the firefighting process. The objectives of the project are subject to expansion as discussions with partners about different measuring techniques and post-fire analysis of battery debris are ongoing.

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Study of Temperature Conditions of Electric Vehicle Post-crash

Daniel Darnikowski
Maritime Advanced Research Centre (CTO)
Gdańsk, Poland
e-mail: daniel.darnikowski@cto.gda.pl

Magdalena Mieloszyk
Institute of Fluid Flow Machinery,
Polish Academy of Sciences
Gdańsk, Poland

Keywords: electric vehicle, fire safety, fire resistance, R100, RESS

Abstract

Following article studies the post-crash fire safety testing standard for the electric vehicles in terms of its repeatability of the conditions during the tests.

Temperature conditions are monitored over the set of tests and statistical data is shown in graphical form. A significant deviation was found during the initial phase of the exposure between 600-900°C. Study is aimed to be extended to provide further data.

Introduction

The rise of electric vehicles in the recent years and the future initiatives, aiming to resign from internal combustion engines, caused major an increase in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) applications in power train [1]. Despite the fact LIBs are deemed generally safe to use, number of fire incidents with EVs has raised.

EV fire has a largely different characteristic from the petrol-based fire plume [2], such as the battery can re-ignite multiple days or weeks after the accident, smoke compounds emitting from the fire are toxic and are exceeding lethal doses particularly in enclosed structures [3], and the fire requires large volumes of water to cool-down the battery. To avoid such fires of EVs, the battery is tested against fire resistance according to the given standard that is required in particular region. For European market, the fire resistance testing procedure is described by Regulation No. 100 series .03 [4] (abbreviated R100.03) and is mandatory to undertake before the battery is allowed for sale.

The aim of this study is to test the stability of temperature conditions of R100.03 testing standard throughout a number of tests. It is expected the conditions will have a small margin of variance of temperature in between the tests, due to the fact the outcome of the test decides whether the LIB is allowed for commercial use.

Experimental set-up

Test set-up for R100.03 testing consists of stationary rectangular pans for gasoline as a heat source and the two movable carts with a specimen (LIB) and brick screen. The dimensions of the pan were adjusted according to R100.03 procedure and were 200 to 500 mm larger than the specimen

(width and length wise). The pans were filled with petrol usage of 20 l/m² and laid below with water. Testing rig was sheltered from the wind to keep the wind requirements below 2.5 km/h.

R100.03 fire resistance testing standard consists of four phases:

- A – pre-heating of the petrol, petrol is ignited and allow to burn for at least 60 s or less provided ambient conditions were above 20°C.
- B – direct exposure the flame, specimen is placed directly over fire for at least 70 s.
- C – indirect exposure to fire, specimen is kept directly over fire with intermediate brick screen for at least 60 s
- D – observation phase; specimen is observed until temperature is levelled or 3 hours expire.

Transition periods between the phases are not standardised and are dependent on the specification of the testing rig.

Figure 1. Thermocouple sets positioning on the surface of the DUT.

Measurement instrumentation included type K thermocouples placed on the outer surfaces of the device under test (DUT) on all of the sides (see Figure 1), as well as anemometer, ambient thermometer and humidity sensor.

The locations of thermocouple sets were following:

- Centre bottom side – 15cm below the bottom surface of the DUT.
- Centre top side – adhered to the top surface centre.
- Left, right, front and back side – adhered to the given surface side.

Test set-up for R100.03 testing consists of stationary rectangular pans for gasoline as a heat source and the two movable carts with a specimen (LIB) and brick screen. The dimensions of the pan were adjusted according to R100.03 procedure and were 200 to 500 mm larger than the specimen (width and length wise). The pans were filled with petrol usage of 20 l/m² and laid below with water. Testing rig was sheltered from the wind to keep the wind requirements below 2.5 km/h at the level of the pan and 500mm above.

Ten tests were performed on a range of battery assemblies (referred as battery energy storage system or rechargeable energy storage system). Sizes of device under test (DUT) and pans with gasoline were listed in Table 1, together with the coverage (DUT surface size compared to pan size).

Table 1. Dataset of DUT and pan areas as well as coverage of pan in comparison to DUT.

Test No	DUT Area, m ²	Pan Area, m ²	Coverage, %
1	0,85	1,60	46,9
2	1,10	2,05	46,1
3	1,22	1,89	35,4
4	0,81	1,48	45,3
5	1,06	2,06	48,6
6	1,05	2,10	50,2
7	1,00	1,61	37,9
8	0,23	0,58	60,0
9	0,62	1,24	50,3
10	0,68	1,24	45,4

All tests included battery assemblies intended for homologation purposes and real-life applications such as vehicle powertrain. Size of the battery base was based on the individual project end-use.

Partial results

Set of data from ten tests were accumulated and analysed. The mean, maximum and minimum temperatures, as well as standard deviation were calculated for each of the thermocouples with differentiation of the phases A, B, C and D. The data was standardised to exclude transition times between phases.

Phase B time-temperature curve of centre bottom thermocouples were presented in the Figure 2. Centre bottom thermocouple represent the temperature in the centreline of the flame, thus it is expected to have the highest temperature and the most stable. The data shows the temperature is levelled after 20-30 s at about 700°C. There is, however, a significant deviation which can range between 600-900°C.

During phase C shown in Figure 3, temperature is stabilised at 700°C with noticeably smaller deviation ranging between 800-900°C. This shows the use of perforated brick screen do not influence temperature in the centreline of the flame.

Additionally, it can be noticed the conditions above the fire reached equilibrium and do not fluctuate throughout the phase C. This shows the intention of phase A (pre-ignition) to stabilise the flame temperature is probably too short.

Figure 2. Time-temperature curve of the centre bottom thermocouples during phase B. Blue line – mean temperature, blue area – standard deviation area, orange line – maximal temperature, green line – minimal temperature.

Figure 3. Time-temperature curve of the centre bottom thermocouples during phase C. Blue line – mean temperature, blue area – standard deviation area, orange line – maximal temperature, green line – minimal temperature.

Further study

Work presented in the article is to be followed with additional five tests with various size DUT. The obtained data will be further analysed and the correlations between temperature conditions, wind velocity, pan and DUT size will be examined.

Complete dataset will be then judged in terms of repeatability and accuracy of the set conditions.

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Pressurisation as a part of firefighting in buildings

Joel Jacobsson
Southern Älvsborg
Fire service
PhD Lund University
Lund, Sweden
Joel.jacobsson@serf.se

Haukur Ingason
Adjunct professor
Lund University & RISE
Sweden

Marcus Runefors
Senior lecturer
Lund University
Sweden

Keywords:

Pressurisation, firefighting, fan

Abstract

Many fire services employ pressurisation techniques using mobile fans to prevent the spread of combustion products between compartments within a building. Pressurisation is performed by blowing air into an unaffected compartment with limited openings to achieve excess pressure in relation to the fire-affected enclosure. The purpose is usually protection of property in unaffected parts of the building. The motivation can also be to create better ingress routes for the fire services and improve the evacuation situation for people evacuation. Pressurisation of stairwells has been extensively studied in the literature, especially in taller buildings.

Pressurisation as a method has several potential advantages in firefighting in buildings and knowledge has been obtained both from scientific works as well as by experience of the rescue service gained over a long period of time. Three important aspects of pressurization have been identified that are important for its usefulness as a tactic for the fire service. One is that it allows control of long boundaries between the affected and unaffected compartment. The second aspect is that it requires less manpower and materials compared to other firefighting actions. Third, since the tactic does not require water, it can be expected that the need to handle contaminated water from the scene is reduced.

The main objective of this study is to find out what is required to obtain successful pressurisation in practice. The underlying physics behind pressurisation is simple, the pressure in the adjacent room needs to be larger than the total pressure caused by the fire (see fig 1), but real fires are more complex with multiple leaks both between compartments and between compartments and outside. It is important to understand this full complexity to determine where pressurization can be effective.

Figure 1. A schematic layout of a pressurisation of adjacent enclosure in order to prevent the spread of combustion products and flames. The pressurisation conditions are given as a graph beside the fire room. The graph shows pressure in fire room (PF), in adjacent room (PA) and atmosphere (PO).

The main objective is to find out what factors influence the pressure on the fire-exposed side and what factors are needed to obtain higher pressure in the adjacent enclosure. The pressure in the fire room can be divided into static pressure and dynamic pressure. The static pressure has a direct correlation to temperature and height [1], while the dynamic pressure is connected to inertial flows in the fire compartments, such as the ceiling jet. Well-established theories can be used to show that the static pressure is expected to be the dominant factor in the total pressure. The height of the smoke layer will be a factor, as well as if the flames that reach into the hot gas layer at the ceiling, since the gas temperature will be higher together with a more complex flow structure. The heat release rate of the fire will most likely affect both aspects of the total pressure. The over-pressure can be estimated based on the geometry of the building and the development of the fire.

Besides the sources of overpressure mentioned above, a period of large overpressure in the early phases of fire development, due to gas expansion, is often experienced. This overpressure is generally too high for pressurization (typically several hundred Pascal) but is rarely of relevance for the fire service since they are usually related to small fires easily handled through conventional suppression techniques.

Besides the pressure profile generated by the fire, the ability to form an overpressure on the adjacent side is critical for successful pressurisation [2]. The capacity of a single fan is generally known, but the ability to generate sufficient overpressure is also affected by the total number of

available fans and the possibility of placing them toward the unaffected part of the building. If the volume of the enclosure that is to be pressurised is elevated from the ground level, it will be more difficult to keep the pressure up. The geometry of the building matters. Number of openings, type of openings and more. Another factor that needs to be addressed is the leakage area in the pressurised enclosure. For a given total fan capacity, the larger the area of leakage to ambient, more likely it is that the pressure in the adjacent enclosure will fail to overcome the pressure generated by the fire.

Another question that will be addressed in the project is how smoke control systems integrated in the building affect the possibility of pressurisation. There are different systems and solutions regarding smoke controls in buildings. There are both fans and hatches, the latter more common in industrial buildings, the first more likely to be found in buildings with high people density. If the system activates and reduces the pressure in the fire room that will be a huge advantage in a successful pressurisation. If the system instead operates in the adjacent enclosure, it may decrease the possibilities to maintain the pressure at a given level.

It is worth mentioning that pressurisation generally works at low pressures with only a few pascals. The possibility to influence these pressures can have a large impact on the spread of the fire. Since pressurisation will mean that fresh air is forced into the fire room, local combustion can also occur in connection with openings. If there is combustible material in openings, these will burn and the influence of combustible materials in the compartment walls is that the combustible material will participate in the combustion.

Model-scale experiments and theoretical analysis of required pressure differences has been carried out by Heskestad [3]. In this project, the ability of FDS to reproduce the results will be investigated. If successful, this will allow extrapolating the results to full-scale enclosures relevant for fire suppression.

Figure 2 Pressure distribution in simulation of one of the model-scale experiments in Heskestad[3].

The research is a part of the PhD study carried out at the department of Fire Safety Engineering at Lund University.

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The safety culture in the Norwegian fire service

Eivind Holm Nøttveit
University of Stavanger,
(UIS)
Stavanger, Norway
elvino@live.no

Eivind Lars Rake
University of Stavanger,
(UIS)
Stavanger, Norway
eivind.rake@lyse.net

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Safety culture, fire service, fire and rescue, HSE, improving.

Introduction

It is well known that firefighters have a significantly increased risk of accidents and health damage during the daily work in connection with emergency call – outs. The function and tasks of the fire service are constantly evolving in sync with societal changes. Emerging threats and shifts in the risk landscape facing the fire department lead to increased demands for the personnel and the need for wider focus upon work environment and risk management. Presently, the fire service responds to new types of incidents such as fires involving lithium batteries, climate-related events and situations involving ongoing life-threatening violence. Changes in the types of incidents firefighters respond to may have a negative impact on the safety culture. With these changes in mind, it is interesting to investigate whether new challenges and requirements for risk understanding affect current safety thinking and culture in the fire service.

This study examines the characteristics of the safety culture in three Norwegian professional fire and rescue services and investigate the measures that should be taken to ensure a strong safety culture in the future. It's necessary to reduce the threats to the fire fighters physical and mental health during the daily work and upcoming fires and rescue operations.

Purpose

The purpose of this study is to assess the safety culture in the fire and rescue services. The study aims to explore the characteristics, strengths, weaknesses, and potential improvements of the safety culture. Furthermore, the goal for this study is to contribute and increase the knowledge base, allowing other fire departments to learn from these insights. The study describes the characteristics the safety culture in three Norwegian fire and rescue services.

The study also aimed to answer following questions:

- How do employees describe the safety culture in the fire and rescue service?

- What is the perception of the safety culture among fire service personnel?
- What types of safety culture dominates within the fire service?
- How can the safety culture be improved?

Method

The chosen methodology for the study was a qualitative approach, utilizing semi-structured interviews, participant observation, along with a review of reported incidents in each fire department. A document analysis of relevant legislation has also been conducted. Participants include emergency personnel from three fire and rescue services with full time firefighters. Fifteen informants, with varied seniority and roles, were interviewed, and a participant observation was conducted at one of the fire services. The research data was collected in connection with one of the authors master thesis [1].

Results

The results from our study indicate that the flow of information in the fire service was previously characterized by a pathological culture, where the management of safety-related information was not prioritized. The fire and rescue service are now more influenced by a bureaucratic culture, where changes occur locally, and information followed the line of hierarchy.

Interviews revealed an improvement in the safety culture in the fire service over recent years. Nonetheless, the majority of respondents perceive the safety culture as lacking. They highlight that the fire service struggles to keep up with changes in work requirements and routines. There exists an opportunity for enhancement in establishing a reporting culture where employees fulfill their participation obligations, while leadership actively facilitates a supportive and positive work environment. The culture in the fire service is perceived as inflexible by informants, especially concerning their ability to adapt to changing external demands. The majority experience that employees are treated fairly, suggesting a just culture. The fire service's learning culture has potential for improvement

in terms of sharing experiences across the organization and other fire services.

The fire service's safety culture, according to informants, is characterized by both a reactive and calculative organization. The similarity with a reactive organization is reflected by the informants who experience that they only see a change in routines and work practice after incidents have already happened. The informants also describe that safety is a focus amongst the employees at their fire service, but its lacking execution. Follow-ups on incidents and improvement reports are reported as deficient, and procedures are rarely reviewed and updated, as experienced by a majority of the informants. This indicates that the fire service has common features with a calculative organization.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it's clear that the fire department's safety culture has room for improvement. Key areas for enhancing the safety culture include the establishment of clear guidelines and procedures for safety, an increased emphasis on training and education in incident reporting, creation of a conducive communication environment and lastly more frequent audit of the fire service.

These measures are essential for encouraging active participation from both firefighters and leaders alike. All employees of the fire service, no matter what position, should be encouraged to contribute to safety initiatives, facilitating organizational learning, and providing critical information for identifying areas of improvement.

Need for information sharing

Currently, there's no standardized approach to sharing experiences within the Norwegian fire services. Individual fire departments share experiences to a very limited extent across different fire services. However, by establishing a centralized platform for exchanging experiences, all fire departments, along with the fire and rescue school and other emergency responders, can benefit significantly. This shared platform would enable them to learn from each other's challenges, leading to more efficient resource allocation and training practices. The involvement of key stakeholders such as the Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (DSB), the Norwegian fire and rescue school, and leaders within the fire department is crucial in supporting and facilitating the implementation of this initiative, ensuring its success and effectiveness in enhancing the overall safety culture within the fire service.

Further studies

It is necessary to explore the safety culture in the fire service further. A factor that may have affected the results in this study is that the study only included a limited number of full-time fire department employee and the majority of

employees in the Norwegian fire service work part-time is lacking in this study. The basis for answering questions about the safety culture due to the background and assumptions may therefore be different. It would be interesting to further explore this perspective in another study.

Another factor to explore is summer substitutes in the fire service. Based on previous experiences, we have the impression that many substitutes aspire to continue working in the fire department. They have a short engagement and, therefore, want to stand out in the best possible way to create opportunities for extending their employment or get a permanent job. This may lead to underreporting of deviations or incidents to avoid negative attention.

Lastly, it is interesting to study the safety culture in other countries and to assess the culture and adapt improvement to the fire service in Norway.

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Utilization of Natural Droplet formation in Firefighting

Marko Hassinen
Fire and Rescue Innovation
Finland (FRIF)
Suonenjoki, Finland
marko.hassinen@frif.fi

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Abstract

The small droplet interior attack extinguishment technique has evolved over time into a proactive internal firefighting approach and is well suited for it. The technique ensures the safety of working for firefighters. The goal of the method is to prevent smoke gases from igniting unexpectedly, which could exceed the firefighting capacity available to the firefighters. Small droplets are generated using specially designed spray nozzles, resulting in a fairly homogeneous droplet size. The small droplets vaporize in smoke gases at a relatively constant distance from the nozzle. In this method, droplets are less likely to land on hot surfaces, allowing for indirect cooling as the smoke gases cool down. This study investigates the use of heterogeneous droplet sizes, where droplet dispersion varies more, and a larger portion of droplets also reaches hot surfaces. Production of heterogeneous droplet sizes is based on the natural breakup of water sprayed into the air.

History

Before the development of small droplet technology (3D technology), room exhaust gases could be cooled by a direct jet aimed at the room's ceiling [1]. The water droplets falling from the ceiling dispersed into the layer of exhaust gas and cooled the flue gases. The droplet size in this method naturally remains quite large, so a large portion of the droplets fall onto burning surfaces. The same technique is still used in transitional attack firefighting [2]. The issue with this technique from the perspective of an interior firefighter is the formation of very hot water vapor.

Using natural droplet breakup

In this study we used a device that sprays water upward from simple holes and the water is let to break up into smaller droplets by natural break-up methods [3]. To study the extinguishing effect both practical experiments and FDS simulations were used. In FDS simulations the droplet size

distribution was Rosin-Rammler [4]. Droplet size distribution was not measured in the practical experiments due to lack of suitable devices.

Methods

In the practical tests, the significance of different droplet sizes on how quickly the fire cools down was tested, as well as whether there is a difference between methods in temperature changes near the floor, i.e., whether a so-called steam effect is created.

Figure 1. Initial seat of fire and the test setup (Emergency Services Academy Finland)

The test was conducted by students from the Emergency Services Academy in a firehouse. Wooden planks and timber were used as kindling (Figure 1). For the burns, three fire extinguishing nozzles (Figure 2) with different hole sizes were prepared. The fire extinguisher with small holes (Figure 2, left side) had 80 holes with a combined area of 378 mm². The fire extinguisher with large holes (Figure 2, right side) had 12 holes with 641 mm², and the one with medium-sized holes had 31 holes with a combined area of 526 mm². The nozzles were constructed with what material was at hand and the construction was guided by visual evaluation of the spray pattern based on an extensive experience of developing similar spray nozzles. The operating pressure was one of the parameters set during the test phase.

Figure 2. Nozzles prepared for the droplet size tests.

The nozzles used in the practical tests were modeled into FDS [5] simulations to test different droplet sizes and nozzle shapes in a controlled environment. Testing nozzles through simulations would facilitate and expedite the discovery of

optimal droplet size distributions, which is quite time-consuming through combustion tests.

For the simulation, the nozzles were constructed using a simple spray orifice for each hole on the nozzle. The orientation of the orifice, the flowrate and initial velocity of water were calculated from the nozzle geometry and the measurements from the practical tests. As the nozzles for the practical tests had different flowrates and operating pressures, the results (figure 3) are not comparable as such.

Figure 3. Temperature curves for various droplet sizes. Blue=ceiling, Red=150 cm, Green= 50cm, time in seconds

A major challenge in building the simulation was the lack of information on the droplet size distribution. To build a simulation that corresponds to reality, information on the droplet size distribution generated by the nozzle would be needed, which in this study had to be based on assumptions and visual estimation.

The calculations for the simulations are quite intensive and require a lot of computing power. The simulations in this study were computed on CSC's (IT Center for Science) high-performance computers in parallel computing.

Results

In both practical tests and simulations, a very fast temperature drop (Figures 3 and 4) was achieved through natural droplet breakup, which was as expected. However, the temperature increase expected near the floor was much lower than anticipated. This was contributed to the small droplets forming in natural droplet breakup, their short travel time and evaporation near the floor. The results of the large droplet-producing shower head in the simulation best matched the results obtained in practical experiments. Further investigation is needed on the simulation of the fire to ensure it matches the one used in practical tests. To obtain comparability between the nozzles in terms of extinguishing power, the flow rates should be harmonized.

The main result of the study was that the effectiveness of different showers in cooling can also be studied through modeling. Using simulation, a more uniform fire scenario can be created than in practical experiments. In this study, the main objectives were achieved in modeling, but further research on modeling is warranted. It would be beneficial to be able to measure the droplet size distributions of different water sprays, to make the simulation more accurate.

Figure 4. Simulated results for a large droplet, time in seconds

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Fire Performance of a Wooden Façade System Using the European Testing Method: Assessing the Contribution from the Side Wing

Guoxiang Zhao^{1*}, Anders Dragsted¹, Mia Fossing Frederiksen¹, Karlis Livkiss¹, Christian Fundby Schou¹, Asmus Haastrup¹
DBI Danish Institute of Fire and Security Technology, Hvidovre, Denmark

*Corresponding author, gzh@dbigroup.dk

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Background

Large-scale façade fire testing has been applied as a tool in building design to ensure compliance with fire safety regulations and building codes.

There are different test methods throughout Europe with different types of fire source, heat exposure to the façade, duration time of the test, pass criteria and so on. The project, 'European Approach to Assess the Fire Performance of Facades,' led by RISE, has been in development [1][2] of a harmonized European testing method for facades and provide regulators with means to regulate the fire performance of façade systems.

Large-scale fire tests were conducted at DBI as per the European testing method to evaluate façade fire performance of ventilated wooden façade system as part of the 'BioFacades: Uphigh' project. This project aims to assist fire engineers in verifying if detailed designs meet functional requirements of the building regulation. This study specifically examines two tests, emphasizing the impact of combustible materials on the side wing.

Façade materials and test method

The wooden board is from Frøslev, profile 2685, featuring a dimension of 21 x 120 mm and with tongue-and-groove connection joints. The wood species is Nordic spruce. The density of the wood board is measured 470 kg/m³ with a moisture content of 12.6% after 48 h in the conditioning room. The thermal conductivity is reported to be around 0.14 and 0.20 W/(m·K) depending on the sample orientation and temperature during the test [3].

The façade system was mounted on vertical concrete façade rig, and consists of an insulated back wall, ventilation cavity and vertically oriented non-fire treated wood cladding affixed to timber frame. Horizontal flame deflectors, extending 32.4 cm outside the cladding at various heights, were used to restrict flame spread. The flame deflectors were made with 2 mm steel with a 4-degree slope, see in Figure 1 (a).

The facade rig was constructed following the methodology outlined in [1], but modifications were made to the primary wall, with its height extended to 1.5 m above the recommended minimum height of 8.5 m, while the width was kept at 3.2 m. The side wing, adhering to the minimum standard dimensions, measured 8.5 m in height and 1.5 m in width and was positioned at a 90° angle on the right side of the main structure. Each floor above the chamber features openings measuring 1.76 m x 1.98 m, surpassing the

dimensions of 1.2 m x 1.2 m specified in the standard test. There are 10 tests in total in this façade test campaign, here only Test 3 and Test 4 are presented. Test 3 refers to the test with non-combustible side wing and Test 4 refers to the test with wood panel on the side wing, see Figure 1(b and c). The fuel load is provided by spruce wood crib resulting in a peak heat release of approximately 3.4 MW[4].

Figure 1. Build-up of the façade system (a) and the experimental set-up of Test 3 (b) and Test 4 (c).

The fire test was conducted at ambient temperature of approximately 7 °C inside the façade hall. A mechanical exhaust of 80,000 m³/h was even distributed at the ceiling. The tests were instrumented with thermocouples, plate thermometers and heat flux meters.

Figure 2. Photos after test: Test 3 (left) and Test 4 (right).

Test results

In Test 3, without combustible material on the side wing, flame spread was confined to the 1st floor during the entire test. In Test 4, featuring wood panels on the side wing, flames were primarily on the first floor but with a minor fire at the base of the second floor. The fire on the 2nd floor ignited at around 36 minutes, spreading from the 1st floor to the 2nd floor through a gap in the cavity between the cladding and the side

wall. Such a scenario is unlikely to occur with a horizontally continuous wall where the gap would not exist in practical design. This has been depicted in Figure 2. In Test 4, the burning was much more severe than in Test 3 and the damage area is much larger as well.

Figure 3. Heat flux at 3 m away from the facade and 1.4 m above the ground level.

Figure 4. Temperature on the 1st floor of the main wall (2.5 m above the deflector and 1 m from the corner).

Heat flux measurements, 3 m outside the combustion chamber and 1.4 m above the ground level, were recorded in both tests, as shown in Figure 3. Throughout most of the test duration, heat flux values were higher in Test 4, peaking at 30 kW/m² in Test 3 and 46 kW/m² in Test 4. This difference indicates the contribution from the additional burning on the side wing and the subsequent increased burning on the main façade.

Figure 4 displays temperature measurements on the first floor of the main wall (2.5 m above the deflector and 1 m from the corner), showing temperatures below 220°C throughout Test 3, whereas in Test 4, temperatures hovered around 800°C from 10 to 40 minutes. The elevated heat flux and temperature in Test 4 can be primarily attributed to the extra burning on the side wing, which led to a larger fire on the main façade.

Figure 5 presents temperature results at the second floor of the side wing, measured along a vertical line 0.5 m from the corner at heights of 0.4 m (F.2.6), 0.9 m (F.2.5), and 1.4 m (F.2.4) above the deflector. Temperatures on the 2nd floor of the side wing remained below 220°C, similar to those on the 2nd floor of the main wall, except at 0.4 m above the deflector in Test 4, where it started to increase after 40 minutes and reached 890 °C due to a small fire on the 2nd floor near the deflector.

Figure 5. Temperatures on the 2nd floor of the side wing.

Figure 6 shows temperature measurements on the first and ground floors of the side wing, taken 0.5 m from the corner at various heights. In Test 3, without combustible material on the side wing, temperatures remained below 200°C, while in Test 4, the thermocouples are in flames. Other measurements during the test, such as temperature inside the cavity and heat flux on the façade, were also conducted but are not included here due to text limitations.

Figure 6. Temperatures on the ground and 1st floor of the side wing.

In this study, large-scale fire tests with ventilated wooden façade system were conducted according to the European testing method. Results of two distinct tests were studied, one with non-combustible material on the side wing and the other with combustible wood panels. Through these results, the study emphasizes the importance of combustible elements in façade design to meet fire performance requirements.

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Sustainable materials in buildings

the influence of wind barriers on fire safety

Kenneth Askov Stærkjær
Byg og Brand, Denmark
ks@bygogbrand.dk

Anne S. Dederichs
RISE, Lund, Sweden and
Civil and Mechanical
Engineering,
Technical University of
Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark
Anne.Dederichs@ri.se

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Abstract

This study examines the construction of façades with a focus on utilizing sustainable materials in the structure. The fire properties for wind barriers and the barrier panel were investigated. The study involves constructions with cement-based materials, biobased materials, as well as membrane (Tyvek® FireCurb Soft). The scenario is fire from a window. The tests were run with and without a fire stop. It was found that the cement-based wind barrier and the biobased wind barrier performed best with respect to fire resistance. The limiting effect of the fire stop was observed. More studies are needed to verify the results of this study.

Introduction

More sustainable building materials are being considered in the construction industry; however, it is important to maintain adequate fire safety. Wind barriers protect façades against wind, rain, and moisture, thus influencing energy efficiency and comfort. According to Danish prescriptive requirements, a wind barrier of class K1 10 / B-s1, d0 [1, 2] should be used. Wind barriers are fastened on panels, often made of cement. The use of cement in the process makes the solution less sustainable [3]. The question in the current work is to study the influence of fire stops on biobased façades using biobased wind barriers and fibrebased cements (figure 1).

Method

The method involved studying the fire development for façades of fibrebased cement and wooden cladding together with 3 types of wind barriers: cement fiberbased cement, a biobased wind barrier Woodfiber Safe®¹, and a membrane product, tested with and without a fire stop. The membrane (Tyvek® FireCurb Soft) is made of woven polyethylene coated with a halogen-free flame-retardant material. The fire

stop was a FireFree® Brandstop Hulrumsventil (Firestop Cavityvalve). For the experiment a method was sought that resembled the scenario of a fire venting through a window, impinging on the cross section of the façade, with and without a fire stop. Different standards were considered. The design from EN14135 was rejected as possible effects of the fire stop could not be seen with this method. The setup should enable the fire to spread to the internal layers of the façade.

Figure 1: Facade

However, the criteria from EN14135 were adapted for the analysis. SPfire 105 was rejected as it needed to be scaled down. Finally, a modified version of DS/ISO 13785 was used (Table 1). A sand burner was built and used as the fire source. The tests were run for 15 minutes in accordance with the modified K₁ 10 requirement, keeping the temperature below 250 °C, with no collapse, and no damage to the substrate. The temperature behind the wind barrier was measured throughout the tests.

¹ Wood fiber, PURglue, paraffine and flame retardents

The change in frame height of the probe compared to ISO 13785 was assumed to be neglectable. Six specimens were built: cement on fibrebased cement, cement on wood, biobased material on fibrebased cement, biobased material on wood, membrane on fibrebased cement, membrane on wood. One side of the specimen was equipped with a fire stop, the other side without a fire stop. Six thermocouples were placed behind the barriers, three on each side.

Table 1: Deviation of from ISO13785

	ISO 13785	Current study
Height	2800 mm	1950 mm
Width	2400 mm	2300 mm
Side wall	600 mm	0 mm
Heat flux meter	On top	-
Surface thermocouple	8 stk	6 stk.
Duration	30 min.	15 min.
Effekt på sandburner	100 kW	85 kW
Effect of sandburner	100 kW	unstable
Fire stop	-	Fire stop in half specimens

Results and Discussion

The façade specimens were ignited as can be seen in [4], which shows the façade fire of biobased material on wood, with (left side) and without (right side) the fire stop. The rapid development of the fire on the part not protected by the fire stop can be seen. However, smoke gases build up on the left side, where the fire stop hinders access to oxygen inside the structure. A flame lift off can be seen. The last picture shows the affected material behind the façade after the fire ended. Figure 2 shows the average temperatures (a) with and (b) without the fire stop. The effect of the fire stop with respect to almost all materials can be seen in the reduced temperatures, except membrane on wood, which is not well protected by the fire stop.

The membrane on fibrebased cement showed high temperature rise behind, and damage at the side with a firestop made of steel. The materials following the Danish prescriptive fire safety requirements, however, performed best in the present study.

The following errors need to be accounted for: a non-intentional error in the design of the sand burner led to a decreasing effect from the burner throughout the run. However, the effect surpasses a generation of the temperature required in EN 13501-1.

Conclusion

The current pilot study on fire safety showed that the prescriptive alternatives, cement on fibrebased cement, cement on wood, as well as biobased sustainable material on fibrebased cement, biobased material on wood, and

membrane on wood, stayed under the temperature criterion of the ISO 13785. The test membrane on fibrebased cement did not meet the criterion. The current study demonstrated that the material of the wind barrier affects the flame spread on the façade. However, the presence of the fire stop has reduced fire damage to the wind barrier and the Fibrebased cement. More studies are needed to verify these results.

Figure 2: Biobased material on wood, fire stop on left side

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Smoldering-to-Flaming Transition of Bio-based Insulation Materials

Patrick Sudhoff
Otto-von-Guericke
University Magdeburg,
Germany
Patrick.sudhoff@ovgu.de

Joakim Åström
Lund University, Sweden
Joakim.astrom@brand.lth.se

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Abstract

Understanding fire behavior is crucial in improving the acceptance of bio-based insulation materials. Many phenomena, such as the smoldering-to-flaming transition, are still poorly understood. While the phenomenon has been observed empirically in several medium-scale fire tests, the critical conditions remain unknown.

The following study examines the critical influence factors such as oxygen concentration and temperature conditions that can lead to sudden flaming combustion. Therefore, an experimental series in the Controlled-Atmosphere-Cone-Calorimeter was conducted with different heat fluxes and oxygen concentrations. A standard loose-fill wood fiber insulation was used as test material.

Introduction

Regarding climate protection goals, bio-based insulation materials represent an essential alternative to conventional mineral or petroleum-based materials.

The production is usually made from sustainably grown, renewable raw materials such as wood fiber, cellulose, hemp, cork, jute, or sea wood. In contrast to conventional materials, bio-based insulating materials can serve as a natural carbon dioxide storage and are easily recycled. The combination with the lightweight timber panel construction offers many possibilities, e.g. urban densification.

A disadvantage, however, is their tendency to smolder continuously after reaching initial ignition, which has been recently investigated in several projects [1-3].

While the smoldering behavior has already been extensively studied with different experimental setups [4], there is still a lack of understanding of the fundamental processes such as ignition, smoldering, and smoldering-to-flaming transition. This phenomenon can lead to a rapidly increased fire spread and could also be a potential hazard during the opening of components through the fire service.

Medium-Scale Component Tests

In medium-scale fire tests at the University of Science Magdeburg-Stendal, a change from smoldering to flaming combustion was observed after the cladding was damaged through thermal exposure. The components built of a 1050 mm x 1050 mm x 160 mm frame were filled with a commonly used loose-fill wood fiber insulation material that consists of wood fibers from pine wood and 5% ammonium salts. It is used as between-stud insulation in timber frame, post, and beam interior and exterior wall structures or as a between-rafter or ceiling insulation. The components were cladded with a 12.5 mm gypsum plasterboard on the fire-exposed side. The specimens were placed in a 1 m x 1 m component furnace and exposed using the standard fire curve for approximately 15 minutes until at least 250 °C was reached on the insulation surface facing the fire.

The components were lifted out of the furnace, placed next to each other, separated by a wall, and observed for 24 hours with thermocouples, thermal imaging, and CCTV. The smoldering front moved from the exposed to the unexposed side. After 6 to 7 hours, the front burned through the medium-density fiberboard on the unexposed side. The smoldering front emerged to the surface, and a high concentration of pyrolysis gases, available oxygen, and internal heating led to a smoldering-to-flaming transition (Figure 1). Nevertheless, the exact conditions for this fire behavior remained unclear. As a first attempt for finding the critical conditions, small-scale experiments with a Controlled-Atmosphere-Cone-Calorimeter (CACC) were conducted at the Fire Safety Division of Lund University. The study aimed to examine the influences such as critical heat flux and limiting oxygen concentration.

Figure 1. 24h fire tests with two wood frame components with smoldering-to-flaming transition after 6 hours

Controlled-Atmosphere-Cone-Calorimeter Tests

The bench scale study of smoldering-to-flaming transition was conducted in a modified CACC in the Fire Lab at Lund University. The enclosure and chimney of the CACC are designed as described in ISO 5660-5. In the duct above the enclosure are standard oxygen, CO, and CO₂ measurements to evaluate the HRR. The HRR was calculated using oxygen consumption calorimetry (OCC) and carbon dioxide generation (CDG). CDG is added to reduce the uncertainties from the reduced oxygen environment [5]. In addition to the HRR measurements, the duct includes a three-laser rig for smoke quantification. This allows for smoke production measurements and an average particle size estimate [6]. Lastly, there was also a Fourier-Transformation-Infrared-Spectrometer (FTIR) connected to the duct (Figure 2). The FTIR was of the type AtmosFIR [7]. The gas sample to the FTIR was routed through a heated line keeping 180 °C to avoid condensation and washing out of acidulous gases. Data collections from the HRR and lasers were made every 3 seconds while the FTIR used a 10 seconds average. The samples were conditioned at 23 °C and 50 % RH and placed in a cylindrical steel specimen holder with 10 cm diameter, and 5 cm height. The bottom 2.5 cm was insulated with ceramic wool. To ensure better test reproducibility, the spark ignitor was used.

Using this setup, the material behavior of wood fiber insulation in varying oxygen concentrations was studied by looking at ignition time, critical heat flux, HRR, smoke characteristics, and extensive gas analysis. Some preliminary results and conclusions are presented below.

Figure 2. Schematic overview of the Controlled-Atmosphere-Cone-Calorimeter with FTIR-Coupling

Preliminary CACC Results

At 20 kW/m² heat flux, the time to ignition (t_{ign}) was shifted from about 10 seconds at ambient oxygen conditions to about 20 seconds at 15 vol% O₂. The duration until flameout (t_{fo}) was reduced from about 4 minutes to 20 seconds. Since the thermal inertia of the sample does not change between the experiments, the lack of oxygen might increase the critical temperature needed to establish a continuous flaming. Also, the produced volatiles and the oxidation at

the sample's surface might have an influence, which will be part of further analysis. Especially the FTIR and laser measurements might give a better insight into the production of volatiles and soot.

Figure 3. Heat Release Rate per unit area (calculated with CDG) and flame appearance for three oxygen concentrations

Below the limit of 14 vol%, no surface ignition could be observed. At about 13.5 vol%, some flashing appeared, which can be identified as a transition zone.

The peak Heat Release Rate decreased from 110 kW/m² at ambient oxygen to 40 kW/m² at 15 vol%. For 13 vol%, the Heat Release Rate per Unit Area remained below 20 kW/m² without the characteristic peak (Figure 3). Furthermore, the appearance of the flame changed significantly with a reduced oxygen atmosphere. While the size and brightness decreased with lower concentrations, some blue emissions were observed at the boundary zone.

Generally, the mechanisms that influence the critical conditions remain complex and challenging to reproduce on a bench scale. However, the first analysis shows promising results to better understand the governing mechanisms of the smoldering-to-flaming transition.

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Cellular Automata-based Wildfire Simulation and Comparative Analysis with Other Models in Norway

Warda Rafaqat
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Haugesund
Department of Physics and Technology, University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway
wara@hvl.no

Bjarne Christian Hagen
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Haugesund, Norway
bjarne.hagen@hvl.no

Nieves Fernandez Anez
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Haugesund, Norway
Nieves.Fernandez@hvl.no

Keywords:

Wildfire, Cellular Automata, Comparative Analysis, Simulation Modeling.

Abstract

Wildfires pose significant threats to ecosystems and human settlements, necessitating the development of robust simulation models for effective mitigation and management. [1]. This study presents a detailed examination of a cellular automata-based wildfire simulation model tailored to investigate the dynamics of wildfire spread in Norway. The model integrates critical factors such as wind direction, vegetation density, and ignition sources to emulate the intricate interactions influencing wildfire behavior. Through this investigation, the study aims to provide valuable insights into the factors driving wildfire spread in Norwegian landscapes, thereby facilitating more effective wildfire management strategies, and enhancing community resilience.

Introduction

In recent years, Norway has experienced notable wildfire events, underscoring the importance of accurate wildfire prediction and management strategies in the region. Between 2016 and 2023, several such incidents have occurred, prompting the need for advanced modeling techniques to better understand and anticipate wildfire behavior. In response, this research endeavors to validate and compare simulation results from established models like Rothermal [2] and other cellular automata models, with the aim of identifying the most suitable model for the Norwegian study area. Specifically, cellular automata are explored as discrete computational models, wherein a grid of cells represents various characteristics such as vegetation, fuel availability, ignition status, and fire spread potential [3]. Governed by deterministic rules dictating cell state evolution based on neighboring conditions, cellular automata offer a promising framework for predicting wildfire dynamics. Through simulating the evolution of these models over time,

researchers can gain insights into wildfire spread dynamics, identify influential factors, and potentially forecast future wildfire extents and intensities under diverse conditions. Moreover, this study aims to assess the applicability and limitations of cellular automata models in informing wildfire management strategies, providing crucial insights for enhancing wildfire preparedness and response efforts in Norway.

Methodology

The cellular automata approach for wildfire prediction consists of two primary phases. Firstly, the initialization phase involves delineating a grid representing the study area, with each cell assigned initial states corresponding to pertinent characteristics like vegetation type, fuel availability, and potential ignition sources. Following this, the iterative simulation phase employs deterministic rules to dictate the evolution of cell states over successive time intervals. These rules incorporate factors such as wind direction, vegetation density, and terrain features, thereby simulating the propagation of fire and facilitating the prediction of wildfire extent and behavior. Through this iterative process, the cellular automata model captures the intricate dynamics of wildfire spread, offering valuable insights crucial for the formulation of effective wildfire management and mitigation strategies.

To enhance the model's predictive capabilities, real-time burn information sourced from DSB Norway, along with access to burn area data derived from Sentinel imagery corresponding to specific dates, is integrated into the simulation model. Additionally, the incorporation of the Rothermal equation into cellular automata further augments the model's efficacy, with ongoing research aimed at assessing its performance.

The methodology documentation encompasses comprehensive explanations of underlying assumptions, data collection procedures, and analysis methods. Furthermore, the presentation includes figures and illustrations depicting the

results of ongoing research, including maps of Norway overlaid with fire information, to provide visual insights into the dynamics of wildfire simulation within the region.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the introduction of a cellular automata model specifically tailored for wildfire prediction in Norway represents a significant advancement in wildfire research, offering unparalleled insights into the complex dynamics of fire spread within Norwegian landscapes. By accounting for the unique environmental and geographical factors present in the region, this model provides enhanced predictive capabilities, empowering stakeholders with the tools to proactively plan and implement targeted mitigation strategies. This study offers valuable insights into the development and application of advanced wildfire simulation models for effective wildfire management strategies in Norway and beyond.

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Citizen responsive contributions in wildfire crisis

Questions on lessons learned from the 2021 Finsjö fire

Lucas Hovart
Brandteknik
Lunds Universitet,
LU
Lund, Sweden
Lucas.hovart@brand.lth.se

Kerstin Eriksson
Research Institutes of
Sweden
RISE
Lund, Sweden

Tove Frykmer
Riskhantering och
samhällssäkerhet
Lunds Universitet
LU
Lund, Sweden

Margaret McNamee
Brandteknik
Lunds Universitet,
LU
Lund, Sweden

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Wildfire, Intervention, Responsibility, Citizens, Solidarity.

Abstract

In 2021, the locality of Finsjö in Sweden experienced an abnormally large wildfire. During an intervention lasting for 6 days, Fire and Rescue Services [FRS] received spontaneous help from citizens, leading to valuable contributions but also questions regarding how to address division of responsibilities.

Through qualitative interviews with the FRS, this study explores the interaction between formal and informal responsibilities and how FRS representatives perceive spontaneous civilian contributions. We will show how informal responses can assist and complement formal duties, and how this source of support also generates questions regarding dependance and accountability.

Theoretical framework

Responsibility as a concept is a complex matter. The notion covers multiple realities and manifests itself in several types of situations, be that moral or legal. Therefore, discussions about responsibilities can often lead to confusion and misunderstanding, where protagonists may have different interpretations of the same concept. Multiple theories offer useful clarification as a starting point for meaningful dialogue. Among the several models developed to represent the complexity of the responsibility attribution processes, we chose to use Pellizzoni's approach [1]. Pellizzoni encapsulates both the distinction between duty and blame, and a distinction between formal and informal responsibilities. These two aspects put together are essential to explore responsibility during FRS activities. Furthermore, this theory has been used by Erik Löfmarck & al. [2] to provide a rich description of confusion encountered concerning questions of responsibility in Swedish forestry regulations and the way they are applied.

Essentially, Pellizzoni's model [1] explains the concept of responsibility in its moral dimension and its legal dimension in relation to a timeline, i.e. before and after blame is addressed. To this aspect, he adds a formal/informal distinction based on whether one is pushed to address responsibilities according to a predefined system, which he calls push-factors, or whether one is drawn to act on responsibilities based on a given assessment of a situation,

which he calls pull-factors. This offers the possibility of drawing a typology of responsibility according to the declination of the concept in different settings. He distinguishes between *care*, *liability*, *accountability*, and *responsiveness*, see figure 1.

Figure 1. Pellizzoni's responsibility matrix [1] with Löfmarck's addition of the Obedience dimension [2].

In this paper, our interest will lie in the distinction between *care* and *responsiveness*. These two sub-concepts share their situation as responsibility given or taken before blame is assigned. It can help to distinguish them from the two others by assigning them to the conceptual field of duty rather than blame, with a focus on the role taken by an individual or organization, based on capacity [3]. While care and obedience manifest from known and codified needs, responsiveness designates action taken based on spontaneous perception of needs, a form of readiness-to-act.

This distinction will constitute our focus. Wildfire interventions are events where a codified set of action encounters a largely unpredictable hazard. In this context, both FRS and citizens will be guided by procedures, leading them to an attitude of care and obedience. However, what is observed in practice is that care and obedience as principles do not cover the entirety of the observed behaviors. Actors step out of the prescribed responsibilities given to them in order to take responsibilities they identify themselves, acting somewhat informally. While this behavior has been observed and studied with firefighters [4], we take particular interest in the way it manifests with citizens and, moreover, what are the perceived benefits and complications emerging from this manifestation.

Results

“It's fun to be involved and help out.”

“It's always a strength in a small community, that's how it is. We have very good support. [...] And people are very eager to help when such things happen, they call and say, “I can come with coffee or water,” both residents and former firefighters who are very, very good and have these things. I must say.”

This extract offers a good example of the general perception of citizen's responsive action. Their ability to perceive needs and their willingness to act on it offers a form of support seen as an asset. The next extract highlights it again while revealing an additional interesting dimension.

“I won't say we are dependent on it, but we do a much better job when we don't have to focus on such things. We can handle this without them, but it becomes much more challenging for us.”

While the benefits of supportive actions are stated, so is the fact that one cannot depend on it, which is further developed by another participant.

“We can't always trust that society, Maria's helping hand, may not come to this fire. Then we can't just stand and wait for her to bring sandwiches to our guys and girls. [...] We can't just wait for society. It's good when they come. It's the icing on the cake. It's a luxury.”

Responsive action remains an informal type of responsibility. In a context of great uncertainty, like a fire intervention, they can also be a source of additional variability. As the next example will show, this supplementary charge can add confusion.

“The problem with these volunteer organizations, some of them actually invoice for this. And then... and then they want some extra benefits sometimes, and they want a little space to set up their equipment. And if you actively build an organization with them, it takes time otherwise too. And it sounds like I'm not interested in working with them. It's not that. It's just that it's so hard to account for this.”

This comment shows that responsive action can bring additional accountability questions. The fact that someone decides to take charge for a perceived need does not imply that this same person will be seen as the answerable person [5], the entity which will be named accountable and blamed in case of a difficult outcome. As a consequence of this answerability challenge, we observe the emergence of manoeuvres blurring the line between formal and informal action.

“They have done a lot of logistics for us during the fires. We've benefited from them. They need very strict control because otherwise, it can spin a bit, but they are good when you guide them. We have organized a civilian resource group that we alert via SMS when our resources run out.”

Discussion: Potential paths for useful clarification

While the results highlight the benefits of informal civilian contribution, they also help identify two underlying problems. While informal solidarity covers needs that are not

necessarily met by standard procedures, it also raises a concern for potential dependency and for accountability. More broadly, informal contributions bring with them an unpredictability which adds a layer of uncertainty to what is already a hazardous operation. We can then see how this issue is addressed when the last participant mentions a need for guidance, a way to channel the help.

A common point between these two problems is their connection with *accountability*. This additional layer of responsibility refers to readiness in front of potential blame, the anticipation of having to answer for choices or actions [6]. While help is being informal, the question of who will answer for what is being done, and potentially done wrong, remains in the scope. This becomes particularly evident when volunteers come with expectations for more formalized collaboration, which would imply more coordination work before fires, and additional layers during operations, each one calling for some form of leadership, for someone who will take accountability. However, while this charge is being mentioned, the preferred course of action remains to include some sort of formalization.

Conclusions

Based on these observations, a few questions emerge:

How does a civilian resource group operate, and how is responsibility addressed in this type of configuration? Who takes accountability? Is help effectively centralized?

Should all informal help be somehow formalized? Is there some room for unpredictable action? Are there some specific benefits and drawbacks for each mode of action?

Addressing these questions can benefit Fire and Rescue Services and communities by offering a basis for planning. Useful approaches have already been tested in similar or different contexts and could offer a path for future research.

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Experimental investigating flame propagation of vegetation fire in different scales

Hongyi Wu
 Bundesanstalt für
 Materialforschung und –
 prüfung, (BAM)
 Berlin, Germany
 hongyi.wu@bam.de

Anja Hofmann-Böllinghaus
 Bundesanstalt für
 Materialforschung und –
 prüfung, (BAM)
 Berlin, Germany
 anja.hofmann@bam.de

Keywords: *vegetation fire, flame propagation, SBI-test, vegetation in Germany, wildfire*

Abstract

Since we are facing more extreme weathers, the occurrence of wildfire has also increased accordingly. The EU project TREEADS aims to adopt a holistic forest fire management and an adaptive, collaborative governance approach based on the deployment of a new systemic and technological framework covering all three interconnected fire management stages: prevention & preparedness, detection & response, and restoration & adaptation.

As part of the task in the so-called German pilot, numerical simulations are performed to investigate the influencing factors for vegetation fires with fire dynamics simulator (FDS). The characteristics of vegetation are strongly related to the local weather and ecosystem. The investigation of the fire behavior of vegetation must be based on the local vegetation in Germany. Thus, the flame propagation of typical vegetation in Germany (pine needles, oak leaves, European beech leaves etc.) was investigated in small scale and medium scale experiments. These results are used as validation case studies for the further simulations.

Method

In the small-scale experiment, a modified device based on the ISO 3795 [1] was applied to test the horizontal flame propagation of the vegetation. The ignition source was a Bunsen burner with methane according to the standard. Figure 1 shows the flame propagation of European beech leaves with a loading of 10g on an area of 10 x 30 cm. The flame propagation velocity can be estimated according to the consumed time for the 30cm propagation. The temperature in the fuel bed was also measured with thermocouples.

Figure 1. *small scale experiment with European beech leaves*

Afterwards, the vegetation samples were brought to the Single Burning Item (SBI) test as medium scale experiments. The measurement of the heat release rate and smoke density is based on the standard EN 13823 [2]. Figure 2 shows the flame propagation of European beech leaves in SBI, with a loading of 150g on an area of 50 x 50 cm.

Figure 2. *medium scale experiment with European beech leaves*

Results

The temperature in the center of the fuel bed was measured for both small- and medium-scale experiment. The result of the European beech leaves is discussed here.

Figure 3. temperature measurement in the center of the fuel bed (European beech leaves)

Figure 3 illustrates the temperature change of the fuel bed when the flame passes by. The starting point lays on the beginning of the temperature increment. The turbulence due to the ventilation in the lab was completely isolated with the test device in the small-scale experiment, while the medium-scale experiment has stronger convection due to the turbulence during the flame propagation. Which results in a faster temperature rise and a 19% higher maximum combustion temperature. According to the visual observation, the fire propagation velocity of medium-scale experiment is approximately 5% faster than the small-scale experiment.

It can be concluded, the flame propagation of fuel bed composed of European beech leaves doesn't show a great scaling up effect. As the numerical model is validated by the small-scale experiment. It can be applied for the simulation of larger scale vegetation fires, to investigate how other parameters, water content, wind velocity, and bulk density influence the flame propagation of vegetation fire. The other vegetation samples will be further studied with the same method.

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Nordic Fire and Rescue Services in the 21st Century (FIRE21)

Margaret McNamee
Fire Safety
Engineering
Lund University,
Lund, Sweden
Margaret.mcnamee@
brand.lth.se

Tove Frykmer
Risk Management
and Societal Safety
Lund University,
Lund, Sweden

Gudveig Gjørund
NTNU Social
Research
Trondheim, Norway

Lotta Vylund
RISE Research
Institutes of Sweden
Göteborg, Sweden

Frans Markert
Structural
Engineering and
Structural Mechanics
DTU
Copenhagen,
Denmark

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FRS, problem-solving networks, emergencies, capabilities

Abstract

Societal change is accelerating through continued rapid population growth and significant changes in demographics, technological advances, and increasing interconnectedness between various infrastructures. Together with climate change and a new global security situation these trends inevitably lead to changes in the risk landscape of the future. One of the key actors that has to deal with such change is the Fire and Rescue Services (FRS). These organizations are both governed by, and dependent on, formal and informal networks. FIRE21 is a research project aimed at understanding those networks which appear to solve problems both today and tomorrow, centered around Norway, Sweden and Denmark. This paper gives an overview of the framework of the project from the point of view of the FRS and presents some findings.

Background

Emergencies and disasters generate two types of demands: the agent generated and the response generated [1]. The agent generated demand comes from the hazard itself, such as the fire or the flood. This could mean the need to extinguish the fire and deal with its consequences, or the need to pile sandbags to inhibit the progress of a flood. The response generated demands are created from the responding resources, typically including needs for communication and coordination. Incident response is all about dealing with these two types of demands, both agent and response generated, at the same time. Such efforts represent different parts of the emergency management network which is applied during response but largely developed prior to the response phase of emergency management. The efforts of meeting both agent and response generated needs harmonizes with the view on external and internal problem solving, i.e. problem solving associated with either the incident or the response [2, 3]. A key managerial challenge during response operations is to handle sometimes both various and numerous external and internal problems in parallel. The capacity to deal with these

challenges is connected to relations that have been built up prior to the acute situation [4, 5].

The aim of FIRE21 is to better understand how problem-solving networks are established in the field of the Fire and Rescue Services (FRS), and how such networks affect problem solving prior to, during and after response operations. The research questions studied include:

- How stable are existing formal and informal FRS networks for emergency management in the Nordic countries?
- How are these networks developed and maintained?
- Which capabilities for problem solving need to be developed to best support emergency management networks in FRS for the future?
- How can these capabilities be implemented and updated in the organization?

Methodology

The project consists of five (5) work packages (WP), see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of FIRE21 project activities

Results

Main findings concerning mapping of formal networks on a national level relate to the diversity of stakeholders related to the work of the Fire and Rescue Services (FRS). Similar types of governance documents and level of governance of the FRS was found between the three countries. The mapping has led to questions such as:

- 1) In what ways are the formal networks similar and dissimilar compared to reports on real fire incidents?
- 2) How can we understand communication in actual fire incidents that do not follow the formal network?
- 3) Are there any organizations unexpectedly missing from the maps?

These questions were included in analysis of case studies in Norway, Sweden and Denmark. The cases which have been investigated or are presently being investigated using document analysis and semi-structured interviews are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of case studies in Sweden, Norway and Denmark.

Case #	Sweden	Norway	Denmark
1	Explosion	Rural FRS	Urban fire
2	Wildfire	Parking garage fire	Wildfire
3	Flood	Landslide	Train accident

Examples of questions raised include:

- 1) Rural FRS in Norway: How is it possible to have adequate preparedness in a large area with limited resources when it comes to personnel, limited water supply, and physical equipment? What is today's role of the part-time firefighter in rural Norway?
- 2) Explosion in Sweden: Which problem-solving networks are developed in an unusual incident response? Which informal contacts could be expected, and which capabilities were needed for the response?

Mapping of the risk landscape has led to a collation of national risk pictures in Denmark, Norway and Sweden as established by the national authorities. In terms of natural events, the national priorities are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of national priorities in terms of risks.

Denmark	Norway	Sweden
Coastal flooding	Extreme weather and flooding	Floods
Extreme rain		
Storms and hurricanes		Storms
	Avalanche	Landslides

Heat waves and drought		Heat waves
	Forest and outlying fires	Forest fires
	Volcanic activity	Earthquakes and volcanic eruptions
	Earthquakes	
Space incidents	Room weather	Solar storms

An important individual capability for problem-solving in the FRS networks has been identified: having the ability to understand perspectives. There are several factors influencing this ability, namely attitudes of the individual, cognitive processes and interpersonal skills. Also, the role of the organizational climate is found important as it needs to be forgiving and open to people making mistakes so that individuals feel that they can take initiative in operations.

Conclusions

The project is in its final year. Collated results show that there are both similarities and differences between the three Nordic countries included in the project. The final year is focused on bringing together results from case studies and workshops with the FRS to identify necessary capabilities and networks for problem-solving in the future.

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Fire and Rescue Service's Problem Solving

Different municipalities – different problem solving qualities

Gudveig Gjørund
NTNU Social Research
Trondheim, Norway
gudveig.gjorund@samfork.no

Petter Almklov
Department of Sociology
and Political Science
Organization
NTNU
Trondheim, Norway

Torgeir K. Haavik
NTNU Social Research
Trondheim, Norway

Keywords: Fire and rescue services, capabilities, high quality relations, problem solving networks, rural vs. urban

Abstract

Emergency preparedness functions can be solved successfully in very different ways, depending on the resources available. In more urban and professionalized contexts, resources and competence are more organized and readily available than in rural contexts. In the latter, several core functions will need to be maintained by means of different forms of volunteerism. Problem-solving networks and structures will then have to take different forms to be able to perform during emergencies in rural and urban areas. Authorities in Nordic countries want to change the structure of fire and rescue services (FRSs) towards bigger and fewer FRSs and more professionalization. What will then happen with the rural FRSs qualities?

Background

In Norway, there is great variation in geography and population density, which leads to differences in terms of size and organization of Fire and Rescue Services (FRS). There are fire services with only full-time employees, some with both full-time and part-time employees, and some with only part-time employees. 80% of all fire constables are part-time, and most often employed in 2% positions. They have their main employment elsewhere but are on call to respond when the alarm is raised.

A general signal from the central authorities is that they want to harmonize the FRSs services in Norway. In sparsely populated areas it is not economically or practically possible to implement a fully professional fire force, and the current heterogeneity in terms of manning and organization can be seen as a result of municipal ownership and adaptation to the local circumstances. To counter this, the authorities are exploring models with a stronger degree of management centralization in rural areas. This means that we are moving towards fewer and larger FRSs [1]. This strategy is based on the fact that fire and rescue expertise must be able to give the same services regardless of where you live, and by being affiliated with a larger FRS with more resources and opportunities for specialization, everyone will have access to the same expertise. This is according to the generalist municipality principle [2] in Norway which states that all municipalities have the same legal status and the same

responsibility for tasks assigned by the authorities, regardless of population settlement structure, economy or other characteristics.

Different approaches to rural FRSs

We find this view from the authorities also in the public investigation after the 2014 fire in Lærdalsøyri [3] – a small community consisting of old wooden houses. In January 2014 a fire broke out and spread quickly. It took 18 hours before the fire was put out, and 40 buildings were burnt to the ground [4]. The local FRS consisting of 16 part time fire fighters (PTFF) arrived Lærdalsøyri after a few minutes, and then called nearby FRSs for assistance. Several volunteer organizations and a lot of civilians participated in the extinguishing work, and many of them played a big part in preventing the fire from doing even more damage. Even if it was a dramatic and long-lasting fire, no lives were lost.

Two investigations show very different results when it comes to the management of the extinguishing work. The investigation from the Directorate of Civil Protection [3] emphasizes the local FRS' unclear organization and management and explains this by the fact that small FRSs are not able to carry out strategic organization quickly enough. Many of the participating actors did not agree in DSBs conclusion. They felt that this evaluation was not fair after the enormous effort they had made during the fire, and that the investigation report used the opportunity politically to mostly show DSB's outspoken goal of organizing the fire and rescue work in Norway in larger FRSs. The department of Justice and Emergency Preparedness therefore commissioned an independent evaluation from the consulting company Pricewaterhouse Coopers (PwC). In contrast to DSBs investigation, PwC emphasized that the response was managed in a fast, efficient manner with a high degree of initiative and independence, in accordance with the understanding of the situation at the scene of the fire [5]. This disagreement, though only superficially presented here, can serve as a starting point for the questions we elaborate on in the current paper. Are there problem-solving capacities in the part-time forces that we should know more about when evaluating changes in the organization of future FRSs in Norway?

FIRE21 and Norwegian cases

In the project FIRE21 we try to understand the formal and informal networks of the Fire and Rescue services in Norway, Sweden and Denmark in order for them to be organized in the most sufficient way to meet future needs and threats.

In this connection, 3 case studies have been carried out in Norway, 2 in rural FRS with part-time fire crews and 1 in a large FRS with full-time crews. We have examined the organizations and their use of formal and informal problem-solving networks and equipment. The findings from these cases can be an input to the ongoing debate about moving towards larger and more professional FRSs.

More than one way to be professional?

It is not only readily available resources in number that contributes to efficiency. Also, the realistically available coordination mechanisms represent important assets. In that regard, different qualities come into play in urban and rural FRSs. While the urban FRSs are depending on a greater degree of professionalization, resources available through informal relations play a relatively more important role in the rural FRSs. The qualities and benefits for urban FRSs are obvious, with their robustness of staff, specialized competence and systematic organization, representing a great advantage during most incidents. But how do rural ones, without sufficient resources to develop these kinds of qualities, compensate? We have seen at least three qualities in rural FRSs that are used in their operations:

1) Part time fire fighters use the competence they have from their daytime jobs actively during both prevention and emergency work.

2) In rural areas our findings indicate that PTFs distinguish less between personal and professional relationships, and that they use personal relationships more actively in professional contexts. Also, they more actively deploy their knowledge about the local demography and geography, acquired in capacity of their full-time job or elsewhere. This kind of local knowledge and relations represent a great advantage when it comes to flexibility in situational adaptation (which is necessary because of the scarce access to resources) and organizing the operations.

3) This local knowledge of the community is also used during emergencies to requisition equipment from, and even to get help from, local actors (such as farmers and craftsmen etc.) to operate them.

If these qualities are overlooked when reorganizing the FRS, we are in danger of losing some of the qualities in rural communities that not only are related to fire extinguishing, but also the local communities' emergency preparedness at large.

It is the feeling of commitment to their own local community, the pride they feel towards their local FRS, and being seen of their own fire chief and colleagues that are described as motivational factors for PTFs, and not the salary. They say that the sense of commitment and the motivation to continue as PTFs, would drop considerably

if they had to answer to an unknown fire chief in a large FRS far away from where they live. One part time fire fighter explains it this way:

“My big concern is if the politicians here find out that they only need one fire chief in this area, and that we will have to answer to a fire chief sitting 200 kilometers away. We will become an outpost and that will have negative impact on us as a crew. Sticking your head in the fire chief’s door can be worth its weight in gold. Many will reconsider their position as PTF if we have to answer to someone who do not know us.”

Long distances and low population density will persist. So, regardless of the choices of new models, one will need to preserve some of the abilities demonstrated by the current rural FRSs. The first step in this direction is to study and analyze them. The next step is to make sure that the changes are carried out in a way that preserves qualities that cannot be compensated for by professionalization and merger of FRSs.

Closing remarks

The structures of problem-solving are one of the things that differs between small and large FRSs. In small part time FRSs, the flexibility, because of the limited resources, is embedded in the way they have to execute their tasks, and their problem-solving network is built up of the PTFs own networks. Large and more professionalized FRSs also need to be flexible when unexpected incidents occur, but they have a more structured organization, and more available formal resources at hand, and the problem-solving networks consists of professional actors. In order for all kind of municipalities to be prepared for new challenges when it comes to fire and rescue services, one need to know more about the problem-solving structures – How they are built, how they function and how these functions can be maintained, in new times with societal, geopolitical and climate changes and threats.

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Present Risk Landscapes in the Scandinavian Countries

Frank Markert

DTU construct, Denmark's
Technical University
Kongens Lyngby,
Denmark
fram@dtu.dk

Nils Johansson

Faculty of Engineering, Fire
Safety Engineering
Lund University
Lund, Sweden
nils.johansson@brand.lth.se

Ole Anders Holmvaag

Brann- og redningsskolen
Direktoratet for Samfunds-
sikkerhet og Beredskap
(DSB), Norway
ole.holmvaag@dsb.no

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Abstract

Climate change is expected to change the risk landscapes of the Nordic countries, as e.g., more droughts, storms, and heavy rain episodes are expected leading to frequent and severe nature fires, floodings, avalanches and landslides.

As part of the Nordic project FIRE21 funded by NordForsk, the current procedures to identify the future risk pictures in the Scandinavian countries Denmark, Norway and Sweden have been investigated and compared. This paper presents today's recognized risk picture in the Nordic countries and how new risks are identified by the emergency services.

Introduction

The current work is part of the FIRE21 project deliverables in work package 3 "Understanding the Risk Landscape from a fire and rescue service perspective – Today and in the Future". The aim for the WP is to create a perception of the Nordic risk landscape today and a projection of potential risk landscapes of the future starting from a global perspective. The focus is on risks specifically relevant for the fire and rescue service. The rapidly changing risk landscape means that there is a need to follow any societal trends to be able to adopt any preventive and operational measures [2-4].

The discourse about new challenges due to changing risk landscape in Europe appears primarily to be dominated by direct impacts due to climate changes as it is foreseen based on input from international assessments and foresight documents, e.g., from McKinsey Quarterly, Bloomberg, Boston Consulting and other reputable sources. The climate descriptions and climate predictions presented in this paper comes from a combination of input from an ongoing project (Extreme-Index) run by the Lund University, analysis of reports from Nordic meteorological institutes and findings from the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

National Risk Assessments

For the Nordic countries procedures are established to work out and to update the national risk pictures in certain time intervals. For a summary of the reasoning behind, the OECD published the report "National Risk Assessments - Cross

Country perspective" in 2018 [4]. It describes the established national risk assessments for several OECD member states including Denmark, Norway, and Sweden.

Fig. 1. A general process to assess and report the national risk picture [5].

The national approaches may follow the EU Guidelines on National Risk Assessment for Disaster Risk Management [6, 7]. These guidelines are to be seen as an overall support and suggestions to facilitate the continuous process to achieve national risk assessments that are the basis to establish the national risk pictures. However, the EU guidelines do offer in-depth support for some of the stages in the assessment process, so each country needs to develop aspects of the national risk assessment process based on the intentions described in the guidelines. For example, in Sweden the following general process was presented in the country's first steps towards a national risk assessment [5]. These points are also shown graphically in Fig. 1. The first step is the very basis to define the valuable objects to protect against the emerging risks. Secondly, the potential risk these objects may be exposed needs to be identified. Third, it is necessary to select some key risks for further analysis, and fourth to develop base scenarios that are representative for most of the situations expected. Fifth, the key risks and scenarios are analyzed, and a risk assessment is worked out. Finally in step six, a synthesis is made of the individually analyzed scenarios, after a national risk assessment is compiled. The risk can then be presented in a risk matrix. The results from the assessment can then be used as a basis for prioritizing resources and activities.

A mapping conducted in FIRE21 compared the present acknowledged risks in Denmark [1, 2], Norway [3, 4], and Sweden [10]. As a starting point the respective national risk profiles/pictures developed by the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA), Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (DSB), and Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) have been evaluated. It is found that the main

risk categories are similar, but the main categories are differently sub divided into more specific threads within the main threads.

Statistics and Forecast Tools

An important source of information is emergency related statistics from each country. It is at the moment seen that climate change related emergencies as forest fires does not seem to change the statistics over the last decades, but it is clearly seen that such accidents when taking place as in 2018 require huge resources as shown in Fig. 2. In 2018, an increased forest fire frequency is observed for both Denmark, Norway, and Sweden. That year the main weather conditions were extremely warm and dry in all the three countries and in fact over most of Europe. This observation across Europe is important to remind, as it may negatively affect the potential of mutual resource sharing across the countries helping and supporting each other in large catastrophic emergency situations.

Fig. 2. Type of triggering event to responses by the rescue service to accidents and incidents in general and in the responses with more than 400 personnel hours in Sweden 2018-2021. [11]

To predict future emergencies and planning for proper dimensioning of the emergency services a number of tools are available. The scientific knowledge in the field is increased in our century and better understanding of the phenomena leads to better predictions. Together with the high-performance computing facilities many types of predictions may be done. These range from weather forecast and “dryness indicators” to consequence models based on GIS systems to evaluate the consequences of, e.g., flooding and forest fire spread and others. This is an important planning tool. Last not least forecasting is made possible by these various models and using special programs to analyze the “big data” needed to identify possible developments.

Conclusions

The research intended to map the present established national risk pictures in Denmark, Norway, and Sweden. It is found that the national processes to establish the respective national risk pictures are aligned by European guidelines. Besides the common pictures some differences in the risk pictures of the three Nordic countries are seen. These are explainable by the difference in topography and geography, the various

population densities, and the types of the countries industries, historical events and the established (critical) infrastructures.

To predict future trends of potential emerging risks and thus a proper future dimensioning of the emergency services the national risk pictures continuously refine their respective pictures within periodic updates. In case for Denmark e.g., in intervals of about 5 years, as national risk reports are established in 2013, 2017 and 2022.

These trends are still not clearly seen in the respective statistics but beginning trends may be seen when combining the present statistics with climate forecast models that predict future climate changes.

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ADAPTED FLASH-CAT METHODOLOGY TO MODEL HORIZONTAL CABLE TRAY FIRES USING COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS

N. Verma

VTT Technical Research
Centre of Finland Ltd,
Espoo, Finland
nikhil.verma@vtt.fi

S. Hostikka

Civil Engineering
Department Aalto
University, Espoo, Finland

J. Vaari, T. Korhonen, T. Hakkarainen

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd,
Espoo, Finland

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Abstract

Nuclear power plants (NPPs) use an extensive network of electrical cables that can catch fire and possibly lead to damage to the nuclear reactor core with widespread consequences. Therefore, accurately assessing the heat release rate (HRR) of cable fires is critical. Under OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) PRISME-3 project, IRSN (Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire) burned two cable trays in an open atmosphere to observe their fire behavior. Based on this, a computational fluid dynamics-based method was developed to model HRR through simulations. The method uses the modified FLASH-CAT model with the surface ignition temperature model of Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) software. Simulation matched the test HRR profile well. Such results provide confidence in using the outlined method in this paper.

Figure 1. Insulated side wall, horizontal cable trays, and blowtorches. Tray length is 3 m and cable length are 2.4 m.

Introduction

Numerical simulation has been done using Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS 6.7.7 [1]) software to replicate a cable fire test conducted by IRSN under OECD PRISME-3 project. Two horizontal trays (against an insulated wall as shown in Figure 1) having PE/PVC insulated electrical cables were burnt in an open environment under a large-scale calorimetric hood and fire related data like HRR, mass loss rate, emission factors (yields) etc. were collected and provided. The data from cone calorimetric tests along with the thermo-physical and chemical properties were also provided to be used in the simulation where FLASH-CAT model [2] was used in conjunction with FDS surface ignition temperature model. The FLASH-CAT model used properties such as linear mass

density, plastic mass fraction, tray width etc. to calculate the effective combustible mass of cable surfaces in FDS. On the other hand, thermo-physical properties like thickness, thermal conductivity, density, specific heat, ignition temperature etc. governed the heat transfer into the cable surface in FDS and the resulting ignition (if any). PE (cable insulation material) and PVC (jacket material) were involved in the combustion. A single step mixing controlled gas phase chemical reaction was formulated by IRSN as:

The reaction and its related stoichiometric coefficients were used in the simulation to model the combustion. Bench-scale average HRRPUA (Heat Release Rate Per Unit Area) was provided for two different irradiance values (average HRRPUA 245 kW/m² and 314 kW/m² at an irradiance of 50 kW/m² and 75 kW/m², respectively) from the cone calorimeter tests of cables.

Adapted Approach

The approach used here is based on the research conducted by McGrattan et al. [2], Zavaleta et al. [3], Beji et al. [4], and Viitanen et al. [5]. By combining their findings, the approach was modified with a few new intermediate steps to address any shortcomings and minimize their prescriptive values like fixed values for vertical and horizontal fire spread rates for trays etc.

FDS's surface ignition temperature model has been used in the simulations. Under such approach, when a computational cell in FDS having fuel surface properties attains pre-assigned surface ignition temperature, it gets ignited. Then it follows a pre-defined burning rate as a function of the time, i.e., HRRPUA(t), as shown in Figure 2. Such computational cells burn for pre-calculated local fire duration (Δt_{fire}) at a given location on cable surface. In this work, the local fire duration has been calculated as

$$\Delta t_{fire} = \frac{6\Delta H_c n \gamma_p (1 - \nu) m'}{5 \dot{q}_{avg}'' 2W_{eff}}$$

where ΔH_c (MJ/kg) is the heat of combustion, n is the number of cables on each cable tray, γ_p is the plastic mass fraction, ν is the char yield, m' (kg/mm) is the linear mass density, W_{eff} is the effective width of the cable tray, and \dot{q}_{avg}'' is the average HRRPUA obtained from cone calorimeter. The “2”

Figure 2. Idealized HRRPUA with respect to time

in the denominator was introduced by Zavaleta et al. in [1] to include both top and bottom areas of the cable trays against the original FLASH-CAT local fire duration formula which considered combustion only on one side of cable trays accounting for all the combustible mass. Moreover, cable surface built in FDS had openings based on the recommendation of Beji et al. in [4] and a stochastic approach to make simplified cable geometries for numerical simulations incorporating openings developed by Viitanen et al. in [5]. Obstructions in FDS representing the cable surface slab had randomly distributed openings, shown as black in Figure 3. Such openings are holes having volume of a single cell allowing smoke and flame passing through them.

Figure 3. Randomly distributed openings on cable obstruction in FDS

Thus, the new effective width, W_{eff} , was calculated as:

$$W_{eff} = \frac{\text{Area of the cable slab} - \text{Area of the openings}}{\text{Length of the slab}}$$

Figure 4. Idealized cable structure for one-dimensional heat transfer

Moreover, the internal structure of the cable was idealized for one dimensional heat transfer as shown in Figure 4 resulting

into two different conduction paths with different thickness. To obtain a reliable estimate of the thickness for the symmetrical half of the idealized cable, the average value was computed from the "thickness_short_path" and "thickness_long_path" and used for cable surface thickness, as it is difficult to determine the actual path for one-dimensional heat transfer in the cable structure in a real fire.

Simulation and Result

The computational domain was 1.5 m x 4.4 m x 5.2 m in dimension with uniform mesh of grid size 0.05 m. The top and side boundaries were given OPEN boundary conditions and floor had concrete properties. Simulation with $q''_{avg} = 245$ kW/m² led to slow fire growth, and another simulation with $q''_{avg} = 314$ kW/m² led to fast fire growth. It is clear that not all the cable surface computational cells will receive irradiance having extreme values of 50 kW/m² or 75 kW/m² in the entire duration of the actual fire. A simulation with $q''_{avg} = 279.5$ kW/m² (average of 245 kW/m² & 314 kW/m²) produced the best (average) profile of HRR (Figure 5) close to the test. Peak HRR was underestimated by 4%, and time to reach peak HRR was overestimated by 5%.

Figure 5. Heat release rate of test and simulation

Despite adapting the HRRPUA curve to the dynamic thermal feedback in the new FDS version 6.8.0 with min-max heat flux scaling, the results have not shown significant improvement especially in the decay phase. Further research is warranted at least on the choice of scaled heat flux limits.

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Old dog, new tricks? Cable fire testing with the LIFT apparatus

Michael Plagge
Division of Fire Safety
Engineering, LTH Lund,
and Department of
Energy & Transport
(Research &
Development), DBI
Lund/Hvidovre, SV/DK
mip@dbigroup.dk

Bjarne P. Husted
DTU and Department of
Energy & Transport
(Research &
Development), DBI
Kgs. Lyngby/Hvidovre,
DK
bph@dbigroup.dk

Patrick van Hees
Division of Fire Safety
Engineering, LTH Lund,
Lund, SV
patrick.van_hees@byggtek.lth.se

Gaëlle Fontaine & Serge
Bourbigot
UMET - Unité Matériaux et
Transformations, Lille
University
Villeneuve d'Ascq, FR
gaelle.fontaine@centralelille.fr
serge.bourbigot@centralelille.fr

Keywords: *Fire testing, LIFT, Power-to-X, cables, cable materials*

Abstract

Two selected cable products have been subjected to fire testing using a lateral flame spread and ignition (LIFT) apparatus. Its gas-fired radiant panel is designed to provide a heat flux varying along the test specimen, here cables, but uniform perpendicular to it. This setup allows not only to ignite a specimen but also to follow the fire spread along a given specimen length.

Placing the apparatus under a hood equipped with oxygen consumption calorimetry and adding thermocouples at varying depths inside the specimens allowed to record information on heat release rate (HRR), smoke characteristics and temperature profiles, in addition to the standardized measurement quantities such as e.g., time-to-ignition or flame-front velocities.

Results indicate that cable fire testing using the LIFT apparatus in the extended configuration shown is principally possible. Both products ignited after ca. 8.5 minutes. Flame-front velocities reached 20 – 43 mm/min. Peak heat release rates were measured between 9 and 22 kW, related total heat releases ranging from 1 to 10 MJ. Temperatures inside the specimens were measured at up to 590 °C.

Context

Renewable electric energy production, conversion (e.g., for storage) and consumption is on the rise in Denmark and elsewhere. “Power-to-X” or “P2X” is a related acronym adopted e.g., in Denmark, to describe energy conversion for various purposes [1].

Renewable energy in Denmark is currently mostly produced by converting wind and solar energy into electricity. Related facilities and equipment are placed off- as well as onshore, but usually exposed to typical Danish weather conditions. Based on the type of equipment, different requirements are put on the related cabling, internally and externally. For example, wind turbines require not only salt

water resistant but also torsion capable cabling. Hence, materials for insulation and protection (cable jackets) applied here differ from e.g., the standard (residential or industrial) building types. To derive proper design fire scenarios for P2X-installations (and to model those), we need to understand the related fire behavior.

Materials

Electrical power levels in P2X applications are higher than in usual residential and industrial environments, starting often at a few hundred Amperes (still low voltage class; < 1 kV). The carrying capacity of a cable is proportional to the type of conductor and its diameter. Typical P2X conductor diameters range from 150 to 600 mm². Overall outer diameter range from e.g., 10 to 50 mm accordingly.

Two different cable products have been tested in the LIFT. Both have different conductors, insulation, and jacket materials. The products are easily identified by color: grey or black. Hence, the “nicknames” and compositions (conductor, insulation, jacket) are as follows:

- Grey copper (GC): copper, polyethylene (PE), polyolefin (non-specified copolymer), and,
- Black aluminum (BA): aluminum, ethylene-propylene-rubber (EPR), thermoplastic polyurethane (PU)

Guided by the apparatus’ standards, short (155 ± 5 mm) and long (780 ± 5 mm) straight specimens have been tested. Both conductors have a nominal cross-section of 150 mm², outer nominal diameters were 23 mm (GC) and 26 mm (BA).

Apparatus

Introduced in the 1980s, the lateral flame spread and ignition apparatus (hereafter denoted LIFT) has been in use in various fire laboratories around the world. No less than 3 standardized test protocols exist, ASTM [2], IMO [3] and ISO [4].

The LIFT features a gas-fueled radiant panel providing thermal radiation to a sample, up to 65 kW/m². The panel and sample are angled at 15 degrees, exposing the sample to a heat

flux gradient along the sample rather than a constant value. Specimens may extend up to 155 x 800 mm (x 50 mm in depth). In the context of P2X the LIFT apparatus was chosen over e.g., the cone calorimeter, based on its ability to produce a longitudinal varying but lateral uniform heat flux but also as it allows the use of larger specimen.

Test setup

Standardized testing with the LIFT allows principally for estimating e.g., time to ignition or flame spread velocities. The IMO procedure refers principally to ISO [4] with some modifications, e.g., allows also for HRR measurements but with an out-of-date temperature measurement technique [3]. ISO standard annex F offers a procedure to mount cylindrical plastic piping. However, the assembly shall be “as representative as possible of a flat surface” [4]. That is not the case here.

In the present case the apparatus was placed under a hood equipped with oxygen consumption calorimetry, to add measurements on HRR and smoke characteristics. A modified sample holder was used to mount one single cable specimen in the middle (or 3 specimens in parallel).

Some experiments included up to 15 thermocouples (Inconel, type K, 1 mm tip diameter, Keysight data logger), embedded in the cable specimen’s conductor, insulation, and jacket material (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Single cable specimen in a modified holder with thermocouples added from the backside in the LIFT apparatus.

Calibration of the radiant panel was carried out using a water-cooled Hukseflux SBG03-050 total heat flux sensor, with a rated measurement range of up to 50 kW/m². For each calibration position 90 values were recorded at a sampling rate of 0.5 Hz.

A modified calibration board was used to not only calibrate according to the standards but also to map the heat flux across the specimen holder. Given the age of the used apparatus and some undergone modifications, this heat map provides a good alternative to understand the quality of the radiant heat flux towards the specimen.

Results

Using the LIFT for cable fire testing works principally well including measurements with oxygen consumption calorimetry. Testing was enhanced by adding thermocouples to follow temperature development and propagation.

Both cable products tested under unsteady and steady radiant heat flux conditions have been found principally ignitable. All four present materials, 2 insulation and 2 jacket materials, contribute to combustion.

While the GC jacket material and the BA insulation material are principally more “sturdy”, i.e., stay in place until combusted, the GC insulation and the BA jacket material are much more “mobile”, i.e., melt, boil, drip, and float off the cable specimen. Notably the BA jacket material made from polyurethane is easily melted off the cable and pooling e.g., in the specimen holder.

Measurements showed peak heat release rates between 9 and 22 kW, with total heat releases ranging from 1 to 10 MJ. Flame-front velocities were estimated at 20 mm/min and between 20 to 43 mm/min, for the GC and BA long specimens, respectively. While the GC product showed a more stable burning, the BA product varied, mostly due to the easily melting jacket material. Both product’s long specimens ignited at about 8.5 minutes of steady exposure to the radiant panel (auto-ignition, no pilot flame was applied).

Temperature measurements inside a GC long specimen showed a peak temperature of about 590 °C inside the cable specimen copper conductor. Temperature plots over time (not shown for brevity) allow to follow the heating by thermal exposure along the specimen.

All values above have been observed at a steady external heat flux (primary calibration position, definition cf. [2]) of 46.5 ± 0.5 kW/m², see also the section “Uncertainties” below.

Uncertainties

Putting cable products into the LIFT principally requires a recalculation of the actual radiant heat flux at the geometrical plane (here better: shape) of the material to be exposed. Related work is still ongoing, e.g., by solving the radiation transport equation numerically.

Cable specimens were tested unconditioned. Relative errors of the type K thermocouples are assumed with 1 K, the ones for the oxygen consumption calorimetry with ± 5% [5].

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Fire-induced breakage of modern windows

Hjalte Bengtsson

Dept. of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark
Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
hjab@dtu.dk

Luisa Giuliani

Dept. of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark
Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
lugi@dtu.dk

Lars Schiøtt Sørensen

Dept. of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark
Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
lss@dtu.dk

Keywords: Fire-induced glass breakage, breaking time, ventilation factor

Introduction

Ventilation conditions play a key role in determining the fire development in enclosures, and thereby, in how a fire affects the structural elements in the fire room. In general, larger ventilation openings lead to fiercer but shorter fires, whereas smaller openings lead to milder but longer fires, which leads to higher temperatures in the structural elements [1]. Therefore, an accurate and not overestimated prediction of the ventilation factor is paramount to avoid overestimation of the structural capacity in fire [1] and possible consequent fire-induced collapses of buildings. Moreover, it can be used to document structural survival through burnout as utilised in e.g., the Norwegian high-rise “Mjøstårnet” and similar tall mass timber buildings [2].

To predict the actual ventilation factor for a given enclosure, it is necessary to know whether and when the glass panes of the windows in the fire room break and to what extent. Common design practice as well as several studies [3], [4] indicate that breakage and fallout of single pane windows used in old buildings would occur already in the early phases of fire, before flashover. However, the same assumption might not be justified in case of modern energy-efficient windows, made of multiple glass layers, often toughened, laminated, or coated with solar shading or energy saving coatings [5]. Therefore, the use of modern windows might pose a threat to the structural fire safety of both existing and new buildings. This is because decreasing ventilation factors will prolong fires, which in turn will heat structural elements more and could lead to unpredicted collapses if not accounted for. However, based on the current knowledge of the phenomenon, the scale of the threat is not very well-known.

The authors have conducted a literature study [6] where several knowledge gaps were identified. This led to the development of a roadmap for future studies shown in fig. 1.

Figure 1. Roadmap for future studies into fire-induced glass breakage [7]

In the current study, the fire performance of modern windows is investigated with the aim to provide insights for better assessment of ventilation factors.

Methodology

The investigations are done using a Heat-Transfer Rate Inducing System (H-TRIS), which is a vertical gas burner that can expose a test specimen to heat radiation [8]. The H-TRIS at DTU is pictured in figure 2.

Figure 2. The H-TRIS with a protective shield in the DTU Fire Lab.

The distance between sample and burner is calibrated for a heat flux of 20 kW/m^2 , which is representing conditions at onset of flashover, on the glass sample for the first stage of the test. In the second stage, the panel is moved closer increasing the exposure to 40 kW/m^2 to investigate possible increase of fallout or breakage of toughened glass after flashover.

The samples are placed in a frame made of 22 mm fire-resistant calcium silicate board that gives a shading width of 15 mm around the edge of the glass samples.

For some of the experiments, the glass samples are also exposed to a mechanical load in form of an over-pressure on the heated side of the specimen. This simulates over-pressure in a fire room. As seen in the literature study [6], the pressure effects on window glass are not very well described in the existing literature.

The glass samples all have a size of $400 \times 400 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$. The aim of the experiments is to investigate the impact of different parameters on the breakage time and fallout area (ventilation opening) of a window. Based on the literature survey to map the knowledge gaps [6], the following parameters has been chosen for this investigation:

- Number of glass layers in assembly: 1; 2; 3
- Gas filling in gap between glass layers: Air; Argon (Ar)
- Glass type: Annealed (A); Toughened (T)
- Low-energy coating on glass: No; Yes
- Over-pressure in fire room: No; Yes

The literature study [6] found that knowledge about the effects of layering is limited, especially for three-layer windows. Thus, more knowledge about this parameter is relevant as most modern windows have three layers.

Fillings of argon gas in the void between layers in windows is common for modern windows as argon increases the insulating capabilities compared to atmospheric air. However, practically no research was found that addresses this parameter [6].

In modern windows, both annealed and toughened glass is used. This parameter is included to give data on both types of materials and to relate this parameter to the others in the study.

Low-energy coatings are commonly used in modern window to decrease the heat loss. However, very little knowledge exists on how this affects the fire performance of the glass [6]. Therefore, this study aims to provide such data.

The chosen parameters are combined in different ways as illustrated in figure 3 in order to investigate the effects of the individual parameters isolated and combined cf. the roadmap in figure 1.

Figure 3. Illustration of the interconnection of parameters in the study.

Perspectives and future research

Results of the experiments will be presented at NFSD 2024. Later, a series of future experiments is planned to take the knowledge from the experiments presented here and study the effects in full-scale room fires with full-scale and realistic windows. Additionally, inputs for finite element analysis will be developed based on the experiments to provide a model for engineers to model different aspects of window breakage in fires for specific projects.

The results of the research project can help increase fire safety on many different levels. For designers, more reliable and precise knowledge can be used to optimise structures and

to utilise the better knowledge on the fire development to increase safety. For existing buildings, where new windows are fitted as part of an energy renovation, designers can apply the updated knowledge to check the impact on the existing structures, thereby determining if upgrades to the fire protection is needed. Additionally, the new knowledge can be used by insurance companies to better tailor insurance policies for clients based on their specific buildings, and it can be used by fire fighters to better prepare their operations in a given building.

Furthermore, new knowledge on window breakage in fires can be utilised in fire design of façades to better limit or account for fire spread between compartments. In this case, it is often beneficial to have a low amount of fallout of window glass, as larger window integrity will limit fire exposure on façades, thereby limiting external fire spread.

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Guidelines for protection of WUI structures in Norway

Max Anthony Gribble
RISE Fire Research
Trondheim, Norway
max.gribble@risefr.no

Ragni Fjellgaard Mikalsen
RISE Fire Research
Trondheim, Norway
ragni.mikalsen@risefr.no

Edvard Aamodt
RISE Fire Research
Trondheim, Norway
edvard.aamodt@risefr.no

Keywords: *Wildfire, WUI, Norway, risk reduction, fire safety, safety zones*

Abstract

This study addresses the pressing need for wildfire mitigation strategies in Nordic countries, focusing on Norway's Wildland Urban Interface (WUI) areas. By analyzing past wildfires and ignition patterns for Norway, the research prioritizes flame contact prevention over spotting. Collaborating with stakeholders, the study aims to provide relevant and implementable guidelines, enhancing societal safety and protection of properties in Norwegian WUI areas.

Introduction

As the climate changes, more and worse wildfires are predicted to affect Nordic countries, including Norway and Sweden. Structures that exist in WUI zones (Wildland Urban Interface) are vulnerable to wildfires. Norway has no guidelines or recommendations for protecting these structures from wildfires.

The current work presents an overview of an ongoing study in the TREEADS project [1], aiming to provide implementable, economical, and practical guidelines for WUI structures, specifically suited to Nordic or Norwegian conditions. The study is based on literature studies, experiments, workshops, and practical observations.

International guidelines and their applicability to Norway

Countries such as the US and Canada have guidelines (Figure 1) for structure protection in WUI areas [2, 3]. These recommendations are based on studies of structure loss during wildfires in the respective countries. These international guidelines provide a blueprint for guidelines that could be implemented in Norway, but more information is needed in order to ensure that the recommendations are relevant for Norwegian conditions.

Wildfires and the WUI landscape in Norway

The Norwegian landscape is characterized by significant amounts of heather, juniper, and pine. Field observations from both real wildfire situations and controlled burns in Norway, show a tendency for low to medium intensity ground fires which is not the main cause for structure loss in North America [4, 5]. The aforementioned countries lose structures to more high intensity crown fires in comparison to Norway. Other factors to consider for WUI landscape in Norway is that they are characterized by isolated structures with vegetation close to structures, and many of the private homes and cabins are made of wooden materials, increasing the risk of structure loss. This shows the importance of well suited WUI guidelines for the Nordic climate. There is ongoing work within the TREEADS project to characterize the various types of Norwegian wildfires such as heather, grasslands, and forests so that the most effective preventative measures can be implemented in Norway.

Figure 1. Guidelines for WUI areas often include safety zones around a home, where there can be need for different measures at different zones around a house. Figure by TREEADS.

How structures ignite in the Norway and Sweden

Fire spread from wildfires to structures occur in one of three ways. Through spotting, which is burning embers landing and igniting a structure, flame contact, which is when a flame directly ignites a structure, and radiation, which is when a fire heats a structure to the point where it ignites. Studying previous fires that have caused structure loss in Norway and Sweden, the ignition method is more often flame contact with the facade than spotting [6], which is the most common cause of structure loss in North America. This implies that recommendations for Norway should prioritize measures to protect from flame contact rather than spotting (Figure 2).

Spotting and radiation are still a risk and safety measures to reduce the risk of structure ignition should be taken.

Figure 2. A wildland-urban-interface fire may lead to a disaster sequence. Understanding the fire spread mechanisms from wildland to buildings and having knowledge on building traditions and other unique factors for Norway is key for adapting international guidelines to Norwegian conditions. Figure by TREEADS.

Methodology for evaluating and prioritizing WUI recommendations for Norway

Currently, work is ongoing by means of workshops (Figure 3) and surveys to find which WUI recommendations will have the most significant impact on structure safety in Norway and also which are culturally and economically acceptable to implement in Norway. The participants of these workshops are fire services, insurance companies, actors within the fire protection industry, and experts/researchers. The aim is to release a set of recommendations that can be used nationally, by both government agencies and private citizens, to improve fire safety for structures in the WUI zones in Norway.

Figure 3. Group work among stakeholders in TREEADS to evaluate how different measures may improve fire safety, and to evaluate their relevance for Norway. Photo: TREEADS.

Expected results

This study is expected to yield a set of guidelines for WUI structures in Norway. The six cheap, implementable, and culturally acceptable recommendations are as follows:

1. Clear the house and immediate vicinity (including decks, gutters, and roofs) of the structure from debris build-up such as pine needles, leaves and mulch.
2. Safe Storage: Store flammable materials away from the house, including such things as lawnmowers, wood piles, furnishings, toys etc. (including storage underneath decks.)
3. Seal or ember proof Roof Eaves, Gaps and Vents: Seal any gaps or openings in your roof eaves to prevent ember penetration or outfit them with mesh/spark arrestors.
4. Have a lawn around your house (This is your defensible space) of about 5 meters. If suitable remove large ornamental plants from this area. Between 5 and ten metres from your house special consideration should be taken regarding coniferous trees, these should not be in this zone.
5. Keep your lawn well maintained and the grass relatively short.
6. Clear dead grass in autumn before the winter snows. This reduces the fire risk for a spring fire significantly.

Several other recommendations are being discussed and considered for inclusion in the final WUI guide.

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Wildfire fuels and spread characteristics

Using wooden materials as model systems

Magne Rosnes¹ (mrosnes1@gmail.com), Ellen Synnøve Skilbred² (ellen.synnove.skilbred@risefr.no), Edvard Aamodt² (edvard.aamodt@risefr.no), Ragni Fjellgaard Mikalsen² (ragni.mikalsen@risefr.no), Ivar S. Ertesvåg¹ (ivar.s.ertesvag@ntnu.no)

¹ Dept. Energy and Process Engineering, NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.

² RISE Fire Research, Trondheim, Norway

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cone calorimeter, fire spreading experiments, wood chips, boreal vegetation

Abstract

Samples of green and brown heather, juniper, lingonberry shrub, bilberry shrub (stem and branch separate) and stair-step moss are tested in a cone calorimeter to observe ignition and flaming time, together with heat release rate.

Wood chips and wood-fibres are tried as more controllable material to emulate wildfire fuel in fire spreading experiments.

Background

The risk of wildfires in a specific area depends on many factors, such as temperature, soil moisture, wind conditions, the presence and type of vegetation and the climate. With changing climate conditions, areas that were once not very susceptible to fires can be at greater risk. The severity and number of number of wildfires in Norway is expected to increase in the coming years with climate changes. Recently there have been several large grass and heathland fires due to high temperatures combined with low precipitation, including some quite unique winter fires [1, 2]. Wildfires may spread from wildland to the built environment, in so-called wildland-urban-interface fires (WUI), which can be a hazard for buildings and critical infrastructure. In this study, we explore fire characteristics of natural, Norwegian fuels, and how to use materials such as wood chips and wood fibre as model systems to document Norwegian wildfires in the laboratory.

Figure 1. Bilberry specimen in the field (October); branch and stem samples in the cone calorimeter sample holder.

Wildfire fuel

First, real samples of fuel were collected: Specimens of green and brown heather, juniper, lingonberry shrub, bilberry shrub (stem and branch separate) and stair-step moss. The samples were conditioned (23 °C, 50% RH) and investigated in a cone calorimeter (heat flux 35 kW/m²). The analysis showed that stair-step moss ignited most rapidly. The maximum variation in time to ignition across specimens was 39 s.

Large variations in burning time were observed. Lingonberry shrub, juniper, bilberry branches, and green heather burning times were similar and relatively short, while those of stair-step moss and bilberry stems were longer. Variations were seen for peak heat release rates (HRR) as

well, with especially juniper displaying high values of approximately 370-450 kW/m². Dissimilarities in average heat release rates further indicated differences in burning intensities across specimens. Additionally, total heat release calculations with different integration boundaries were explored. Because of this, it was discovered that for some specimens, a significant amount of total heat release occurred after flameout.

Fire spread – wooden materials as model systems

Using field experiments is challenging considering both safety, damage to nature and reproducibility of results, and it is therefore desired to find laboratory conditions that can expose a surface to similar flame front propagation, fire residence time and heat flux as a wildfire. Wood chips and wood fibres have been proposed as a potential fuel to imitate grass and heather fires in the laboratory, but parameter studies are needed to ensure similar fire behavior.

A parameter study of wood chips and wood fibres fires was conducted to investigate whether these fuels can be used to mimic Norwegian wildfires. The fuel bed was horizontal or tilted, and parameters such as wood chip humidity, wood chip size distribution, mixing and thickness of layers were varied. Properties such as flame front propagation, fire residence time and heat flux can be measured in the experiments and compared with properties measured previously in field work and in the literature. The focus of the parameter study was on small scale experiments, and for selected parameters, although scalability to larger scale is discussed.

The presentation is based on the master thesis work of the first author [3].

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Figure 2. Small scale experiment with wood chip fire in horizontal plane.

Figure 3. Large scale experiment (2.5 x 4 meters) with bottom layer of wood fibre, and top layer of fine wood chips.

Figure 4. Large scale experiment with wood fibre in a 20° incline.

Advancing EU Fire Safety: The KeepEUfiresafe Campaign and Manifesto

Author: Eugenio Quintieri, Managing Director of Fire Safe Europe – eugenio.quintieri@gmail.com

Abstract

The KeepEUfiresafe campaign is a collaborative effort across the European Union aimed at enhancing fire safety in buildings, receiving strong support from various Members of the European Parliament and stakeholders in the fire safety and construction sectors. Highlighting the urgent need for improved fire safety measures, it addresses new fire hazards introduced by the European Green Deal and emphasizes the necessity of tailored fire safety measures for vulnerable populations, including the aging and those in energy poverty, amidst the challenges posed by climate change. The campaign's manifesto calls for a comprehensive EU fire safety strategy, focusing on awareness, standardized data, educational initiatives, research, legislative integration, and enhanced market surveillance. This initiative seeks to advance fire safety measures within the EU, aligning with broader sustainability and public health goals, and showcasing a unified commitment to this critical cause.

Introduction

The KeepEUfiresafe campaign is a testament to the collaborative efforts across the European Union to enhance fire safety in buildings. Significant support for this campaign and manifesto has been garnered from various Members of the European Parliament, including Seán Kelly (EPP, Ireland), Carlos Zorrinho (S&D, Portugal), Ciarán Cuffe (Greens/EFA, Ireland), Maria da Graça Carvalho (EPP, Portugal), Adam Jarubas (EPP, Poland), Niels Fuglsang (S&D, Denmark), and Billy Kelleher (Renew, Ireland), as well as numerous stakeholders in the fire safety and construction sector.

The Rationale for Enhanced Fire Safety

In the EU, the majority of citizens' time is spent indoors, necessitating robust fire safety measures across all building types¹. The KeepEUfiresafe campaign's manifesto, underpinned by alarming statistics, reveals the urgency: nearly 5000 fire-related casualties occur annually in EU domestic settings.

The Impact of the European Green Deal

The European Green Deal introduces new fire hazards with its focus on decarbonizing buildings. Innovations like photovoltaic panels, electric vehicle charging points, and heat pumps increase ignition risks, while new building materials and methods present unique challenges in fire dynamics.

Demographic Considerations

¹ European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, "Indoor Air Quality": <https://oshwiki.osha.europa.eu/en/themes/indoor-air-quality-iaq>

The manifesto emphasizes the need for specialized fire safety measures for Europe's aging population and those in vulnerable living conditions, such as energy poverty.

Climate Change and Fire Safety

Climate change exacerbates fire risks through drier conditions and unpredictable weather patterns, affecting evacuation and firefighting efforts.

The Manifesto's Call to Action

The manifesto calls for a comprehensive EU fire safety strategy with key objectives:

1. **Awareness and Prevention:** Integrating fire safety into EU social protection frameworks.
2. **Standardized Fire Statistics:** Ensuring reliable and comparable data.
3. **Fire Safety Competences:** Promoting educational initiatives and certifications.
4. **Research and Innovation:** Incorporating fire safety into research on energy transition and sustainable innovations.
5. **Legislative Integration:** Embedding fire safety in building and energy transition policies.
6. **Standards and Test Methods:** Addressing gaps, especially concerning furniture and sustainable solutions.
7. **Enhanced Market Surveillance:** Ensuring product safety and building compliance.

Conclusion

The KeepEUfiresafe campaign and manifesto provide a comprehensive framework for advancing fire safety in the EU. Implementing these measures will not only protect citizens but also align with broader EU objectives of sustainability and public health. The significant backing from MEPs and stakeholders highlights the collective commitment to this crucial cause.

For further details and engagement, visit [KeepEUfiresafe](#) and [The Manifesto](#).

The importance of Problem-Solving Networks in emergencies

Lotta Vylund
Research Institutes of
Sweden, (RISE)
Borås, Sweden
lotta.vylund@ri.se

Gudveig Gjørund
NTNU Social Research
Trondheim, Norway
gudveig.gjosund@samforsk.no

Frank Markert
DTU construct
Kongens Lyngby, Denmark
fram@dtu.dk

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Abstract

To be able to solve problems arising in emergencies, actors need to work together in Problem-Solving Networks (PSN). In our research, we have explored how PSN functions when responding to adverse events, and our findings emphasize several key characteristics of a PSN that enhance problem-solving during emergencies.

Solving problems in emergencies with PSN

Solving problems in emergency situations present challenges for the fire and rescue services (FRS). Modern society not only presents new challenges for the FRS, but it also increases complexity due to the interconnected nature of modern life, marked by various interdependencies. Present/Encountered problems are often considered complex, unclear, and difficult to manage. To be able to solve these complex problems in emergencies, problem-solving depends on collective efforts where actors need to work together to solve the problems that appear (Frykmer, 2020; Nohrstedt, 2016). This collective effort to solve complex problems could be seen as taking place in a problem-solving network (PSN), which can be defined as a network of actors and/or artifacts and associated relationships relevant to bridging the gap between the problem's undesired current state and the desired goal state (Vylund et al 2024).

In the research project FIRE21, PSNs in Sweden, Norway and Denmark have been explored by conducting eight different case studies. The aim of the project is to improve problem-solving through understanding the underlying problem-solving networks in emergency management and establishing strategies for their development in support of societal change. In our research we have found several important characteristics of PSNs that contribute to better problem-solving in emergencies. These characteristics are described in the following sections.

How PSN are developed during emergencies

The purpose of a PSN is to solve a particular problem and include actors and/or artifacts and relationships needed to find

Figure 1. Problem-solving network created to find the location of a fire. Red color symbolizes actors and/or artifacts connected to the Fire and Rescue Service.

solutions to the problem at hand. The driving force behind developing a PSN lies within the relationships that contribute to solve sub-problems in emergencies. Example of how a PSN could act in emergencies is illustrated in Fig. 1. Here we see how the PSN was created to find where the fire was located within a larger building. The problem of locating the fire was centered around the Incident Command, which was responsible for establishing relationships of information flow between different actors and artifacts such as drawing of floorplans, smoke from the building, fire teams, residents, building owner etc. (Vylund et al 2024). In the figure, the upper part shows how actors and building drawing provides insights into the building layout. The lower part in the figure shows how visual observation of smoke created different sub-networks, each of which evaluated the presumed location of the fire.

Finding the right PSN by breaking down complex problems into sub-problems

Complex problems are inherently difficult to understand, and solutions can be hard to find. However, breaking down a complex problem by dividing it into more manageable sub-problems could be a way to easier understand the problem (Head and Alford 2015) and could be a necessary first step in addressing the whole comprehending understanding of the problem. This also allows the FRS to match the situation with previous experience and thereby manage the complexity. This supports the clarification of the problem and thereby make it easier to find the right type of components and relationships within the PSN to solve the problem.

Artifacts as a fundamental component

In the literature, networks are often studied in terms of organizational, contextual, inter-organizational or structural factors (Hu et al., 2022). However, problem-solving is influenced not only by the individuals and organizations engaged in the incident but also by the artifacts involved in the adverse event or in the response system (Vylund et al, 2024). This is exemplified in Fig. 1. with a burning building where the smoke from the building (artifact from the adverse event) together with drones (provides an overview of the burning building) support the responders in identifying where the fire is located and thereby leading to finding a solution to the problem. Also, different communication systems used during emergency response are crucial artifacts. This underscores the necessity to also comprehend and incorporate the relationships with artifacts into PSN.

Diverse skills in the PSN provide a depth of knowledge.

The complexity of problems in emergencies means that it is important to involve different stakeholders with different types of knowledge and backgrounds in the PSN. Different perspectives enhance the possibility of identifying the right problem, but also enhance the possibility of identifying the right type of solution. Here we acknowledge that also informal contacts are important to be able to solve problems, e.g. owner of the building, volunteers etc. In addition, our findings also show that complexity is in the eye of the beholder, and whether there is a problem or not is highly subjective (Smith, 1992; t Hart & Boin, 2001), and how to reach the goal might not be agreed upon (Klein, 1998). In other words, complex problems that seem challenging to one stakeholder may not be as complicated for another stakeholder, when tackled by people equipped with the right skills. In rural areas in Norway and Sweden there are a large number of fire fighters who are employed in small part-time positions (2%). These part-time fire fighters have different types of day jobs which also provide a great variety of diverse competence and skills into the FRSs in rural areas. This highlights the implicit value of collaboration between stakeholders who can bring different skills to the mix.

Qualitative relationships with continuous networking

As part of emergency preparedness, networking with different stakeholders is important to comprehend each other's roles and responsibilities and thereby make it easier to find the right actors to involve in the PSN when the emergency occur, e.g. joint exercises or meetings before the emergency facilitates that the actors get the know each other beforehand. This approach could also assist the FRS in managing relationships as vital resources, and better comprehending the efficacy of different relationships in addressing emergency challenges (Hu et al., 2022).

Flexible and adaptive capacity in PSN

Even if fires in rural areas can become just as big and complex as in big cities, small local FRSs are not dimensioned, nor specialized, to be prepared for all types of incidents. What we have seen in FIRE21 is that small local communities where people know each other, it is often easier to have an overview of informal actors in the municipality who can assist with their expertise or equipment. This then becomes a way of adapting and compensating for the fact that they have less capacity, equipment and have available specialists for every imaginable incident than the larger and more professional FRSs.

FIRE 21

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Well connected?

Important individual qualities for collective problem-solving in the fire and rescue services

Tove Frykmer

Division of Risk
Management and Societal
Safety, Lund University
Lund, Sweden
tove.frykmer@risk.lth.se

Victoria Johnson

Division of Risk
Management and Societal
Safety, Lund University
Lund, Sweden
victoria.johnson@risk.lth.se

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Abstract

To develop an effective fire and rescue service (FRS) for the future, it is important to explore essential qualities needed to support the field. The fourth work package in the project FIRE21 uses a multi-step process that incorporates insights from expert interviews and literature to filter out essential individual qualities that are important for collective problem-solving. With these in mind, a workshop was conducted with FRS in southern Sweden to identify their perception of important qualities, with an emphasis on the need for understanding perspectives. Preliminary conclusions suggest that these qualities can be grouped into attitudes, cognitive processes, and interpersonal skills, all essential for understanding perspectives. Additionally, organizational factors impact the presence of such individual qualities in the group.

Individual qualities for collective problem-solving"

The research project FIRE21 investigates problem-solving in the FRS in the 21st century. The objective of the project is to bed for an effective FRS in the future and it will explore which essential abilities best support the field.

The fourth work package, presented here, concerns individual qualities that are important for collective problem-solving. The FRS often face complex problems, in a context characterised by uncertainty and time pressure. In order to solve these kinds of problems, collaboration between involved individuals and organisations is crucial [1]. Given this context, effective problem-solving in the FRS will require input from many individuals and, therefore, the qualities of these individuals will matter.

Method

Our research used a multi-step process that started by integrating insights from experts in problem-solving-related fields, with a literature review based on their references. This consolidated the theoretical foundation of the research. The interviews were conducted in the fields of psychology, cognitive science, pedagogy, computer science, political

science, and logistics which all had valuable insights into the challenges and success factors of collective problem-solving. Building upon the knowledge gained in these interviews, we delved into the literature recommended by the interviewees. From these, we filtered out a wide collection of individual qualities which are generally important in group work and problem-solving, as well as external factors which have an impact.

Using this theoretical background, we conducted a workshop with fire and rescue professionals in Sweden to get input from the field on what they see as important qualities, with a special interest in their take on understanding different perspectives as such a quality. This workshop had two parts: the first focused on understanding perspectives and what other qualities and aspects play into that. The second part zoomed out and opened for discussions on what they as professionals saw as important. Similar workshops will be planned in Denmark and Norway to capture any differences in context affecting what is seen as important. Finally, a more widespread survey will be sent out to all three countries within the Nordic FRS officer network to validate the results.

Understanding of perspectives

In our exploration of collective problem-solving in FRS operations, we found many qualities essential for effective collaboration. From adaptability to the influence of experience, effective communication, and the role of group composition and dynamics, the findings provide insight into the multi-faceted nature of successful problem-solving in groups.

Adaptability in this context relates to the ability to reassess problem definitions, engage in self-reflection, and navigate the evolving dynamics of emergency situations. One method of being more adaptive is to use self-reflexive examinations [2]. Related to this, experienced individuals tend to be better at adapting to the given context as well as dealing with contradicting information [1], as well as handling time pressure [3]. Communication and knowledge sharing filters into several aspects of collective problem-solving, with varying methods of looking at the quality or effectiveness of it. Especially important in the case of FRS is the potential pitfall of "groupthink" occurring, for instance, due to a desire to maintain friendly relations in the group and

thus becoming more uniform with fewer perspectives present in conversation [4]. Additionally, when collective problem-solving is taking place across different actors and/or organizations it can be important in collaboration to have a type of “translator” between organizations [5].

A main finding from the research was that understanding perspectives emerged as a key factor for collective problem-solving in FRS operations. In the context of emergencies, being able to understand the problem from different angles, the needs and capacities of involved response organisations or the needs of the affected population are examples of important perspectives to apply, and thus a part of this suggested quality. While there are many more qualities to consider to understand the entirety, what we found was that a lot of these qualities are of importance because they lead to a better capability of understanding different perspectives. Therefore, we see understanding perspectives as a key quality that one wants to obtain, with the help of complementing, underlying, qualities.

Workshops with professionals

With our theoretical base set, we conducted the workshop with an FRS in Southern Sweden. From this, we gathered several aspects which professionals saw as important for understanding perspectives: such as trust between individuals and actors, and simultaneous capacity/the ability to multi-task. The participants brought up the role that different attitudes play in understanding perspectives as you need to be curious, willing to understand and invite new perspectives. According to participants, the way this looks in practice is showing an interest and asking questions, showing initiative and working on following up. Taking initiative was mentioned repeatedly as an important factor of operations in general, as well as for the benefit of understanding perspectives.

The professionals also report a need to have knowledge of their own internal system, and that of other actors, as well as an overall knowledge of society. This aspect is potentially the most straightforward to develop with the help of traditional learning. Interestingly, it can be important to remember that understanding perspectives is different depending on different leadership functions, due to the scale of operations and the time aspect associated with the different stages. One additionally needs to be able to sort, prioritize between, and sift through perspectives.

Additionally, the organizational climate is mentioned as important as it needs to be forgiving and open to people making mistakes so that individuals feel that they can take initiative in operations. If the organization is not open-minded, then the team members may be discouraged from applying their individual qualities at full capacity, such as taking initiative, due to a fear of acting the wrong way.

For future qualities, the FRS professionals expect that these will relate more to knowledge-based qualities, as well as cooperating with new groups of people both internally in their organization but also with other actors. In addition, they suspect that they may need to have more knowledge on

leading autonomously if they were to lose contact with their team, as that may be more of a frequent risk in the future.

Preliminary conclusions

Given the results from our theoretical framework, combined with those of the FRS workshop in Sweden, we can draw several preliminary conclusions. There is an agreement that understanding perspectives is important for collective problem-solving, and there are several factors which feed into, or are a part of, this quality. These can be grouped into 3 different categories: (1) attitudes of the individual, (2) cognitive processes and (3) interpersonal skills. Additionally, while the organizational factors are somewhat outside of this project's scope, it is still highly relevant given the significant impact that professionals perceive this to have on whether the individual and collective attitudes are shown in the group.

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Theorizing rescue services as organizations

Michael Grothe-Hammer

Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Michael.grothe-hammer@ntnu.no

Abstract

“Rescue services” as defined as those “emergency services...which serve to bring people out of danger, attack, harm, etc” (Collins Dictionary 2024) are a universally known and established social phenomenon in large parts of the world. Their importance in modern society cannot be understated given that these services literally save lives from imminent danger. Whereas there is much research on rescue services, for example, in respect to their management and governance, there exist little theorization about what constitutes and characterizes the thing called rescue services. Indeed, rescue services are often researched as cases for other theoretical discussions. Rescue services can be found as case studies of flexible bureaucracies (Bigley & Roberts 2001), public administrations (Comfort et al. 2012), crisis management as well as sensemaking in "turbulent contexts" (Maitlis & Sonenshein 2010), hybrid network governance (Berthod et al. 2017), adaptive structuring (Roberts et al. 2008), high-reliability organizations (Weick & Sutcliffe 2007), project organizations (Bakker 2010), or even organized behavior in disasters (Dynes 1970) - to name just a few examples. However, rescue services have not received a substantive social-theoretical consideration as a relevant phenomenon in its own right.

To address this gap, I suggest to theorize rescue service as a particular type of organization with specific characteristics. I assert that fire departments, emergency medical services, technical assistance organizations, search and rescue services and the like constitute one type of organization that can be meaningfully categorized and theorized as rescue services or more specifically as organizations for emergency rescue.

Drawing on social systems theory (Luhmann 2018; Grothe-Hammer 2022), I will outline that rescue services can be understood as autonomous organizational systems specialized in rescuing people and objects from emergencies. Structurally, they exhibit special characteristics. Confronted with the challenge of having to deal with all expectable and non-expectable emergencies, often in particularly dynamic and time-critical situations, rescue services exhibit a special relationship between rigidity and flexibility of their organizational structures. First, they exhibit an inevitable under-specification of goals and rules stemming from the fact that concrete goals are usually decided spontaneously during the operation, and that concrete operations can be pre-structured in a rule-based format only to a very limited extent. Second, rescue services are characterized by a pronounced specification and differentiation of vertical and horizontal communication channels and hierarchies (responsibilities, division of labor, addressability, decision-making authority), as well as generally highly qualified personnel. Thereby, the high degree of specification of communication channels, hierarchies, and personnel compensates for the under-specification of goals and rules and allows the latter to be used as an area of necessary flexibility in operations. Third, these structures are accompanied by a culture of collective mindfulness. This counteracts possible negative effects of strong hierarchies by attaching particular importance to the expertise of the personnel. It also ensures that staff constantly question their own processes and interpretations and attaches particular importance to even minor mistakes. Fourth, as a result of these particular structures and organizational culture, rescue services are very often granted a high degree of self-referential evaluation. Thus, rescue services usually evaluate the success of their actions themselves - which once again distinguishes them in

from those types of organizations that are confronted with similarly dynamic and uncertain situations, such as law enforcement or the military.

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Lateral flame spread on PMMA in vertical orientation

Realisation of pyrolysis simulations with Fire Dynamics Simulator

Osburg, Manuel

Brandschutz Consult

Ingenieurgesellschaft

mbH Leipzig

Leipzig, Germany

m.osburg@bcl-leipzig.de

Troff, Anna

Brandschutz Consult

Ingenieurgesellschaft

mbH Leipzig

Leipzig, Germany

a.troff@bcl-leipzig.de

Keywords:

Lateral flame spread, pyrolysis, PMMA, Fire Dynamics Simulator, FDS

Abstract

In this contribution lateral flame spread in vertical orientation is analyzed for PMMA. For this purpose, the standardized experimental setup described in ISO 5658-2 [1] was implemented in Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS). The target values for heat flux to the surface of the sample given in the norm were recreated in FDS simulations and the agreement was analyzed for different grid sizes. Blind calculations for different pyrolysis models were conducted to predict the lateral flame spread on PMMA, also with different grid sizes. The results will be compared to the measurements in planned experiments.

Experimental setup

The CFD simulations and experiments regarded in this contribution are based on the experimental setup described in ISO 5658-2 [1]. In this setup specimens are exposed to a well-defined field of radiant heat flux. The time of ignition, length of lateral spread of flame and extinguishment are recorded.

The specimen is placed in vertical orientation opposite a gas-fired radiant panel. The radiant panel is angled 15° away from the specimen resulting in a changing distance between panel and specimen along the specimen's length.

Figure 1. Schema of experimental setup (lateral flame spread) [1]

Recreating target values with FDS

For the calibration purposes target values and tolerances for the heat flux to the surface of the specimen are given in ISO 5658-2. These target values are given for 16 locations along the specimen length.

A simplified version of the experimental setup was implemented into FDS where the radiant panel is depicted as a surface with a specified temperature and emissivity (see Fig. 1). For the implementation of the angled arrangement an unstructured geometry (&GEOM) was used. The temperature was specified using the generalized inverse modelling framework PROPTI [2]. The optimization algorithm SCE-UA was used to output the temperature of the radiant panel that leads to the best possible match to the target values (gauge heat flux with emissivity of 0.95). A radiator temperature of 887°C with an emissivity of 1 was calculated. For the simulations a grid size of 6.25 mm and 500 radiation angles were used.

Figure 2. Simulation setup for determination of radiator temperature

In figure 3 the comparison between FDS results and target values for different grid sizes are shown. For 6.25 mm and smaller grid cells, the calculated heat fluxes are within the tolerance range for most target values.

Figure 3. Comparison between FDS results and target values

Blind Calculations with PMMA

With the calibrated simulation setup, blind calculations were carried out using FDS to calculate the fire spread on a PMMA sample. The parameters for complex pyrolysis were estimated by Hehnen et al [3], based on MaCFP database [4].

Figures 4 and 5 summarize the results of an exemplary blind calculation for a grid size of 6.25 mm. The initial flame propagation in the region with high heat flux is relatively fast. From the 400 mm position, the flame propagation stagnates before dying out at 570 mm. These results do not correspond to the authors expectations, because a complete burn-up was expected for PMMA. Further blind calculations with a lower grid resolution and other modelling methods are currently being processed.

The blind calculations are used to gain a better understanding of the interactions between the model inputs and simulation results.

Figure 4. Results of an exemplary blind calculation (time: 150 s)

Figure 5. Results of an exemplary blind calculation (grid size 6.25 mm)

Outlook

In the next step, several experiments with the setup described above will be carried out to examine the flame spread on PMMA. Additional measurements of temperature and heat flux will be taken during the experiments as well as the mass loss rate.

The results of the experiments will be used as a validation basis for pyrolysis models.

BESKID

These investigations are part of the BESKID project [5], which is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research.

The overall objective of the project is the development of two AI systems that allow to perform fire spread simulations especially in rail vehicles based on less experimental data. In this context, cross-scale fire experiments are carried out to obtain parameter sets for pyrolysis modelling and to validate these models.

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Limiting Lip Height Effect in Pool Fires

Temperature controlled container

Einar Arthur Kolstad
Western Norway
University of Applied
Sciences, (HVL)
Haugesund, Norway
einar.kolstad@hvl.no

Ulrich Krause
Otto von Guericke
University Magdeburg,
(OVGU)
Magdeburg, Germany

Kim Christensen
Imperial College
London (ICL)
United Kingdom

Vidar Frette
Western Norway
University of Applied
Sciences, (HVL)
Haugesund, Norway

Bjarne Chr. Hagen
Western Norway
University of Applied
Sciences, (HVL)
Haugesund, Norway

Keywords:

Limiting Lip Height, Pool fires, Temperature control.

Abstract

Pool fires have been widely studied since the 1950s. Work to be published by Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL) shows that pool fires in freestanding containers will burn for a time before self-extinguishing. The distance from the container rim to the fuel surface when fire ceases is called the Limiting Lip Height (LLH). This work compares the results from the mentioned HVL experiments and temperature-controlled experiments.

Three container diameters have been studied; the diameters were 100, 150 and 200 mm. The heights of the containers were 450, 500 and 800 mm, respectively.

The average limiting lip height in the experiments with no temperature control thus, room temperature was 213 ± 9.9 , 314 ± 12 , and 490 ± 27.8 mm for 100, 150, and 200 mm diameters, respectively.

At the end of January 2024, five experiments were conducted in a container with a diameter of 100 mm, and the temperature at the container wall was kept at approximately 4°C by using a water bath with ice. The results show that the average limiting lip height was 185.8 ± 8.5 mm.

This result shows that the limiting lip height is reduced by 13% for heptane burning in a temperature-controlled container with a diameter of 100 mm. Experiments using containers with $D=150$ mm and $D=200$ mm will be conducted spring 2024.

Introduction

Pool fires have been studied since the 50's, led by Blinov and Khudiakov [1, 2]. In the 80's Babrauskas presented a formula for the mass-loss rate from pool fires [3] based on the work of Bouhafid and Joulain [4]. Kolstad *et al.* have studied the mass-loss rate in pool fires [5, 6].

Work to be published from Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL) shows that pool fires in freestanding containers will burn for a time before self-extinguishing. LLH values for diameters 100, 150, and 200 mm, are given above.

These results raised the following research question: What would happen if the container walls were cooled, and

how would that affect the LLH? This is a presentation of preliminary results from experiments in which the temperature of the container walls was fixed between 3 and 8°C during the experiment.

Experimental setup

Three container diameters have been studied; the diameters were 100, 150 and 200 mm, and the heights were 450, 500 and 800 mm, respectively. Figure 1 shows the experimental setup used to study the effect of controlling the temperature of the outer container walls.

A container with thermocouples attached was placed inside a cargo container ($D=572$ mm), secured with a 4 mm chain, and tightened with turnbuckle. Ice and water were then filled in the cargo container. Finally, the container was filled

Figure 1: Container with heptane in a cargo container filled with water and ice. The red dots show the arrangement of thermocouples, from the rim and every fifth centimeters downwards the outer container wall.

to the brim with heptane, and the liquid ignited with a lighter. The fire burned till it self-extinguished, and the limiting lip height, the height from the container rim to the heptane surface, was measured.

Preliminary results

The results achieved at the time this abstract is written are from six experiments in the container with a diameter of 100 mm, five in container with diameter of 150 mm, and three in container with diameter of 200 mm. The results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The stars show Limiting Lip-Height (LLH) from 14 experiment, six from $D=100$ mm, five from $D=150$ mm and three from $D=200$ mm.

The LLH is 188.3 ± 9.8 mm compared to the container with no temperature control, where the average LLH was $213 \text{ mm} \pm 9.9$ mm. This gives a reduction in the LLH of 12%. For $D=150$ mm and $D=200$ mm the reduction was 17% and 29%, respectively.

The effect of cooling the container was expected to be less for larger containers. However, this is not the case for the tested container diameters, and the reason for this has not yet been evaluated.

The fuel surface of a pool fire receives radiation from the fire, the container wall, and conduction through the container wall. When the container walls are kept at approximately 5°C , the conduction is eliminated, and the radiation from the wall to the fuel surface is significantly reduced. Therefore, the fuel surface receives less energy when the container walls are cooled. The result is a lower LLH for the cooled containers. The effect increases with container diameter, indicating that wall-to-fuel radiation gives an important heat contribution in the free-burn case for large containers.

Conclusion

Heptane burning in cooled containers will have a lower Limiting Lip Height than in containers without temperature control. The difference between these two cases is the reduced conduction through the container wall from the heated upper part of the container to the lower part of the container where the heptane is located.

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Measurement results from fires

Analysis of Environmental Incident Service measurement data from 2008–2021

Henry Keijzer

Centre for Environmental
Safety and Security, Dutch
National Institute for Public
Health and the Environment,
(RIVM), Bilthoven,
Netherlands

Henry.keijzer@rivm.nl

Rob Jongeneel

Centre for Environmental
Safety and Security, Dutch
National Institute for Public
Health and the Environment,
(RIVM), Bilthoven,
Netherlands

HenkJan Manuel

Centre for Environmental
Safety and Security, Dutch
National Institute for Public
Health and the Environment,
(RIVM), Bilthoven,
Netherlands

Keywords: (5 key words)

Environmental incidents, hazardous substances, health risks, measurements, fire.

Introduction

Fires produce many substances that are hazardous for humans and the environment. These substances can be dispersed throughout the surrounding area and can be hazardous to health if people inhale them or come into contact with them. The type and quantity of hazardous substances produced and spread by a fire depends on factors including the materials involved in the fire and the combustion process. Virtually all fires form certain hazardous substances, including soot, particulate matter, CO, CO₂, various volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). Other substances may be released specifically as a result of the combustion of certain materials, such as dioxins (from certain plastics) and metals (including heavy metals) from sources including scrap metal, construction materials and waste.

In 2007, the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) published a report on the nature and quantities of substances that may be emitted during fires [1] based on i) data from the literature; ii) fire tests conducted in a laboratory and full-scale tests with controlled fires; and iii) measurements taken by the Environmental Incident Service (MOD) at fires in the 1997–2007 period. This report concluded that, while substances may be released in high concentrations, this is not necessarily harmful to health, depending on the rise, dispersion and diffusion of the smoke plume. Particularly at locations more than 1 km from the origin of the fire, the health risks are extremely small. In practice, this is known as the ‘one-kilometre rule of thumb’.

The MOD has taken measurements of hazardous substances in the living environment in connection with more than 130 fires after 2007. We have studied these incidents to systematically analyse measurement data to update the ‘emission from fires’ report from 2007 and to determine whether it is necessary to adjust and/or supplement the insights and conclusions. The study included questions like: is the one-kilometre rule of thumb still valid? Are there criteria

that make taking measurements at fires a matter of necessity? Is the measurement strategy of the MOD up-to-date?

Methods

RIVM has obtained data from the MOD’s reports on fire incidents and systematically arranged it in an overview. These data include information such as the date, time and location of incidents, the materials burned, the samples which were taken and the main points of the analyses.

Based on this overview, in-depth analyses were conducted on the various substance groups measured. This was done by systematically compiling and comparing the quantitative and semi-quantitative measurement results for each substance group. Concentrations of measured gas-phase substances were compared to the Dutch intervention values: these values are used to assess the potential risks to human health which result from acute releases and support the management of chemical incidents [2]. An extensive overview of the MOD measurements methods and strategy has been described in a RIVM report [3].

Results

For the analyses, we made use of a data set consisting of measurement data collected by the MOD at 132 fire incidents in the 2008–2021 period. The MOD conducted most of the measurements at building fires and fires in which materials such as plastic, waste, rubber, chemicals, scrap metal, electronic equipment and wrecked/demolished cars were involved in the combustion process.

Results for gas-phase compounds (VOCs, aldehydes, ketones)
In case of a fire, the MOD often detected concentrations of VOCs that were elevated compared to the background levels in both the source and effect areas. Aromatic compounds (benzene, toluene, styrene etc.) and aliphatic compounds (alkanes, alkenes and alkynes) in particular are formed in nearly every fire. Benzene is nearly always detected in the highest concentration, followed by styrene, toluene and naphthalene. In only few incidents specific Dutch intervention values were exceeded; the Instruction guidance value was exceeded five times and only one incident involved an exceedance of the Alarm boundary value. These incidents

involved substances such as acrolein and methyl methacrylate that were sampled directly from the smoke plume. At distances greater than 300 m the MOD detected levels of VOCs that were barely elevated above normal. The same was true for aldehydes and ketones.

Results for dust-bound compounds (PAHs, elements, dioxins)

Of the 132 fire incidents, 58 incidents involved testing for elements, 52 were tested for PAHs and 46 for dioxins. In some of the incidents, these substances were identified in total suspended particulate (TSP) samples. The deposition was also frequently determined, by testing deposited dust (dustfall) wipe samples and/or analysing grass and crop samples. This study showed that high concentrations of PAHs, dioxins and some elements (mostly metals such as lead, zinc, copper and antimony, but sometimes other elements) were often present in the source area (<300 m from the origin of the fire), especially in TSP samples – but not always. The MOD measured elevated concentrations in the effect area (medium distance: 300 m to around 1 km from the origin of the fire) as well, although not as high and not as often as in the source area. In rare cases, concentrations higher than the background level were measured further away from the fire than 1 km. This usually pertained to dioxins. In dustfall wipe samples and grass and crop samples, the concentrations of PAHs, dioxins and elements were less elevated than in the TSP samples.

Despite the fact that elevated concentrations of PAHs and metals may occur in the effect area, exposure to these concentrations generally does not lead to intake higher than health-based guidance values, whether through inhalation, hand-to-mouth contact or the ingestion of crops. The MOD detected (slightly) elevated concentrations of metals and dioxins in grass samples taken at distances of up to 1 km and – in the case of a handful of fires – even at distances greater than 1 km. These concentrations sometimes exceeded the limits for dioxins in livestock feed. While exceedances tend to be small, there is a risk that contaminated grass will find its way into livestock feed. This could lead to an exceedance of the maximum permitted levels of dioxin in milk and meat.

Conclusion and recommendations

Based on the results of this study, it is possible to conclude that the research findings based on measurement results from the 2008–2021 period are largely in agreement with those of the 2007 study. This study confirms the ‘rule of thumb’ that hazardous concentrations of substances are almost never present at distances greater than 1 km from the origin of the fire, neither in the air nor through deposition (dustfall). With regard to VOCs, aldehydes and ketones, measurements taken at distances of less than 1 km also detected no concentrations that would pose a health risk. For this reason, we recommend either to stop these types of measurements or conducting them only in exceptional circumstances or at the request of emergency response teams or a relevant competent authority.

We recommend that measurements of PAHs, elements (metals) and dioxins in TSP samples, dustfall wipe samples and grass and crop samples should be performed especially in fires with the following characteristics:

- very large, complex and long-lasting fires ;

- a limited plume rise during a portion of the fire;
- heavy smoke development.

Measurements are particularly advisable for fires at industrial sites involved in waste processing, demolition and recycling, and in warehouses and large buildings, when the burning materials are scrap metal, plastics (such as polyvinyl chloride), bitumen, car tyres, rubber materials, chemicals, wood waste (especially impregnated wooden garden products) and electronics. In these types of fires, there is a possibility that hazardous substances (particularly dioxins and metals) will be produced and spread. With regard to dioxins, measurements are worthwhile only if grazing land for livestock, crops for human consumption and/or grass or crops that are being grown for livestock feed are present in the downwind area less than 3 km from the fire. The MOD can also supplement this by taking samples of TSP in the smoke plume, for which it uses a rapid X-ray fluorescence (XRF) screening to determine the chlorine content. This provides an indication of whether it is necessary to sample and analyse dioxin levels. The MOD will use these recommendations to revise its measurement strategy for fire incidents.

Another important conclusion is that the information from the 2007 study, which identified the types of substances that were emitted during fires involving specific types of material, is still up to date and relevant. It remains desirable that further research be conducted into types of substances that have – as of yet – not been measured by the MOD, but which may be present in the smoke from fires. A few examples of such substances are isocyanates (investigations started this year), amines, nitriles, nitro-PAHs, flame retardants, brominated dioxins, hydrogen bromide and hydrogen fluoride. It is also possible that new developments, such as the energy transition, will give rise to new kinds of fires that might release other potentially hazardous substances like the spread of photovoltaic solar panel particles [4] or where the concentrations of the hazardous substances released will be different.

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Reuse of fire safety components

A possible assessment process to evaluate the potential of reuse

Björn Hedskog

Brandskyddslaget

Stockholm, Sweden

Bjorn.hedskog@bsl.se

Felicia Klint

Brandskyddslaget

Stockholm, Sweden

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Abstract

This paper summarizes an assessment process that can be used when evaluating the reusability of fire safety components. The assessment process has been derived from a literature study where building codes, test standards and guidelines has been reviewed and later combined with experience from the field of fire safety design in practice. This paper also includes the results from a theoretical application of the assessment process on the component “fire door”. The results show that performance-based design must be used when reusing an older door in a new building or a new position.

Introduction

Climate change is one of today’s biggest challenges and it is causing unnatural weather patterns worldwide. We all need to change our behaviors and do what we can to stop the ongoing, unsustainable development. We need to think smart, reduce the use of new material and find solutions regarding energy production and energy consumption. One way to do this is to reuse building materials and building components when the lifetime of a building has ended.

Within the building industry there are many ongoing projects within this field [1] but until now there have been few initiatives that include the aspect of reusing and expanding lifetime for different fire safety components.

In Sweden the building code limits the possibilities to reuse fire components and installations. The Swedish building regulation requires that the necessary level of fire protection is determined by using either prescriptive design where you follow mandatory provisions or applying performance-based design. Performance-based design requires design through qualitative assessment, scenario analysis, quantitative risk analysis and calculations or a combination of these methods. When applying prescriptive design, it is required that components used meet certain standards or that the component has a type-approval which demonstrates the fire specific properties. Something that can be challenging when it comes to reuse of fire safety components. One issue is that the methods used within the standards continuously change over the years. A situation which entails that fire safety components and installations which are tested and approved according to older regulations do not comply with the requirements of today. To be able to reuse fire safety

components and installations, extensive verification may therefore be necessary. In addition to verify compliance to the current legislation, other aspects also need to be considered when discussing reuse, such as a wear and aging of materials.

A study performed by BSL (Brandskyddslaget) [2] aimed to investigate if, and how, fire safety-components and installations can be reused and thereby fulfil the requirements of today. However, the specific goal for the study was to develop a process to apply when evaluating the potential for reuse of these kind of installations and components and thereafter apply and evaluate the process on the component “fire door”.

The component “fire door” was chosen because it was assumed that this component has a rather long lifetime, is possible to dismantle and reuse in a reliable way at the same time as it was judged that there is a potentially large climate and economic saving to be made.

Methodology

When analyzing a fire rated component’s reusability, the component needs to be evaluated in several different steps. These steps can be seen as a process for evaluating and analyzing the components fire rated properties. Such a process was created using an iterative process.

When structuring the method, reuse has been defined as taking a component from an older building and then used within a new building.

The first step to decide if a component can be reused is an initial evaluation with focus on the state of the component. For example, a 100-year-old door which is severely damaged can be hard to reuse while a two-year-old door with no visible damages has a good chance to be reused.

If the component is considered reusable, it’s condition as well as fulfilment of standards need to be charted. This was done by reading building codes and test standards to clarify how the code and test varies through the years. This made it possible to compare components state and type-approval to the current building code. Any differences in quality between the old door compared to a new one need to be analyzed further to secure its fire safety capacity.

Result and conclusion

The result from the study is a possible process to apply when evaluation the potential for reuse of fire safety components and installations as well as a case study on the component “fire

door". The process to use when evaluating possibilities to reuse materials presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. Process for evaluating the reusability of fire safety components.

When testing the process it was applied on the component “fire door”, although the part involving performance-based design was not performed in full. The findings from the study on fire doors can be summarized as follows:

1. Overall assessment: The first examination can be done by a visual control where you consider aspects such as “general impression”, stamps and markings, warp, cracks, leaks etc.
2. Compilation of old and current requirements: A deep dive revealed that both test procedures and specific criteria that must be met have changed over time. It is noted that although different versions of the building regulation refer to the same standards and test methods, the specific procedures and requirements within these standards and test methods might have been changed. This fact makes a direct comparison between new and old products challenging.
3. In depth investigation of the condition: When doing such an investigation the analysis must include both the blade and the frame as well as the possibility to dismantle reassemble these. Further, to do an in-depth investigation of a fire door, the specific item probably must be damaged, which requires several types of the same door to be considered reusing. The dismantling might include glazing beads, sealing strips, composition of the door blade etc.
4. Comparative analysis: The analysis was not performed for a specific door.

5. Performance-based design: Several possible routes for performance-based design were identified as possible regarding the component “fire door”. Simplified fire tests which can be used to verify specific characteristics such as burn-through time and lining materials contribution to fire, calculations showing the components fire resistance, comparative analysis of the buildings overall fire safety when using the reused fire doors, different combinations of the mentioned.

The conclusion from testing the process on fire rated doors is that if the product is not tested with the latest standards, performance-based design must be done to be able to reuse the product. Another conclusion is that every component needs to be evaluated and analyzed since the components condition can vary depending on age, surrounding temperature, endurance etc.

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Scenario thinking in major infrastructure projects

Decision making under uncertainty during accelerating societal change

Henrik Bjelland
Institute for Safety,
Economics and Planning
University of Stavanger
Stavanger, Norway
henrik.bjelland@uis.no

Ove Njå
Institute for Safety,
Economics and Planning
University of Stavanger
Stavanger, Norway
ove.njaa@uis.no

Keywords: *Uncertainty, Scenarios, Infrastructure, Design*

Abstract

Major events and accidents are important knowledge for the development of safety in the society. Within road tunnel safety, for instance, the Mont Blanc tunnel fire in 1999 was monumental in terms of generating political and public awareness to fire safety, which again led to several research projects and change of European regulations [1; 2].

Avoiding reoccurrence of major historical accidents is essential. However, are we focusing too much on the past when we are designing our systems for the future? In this paper we work from the perspective that safety management is about being prepared for future events and we discuss how scenario thinking, or foresight, may expand current perceptions about the world and how our infrastructures work in this world. We argue that there is a need to rethink the balance between knowledge of the past and reflections about the future in decision making under large uncertainties.

Uncertainty and emerging societal trends

Investing in major infrastructure projects is a gamble and could be seen as a game of conviction/persuasion and persistence. For instance, the world's longest and deepest subsea road tunnel, Rogfast, is currently under construction in Norway. The idea about a firm connection across the Bokn fjord in Rogaland was initiated in 1985 [3], which means that close to 50 years have passed when the first car drives through the completed tunnel, probably in 2033. Since 1985, there have been major changes in the Norwegian society and the world. The Rogfast project have also developed according to changes in regulations (e.g., influenced by the Mont Blanc tunnel fire in 1999), political processes, and new needs. However, the original concept of a road tunnel has survived.

Considering the major realization time and societal impact of mega projects, like Rogfast, it is essential that uncertainty about the future is incorporated into the decision support, to allow for critical reflection upon the major assumptions that supports our "gambling activity". Another aspect is the global acceleration of changes related to climate, urbanization, and technology. In times of accelerating changes, the relative importance of reflections about the future will increase, against our understanding of the past, to guide decision

making in major infrastructure projects. However, public planning processes and decision making rely heavily on methods from the field of social economics, favoring forecasting based on data from the past as well as expected values. Possible surprises through major events and societal changes, is effectively diminished through the methods used.

Scenario thinking

Scenario thinking comes in different formats and the term *scenario* is used in various contexts [4]. For this paper, we suggest a two-dimensional classification, using the axes macro-micro and normative-explorative, which is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scenario classification on the axes micro-macro and normative-explorative.

In risk assessments we usually find examples of micro-oriented scenarios. Normative micro-oriented scenarios are the specific events that the society expect to be considered as part of the design process. Normative micro-scenarios are typically founded in previous events and specified through regulations, standards, and norms, but could also exist as a more unspecified understanding within a professional discipline.

Explorative micro-scenarios are specific events which represent surprises to our common thinking about accident loads. We cannot say they are probable in a statistical sense but based on, for instance, comparisons with other sectors and societal trends that increase the likelihood of such events, they might be called plausible. The increased attention to hydrogen and ammonia as energy carriers for vehicles, should for instance lead to a discussion of including specific events including such substances in tunnel design and emergency preparedness plans.

Macro-scenarios are scenarios that says something about the future in a broad sense and within a defined context. For instance, it could be a description of Norwegian mobility patterns under the assumptions that there are major innovations within vehicle autonomy and traffic regulations. Building on emerging trends as critical assumptions, we can establish explorative macro-scenarios, which represent futures that might occur, i.e. plausible futures. Conducting a risk assessment based on different explorative macro-scenarios, would probably lead to identification of several explorative micro-scenarios, which we do not think too much about today.

Normative macro-scenarios are descriptions of futures we want, or not want, to occur. Again, these are not scenarios we believe will occur or consider probable. Rather, they are scenarios that we might work hard to realize or avoid. A discussion about what need to happen to realize the normative macro-scenario, in a broad societal perspective, should inform the development of strategies, surveillance programs and emergency preparedness plans. An example could be to establish a scenario related to the goal of maximum 1.5 °C increase in global temperature. *Backcasting* is a common technique for “working backwards” from the normative macro-scenario to the current situation, to identify critical processes, events, and decisions.

The knowledge content in scenarios

In the autumn 2022 the Norwegian Defence Research Establishment (NDRE) completed a report entitled “Scenarios for unwanted influence in connection with Norwegian elections” [5]. The report was originally commissioned by the Department of Defence, but the Minister of Defence attributed political intentions to some of the scenarios and did not want to publish the report, which raised a public debate about scenarios and scientific freedom. A chronicle written by an associate professor in philosophy of science argued that the report was unscientific, based on the use of scenarios [6]. The debate raises some questions:

- Who are eligible to define normative scenarios, i.e. in a macro-perspective *the desirable futures* or, in a micro-perspective, *reasonable accident loads for the society's critical infrastructures*?
- What distinguish relevant scenarios from irrelevant scenarios as a foundation for decision making under great uncertainty?
- Is it the development and use of scenarios, which is scientific, or is it the study of the use of scenarios for various decision-making purposes?

There is no universal definition of desirable futures. This needs to be recognized in decision making processes involving investments of the society's funds. Desirable scenarios need to reflect the context in which they are created and serve the purpose of the scenario's owner. The decision stakes and variety of stakeholders associated with the scenario(s) must be considered. The higher the stakes and the number of various stakeholders, the more democratic the decision-making process should be, considering desirable futures from different perspectives. During times of accelerating societal change, scenarios represent social artefacts with a potential to be useful or not in terms of expanding the decision makers' original perspective.

The second question is related to the quality of scenario descriptions. Considering that no scenarios are true, are there scenario descriptions that should be taken more seriously than others and why? For instance, could we educate “experts” in scenario development? What is the difference between a useful scenario and a conspiracy theory? Does it matter how the scenarios are developed if they are useful in expanding current thinking? We think that the discussions between safety or risk acceptability, tenability or even resilience characteristics would be an interesting starting point of answering these questions. If there is no plausibility, consistency or relevance included, it is not clear how measures become relevant, thus, logic, modelling and scientific data collection would be necessary. Considering normative macro-scenarios, it does not matter how the scenario description emerge, but the following process of analyzing the path from the scenario to the current situation would reveal issues related to lack of plausibility, consistency, and relevance [7].

Considering the third question, we will not contribute to a discussion of the frame of scientific work in this article but concentrate upon scenarios as expression of design premises.

A critical reflection of the knowledge content of scenarios in different decision situations is needed. To improve the usefulness of scenario thinking we suggest a mapping of classes of decision situations against scenario types, and the development of associated requirements for scenario development and content.

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Efficiency, reliability, testability, sustainability of fire extinguishing and suppression systems.

Necessary considerations in critical applications

Author 1 Torbjørn Laursen

R&D

Fire Eater A/S

Hillerød, Denmark

topper@fire-eater.dk

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Abstract

New technologies such as data centers, BESS, Power-to-X, and various hot production facilities are highly effective, critical to society, and involving high risk (varied probability, but general very severe consequences). When choosing the fire safety system, it is very important to consider more than the lowest common denominator. This presentation will provide examples how to minimize residual risk for societal critical infrastructure.

The new challenges

The past few decades have been unprecedented in terms of technological development. Increased performance. Implementation of complex digitalized solutions. Increased dependency of energy supply. Transition from carbon based energy to “renewable”.

Fire safety systems must adapt to these circumstances, and ideally standards should be able to embrace the new technologies with all their challenges. Technical standards are very important but by virtue of their nature they will always be behind the technological development: the fire safety solutions addressing the new technologies often take years to develop. If, which is often the case, they do not fit into the existing standards and building codes, new standards or standard revisions must be made.

Second challenge of keeping standards up to the technological development, is the fact that the standards often become the lowest common denominator of what the involved industry can agree.

Third challenge is the battle of providing “sustainable solutions”. Sustainable is subject to the definition of the technology provider, and therefore we are bombarded with “green” solutions offering “sustainability”, but at the end of the day are they really? An example is the replacement

products for AFFF’s and Halons. The end-user or system owner has no chance to judge if the statements are really true or just a marketing gimmick based on a fraction of the reality.

This presentation will address the often forgotten elements, that are extremely important when a critical function or asset must be protected, and the fire safety system comply with present standards, but additional measures must be considered

Efficiency

Each system has its advantages and disadvantages. The “Clean Agent Systems” are often viewed as one category, but within this, there are very large differences when it comes to the actual efficiency of the agents. These differences are not identified in the standards, and often misunderstood by highlighting that a system discharging in 10 seconds is much more efficient than discharging in 120 seconds¹, because the implication of the discharge time has nothing to do with the time to extinguish, or the ability to keep the atmosphere survivable or minimize damages.

When it comes to clean agent systems, one of the requirements is to have an enclosure that can contain the gases and maintain the extinguishing concentration. Inert agents are generally superior, but in case of leakages in the enclosure, or when other system parts like doors, windows, or ventilation system fails, then what? The standards operate with “extended discharge”, which is essentially “use more gas to compensate for leakages”. This approach is undefined in the standard^{2,3,4}, and wisely so, because using more gas to compensate for leakage can have serious safety consequences if the leakage during and after discharge is not present.

Fire Eater presents a simple and efficient solution for this challenge.

Reliability & testability

When a system is installed and commissioned, the check-list has been completed, but how sure can you be, that the system actually works in all details? A full-scale test can document the present condition of the system, and can be very useful, or even necessary, when applications falling outside the standard (e.g. extended discharge) shall be verified. But what happens during the life of the system, when it has to work in dynamic circumstances, where human interaction is a factor?

Fire Eater presents some of the critical and vulnerable parts of the system and suggest how they should be addressed, to secure reliability. One of those elements is testability, and documentation of the critical system functions.

Sustainability

To keep the system functional and operational for several decades, most people today realize that real sustainability must be facilitated. In the past decade it was popular to buy a system covered by a warranty against implications of Global Warming. But just a few years after it becomes publicly known that they may have a low GWP, but they are PFAS, and are facing restrictions⁵, as they are suspected to cause serious environmental risk.

All agents containing organic Fluor (F+C) has environmental risk. Only water and atmospheric gases (and some condensed aerosols), are really sustainable.

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The effect of Bjørnis the Fire Bear

Study of the effect of a mascot on fire safety in Norwegian households

Ragni Fjellgaard Mikalsen¹, Janne Siren Fjærestad¹, Nora Fredagsvik², Annette Nergård², Anniken Lie³

¹ RISE Fire Research, Trondheim, Norway, ragni.mikalsen@risefr.no

² The foundation “Stiftelsen Brannbamsen Bjørnis”, Trondheim, Norway

³ Trøndelag fire and rescue service IKS (TBRT), Trondheim, Norway

Keywords:

Prevention, communication, children, elderly, survey

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of Bjørnis the Fire Bear on residential fire safety in Norway. Our survey with 1275 respondents show that Bjørnis prompted the implementation of 5181 fire safety measures, averaging 4.1 per household. Results indicate a correlation between exposure to Bjørnis and increased safety measures. Findings underscore Bjørnis' effectiveness in promoting fire safety awareness, which may be an inspiration for establishing or continuing with similar mascots and programs internationally.

Introduction

The fire and rescue services' mascot named Bjørnis (Figure 1) started as a mascot of a local Norwegian fire service and has since been welcomed by over 100 fire services nationwide. Today, Bjørnis is a national superstar among kids in Norway.

Bjørnis the Fire Bear is utilized for three main purposes: first, to provide comfort for kids involved in fires or other accidents; second, as part of the national fire prevention education for children in kindergartens; and third, to promote national and local fire safety campaigns and to be a positive representative for the fire departments.

Figure 1. Bjørnis is a national superstar in Norway, comforting kids involved in accidents and utilized for fire prevention education. Photo: The foundation “Stiftelsen Brannbamsen Bjørnis”.

Survey

In this study, we document and quantify for the first time (to our knowledge) the effect a fire mascot may have on residential fire safety. The data was collected through a survey conducted by 28 local fire services in all regions of Norway. The respondents were selected among participants present on the open fire station day in September 2023.

Method limitations

In order to obtain a representative sample of the population, the sample must be selected randomly from the entire population. This was considered, but was not within the budget. The respondents mainly represent Norwegian households *with* children (93.6%, or 1193 of 1275 respondents were households with one or more children). Our sample is most likely skewed by expectations, since respondents who have turned up at an open fire station are probably over the average concerned with fire protection. The results can therefore be used for an effect among this group but cannot be generalized to the whole population.

Results

The data set comprises 1275 survey responses, documenting a total of 5181 measures implemented for fire safety because of something the respondents have learned from Bjørnis. This gives an average of 4.1 measures per household among the respondents. The most frequently implemented measures were the least time-consuming and least complex ones: talking about fire safety at home (performed by 18% of respondents) and learning the emergency telephone number (performed by 14% of respondents). In addition, checking the smoke detector was frequent (performed by 14% of respondents) despite being more time-consuming. Checking the smoke detector is the single measure most often emphasized by Bjørnis.

Repetition was also found to help with the overall number of measures implemented; a clear correlation was found between the number of arenas where people have met or seen Bjørnis and the number of measures implemented.

Conclusions

The study concludes that Bjørnis has had a clear and documented positive effect on domestic fire safety in Norwegian households with children. In addition, one in five of the respondents had made fire safety improvements not

only in their own homes but also in households around the child, including at-risk persons.

This study may be used 1) nationally to motivate the continued, systematic work utilizing Bjørnis for preventative fire safety work, and 2) internationally as an inspiration for establishing or continuing with similar mascots and programs.

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Firefighter's exposures

Preliminary study on fire gases from burning 'new' and sustainable building materials

Evalyne Arinaitwe
Div. Fire Safety
Engineering,
Lund University.
Lund, Sweden.
evalyne.arinaitwe@brand.lth.se

Johannes Rex
Ergonomics and
Aerosol Technology,
Lund University.
Lund, Sweden.

Margaret McNamee
Fire Safety
Engineering,
Lund University.
Lund, Sweden.

Joakim Pagels
Ergonomics and
Aerosol Technology,
Lund University.
Lund, Sweden.

Vilhelm Malmberg
Ergonomics and
Aerosol Technology,
Lund University.
Lund, Sweden

Keywords: firefighters' exposure, fire gases, emissions from fire, new building materials, sustainable building materials

Abstract

Firefighters are exposed to harmful and toxic substances during firefighting activities (i.e. training, live firefighting and overhaul) in building fires. This paper studies the impact of 'new' and sustainable materials ('green' buildings) on firefighter's exposures during firefighting interventions. Cross-laminated wood (CLT), recycled wood material (referred to as 'RECOMA' in this paper) and glass fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) were burned in the cone calorimeter and the gasses produced quantified using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Results show that many different fire gases are produced beyond the common gas analysis of oxygen, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide by standard fire testing equipment. The presence of benzene and formaldehyde which are associated with increased risk for cancers in humans, indicates the need for better understanding of fire gases from such new materials in order to continually ensure the proper protection of firefighters.

Introduction

Occupational exposure as Firefighter has been classified as carcinogenic to humans (group 1) by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) [1, 2].

Fire statistics from different cities across the world show that building fires are the main causes of fire deaths and injuries [3]. Today, the building sector is transitioning from 'traditional' building materials (e.g. wood and concrete) to more sustainable materials, the concept of 'green buildings' in a bid to improve its impact on the environment [4]. These 'new' and sustainable materials are generally produced from the recycling and reuse of existing materials in line with the concept of circular economy [5]. These materials pose new challenges to firefighting [6] as well as present new sources of risk to firefighters' health. To address this knowledge gap, our study analyses the fire gases produced from the combustion of three (3) such 'new' materials, the results of which are envisaged to enable deeper understanding of the potential risks to human health associated with combustion of these materials.

Materials and methods

An experimental study was performed on CLT, RECOMA and FRP with the aim to investigate the fire gases produced during the combustion of the materials in the Cone Calorimeter (CC) in the Fire Lab in Lund.

Two conditioned samples (at 23 °C and 50 % RH) of CLT, FRP and RECOMA materials of thicknesses between 10 and 24 mm, were burned at a pre-determined heat flux of 50 kW/m² in the CC in accordance with the fire test standard 5660-1 [7].

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was used to analyze the fire gases produced (Model atmosFIR, Protea). The FTIR was connected (online) to the gas sampling duct of CC to facilitate real-time gas analysis using a heated sampling head. All values presented are the average of duplicate measurements.

Results

Table 1 shows some of the analysed fire gases produced from the burning of the selected materials. More than 15 different gaseous species have been quantified by the FTIR including the common gases (CO and CO₂) analysed by standard fire testing equipment such as the CC. This further shows that gas analysis of fire gases is necessary during fire tests.

Table 1: Preliminary peak concentrations of some of the fire gases produced

Fire gases	CLT	RECOMA	FRP
CO (ppm)	90.5	59.5	352.2
CO ₂ (vol %)	0.8	0.4	0.7
CH ₄ (ppm)	8.9	10.2	15.2
SO ₂ (ppm)	2.7	3.1	2.6
HCl (ppm)	0.7	2.6	267.2
HCN (ppm)	2.1	3.1	19.0
NO ₂ (ppm)	2.9	1.9	3.31
NH ₃ (ppm)	2.4	2.7	2.4
Benzene (ppm)	2.2	1.8	14.6
Formaldehyde (ppm)	10.8	3.8	3.8

Notable was the presence of benzene and formaldehyde which are associated with risk for cancers in humans. Other toxic gases e.g. HCl, SO₂, NO₂ and HCN were also present in addition to the previously mentioned gases analysed by standard fire testing equipment such as the CC. It should be

noted that the FTIR results as presented are preliminary and in particular the organic species will require more study for confirmation.

For all three materials, the peak concentrations for formaldehyde and benzene were higher than both the EU short-term and long-term occupational exposure limits [8], i.e. 0.3/0.6 ppm (LTEL/STEL) for formaldehyde and 1.65/0.6 ppm (LTEL/STEL) for benzene respectively.

Limitations

Some of the limitations encountered during the study that may impact the generalization of our findings are presented in this section. The material

Only two samples for each material were tested. Since the study's primary objective was to quantify fire gases, it was assumed that performing two tests per material would still provide adequate repeatability. Further, specific products were tested and not generic material. A wider variety of material should be tested in the future to extend the validity of the conclusions.

All species were gaseous. It is worth noting that exposure pathways for firefighters include ingestion, absorption (dermal) and respiratory exposure, see figure 1. Ingestion is through contamination of food and drink. Absorption can be through exposure to condensate from the fire or fire gases. Respiratory exposure is mainly through gaseous emissions in fire smoke. This paper only deals with respiratory exposure.

Figure 1. Cancer exposure routes for firefighters (Source: CDC)

Conclusion

Although these were preliminary studies, the results show that there are potential health risks associated with fire gases released from the combustion of 'new' and sustainable building materials, some of which are linked to cancers in humans. In order to protect firefighters from such risks, there is a need to undertake gas analysis studies of the new and sustainable materials to fully understand the composition of the fire gases that are emitted.

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Modifying the ISO 9705 room corner test for smoke toxicity quantification

Large-scale smoke toxicity quantification of Oriented Strand Board (OSB).

Dr Gabrielle Peck
Fire and Hazards Science
University of Central
Lancashire, (UCLan)
Preston, UK
gpeck1@uclan.ac.uk

Keywords: (5 key words)

Smoke toxicity; OSB; ISO 9705; Large-scale testing; equivalence ratio.

Abstract

The ISO 9705 room corner test is a large-scale fire test used to assess the flammability of materials, from ignition to flashover in a small, standardized room. The ISO 9705 test was modified to design an experimental procedure for smoke toxicity assessment of non-homogenous materials. This paper presents the results obtained from testing Oriented Strand Board (OSB) in 3 different ways; using no restriction of ventilation with normal fuel loading (1x SBI no door), using a door to restrict ventilation with normal fuel loading (1x SBI with door) and no restriction of ventilation with double fuel loading (2x SBI). The OSB was mounted (with a 4 mm) air gap to an SBI rig, and placed inside the room on the scale. Gas measurements (CO, CO₂ and O₂) were taken in the doorway of the test room and the exhaust duct, and the equivalence ratio was measured in the door by using a phi-meter. The rig(s) were ignited using 7 kg heptane burners to produce a similar HRR as the burners used for ignition in the SBI test.

Using 3 different test configurations allowed for different experimental set-ups to be assessed to identify what is needed to achieve specific burning conditions in the ISO room corner test. The use of 1x SBI rig with no door meant that the fire had enough ventilation and fuel to burn well-ventilated, showing a measured equivalence ratio of 0.7. The addition of a door to the test room for ventilation restriction did not force the fire to transition to under-ventilated flaming. The maximum equivalence ratio reached was only 0.95.

When using 2x SBI rigs with no door, there was sufficient fuel for the fire to transition to under-ventilated flaming. The equivalence ratio was measured to be 1.5 at its peak, which is representative of under-ventilated conditions. However, the sampling did take place inside of the flame as the fire became so vigorous that the flames poured out of the test room for a significant portion of the test. This means that the equivalence ratio was 1.5 within the flame zone, and is less indicative of the actual fire condition in the room.

In large-scale testing, particularly when using the ISO room, fuel loading and test geometry has more significant impact on the fire condition than restricting the ventilation. While imposing restrictions on the test rooms ventilation did increase the equivalence ratio, it was not sufficient enough to force the transition into under-ventilated flaming.

Introduction

During a typical ISO 9705 room corner test [1], the material is mounted to the room's walls and ceiling, meaning mass loss measurements throughout the test are impossible as the material is not placed directly on the load cell. As these are valuable measurements for calculation of toxic gas yields, the test design was modified. Previous tests measuring the smoke toxicity of simple materials in the ISO 9705 room have been conducted, however these were as pool fires [2].

The Single Burning Item test (SBI) [3] is a recognized intermediate scale test. This test would be easy to describe and reproduce. However, the ventilation duct usually dilutes fire effluent and the lack of a ceiling reduces the severity of a test meaning under-ventilated flaming is rarely achieved.

Therefore, it was decided that 1 to 2 SBI rigs were to be used (placed opposite one another for tests using higher fuel loading when using 2 rigs) and placed inside the ISO room. The use of the SBI rig(s) inside the test room with the presence of a ceiling was hoped to allow for a well-ventilated test to be achieved, and a corresponding under-ventilated test.

Using two SBI tests facing each other inside the ISO room with a liquid fuel ignition source allowed the load cell in the ISO room to be used, have a well-known, standard geometry, and create high enough rates of burning to force under-ventilated flaming. Previous tests using the ISO 9705 room have used a 'door' to restrict the ventilation to the test room to force under-ventilated flaming. These experiments aimed to assess if restriction to ventilation was significant enough to force under-ventilated flaming, or if doubling the fuel loading had more impact on the fire condition of the test.

Methodology

Three stainless steel tubes with an internal diameter of 6 mm were secured near the top of the doorway of the ISO 9705

room. One was used as a sampling line for a phi meter that was specifically designed and created to monitor the equivalence ratio. The two remaining sampling lines went to a specially made portable gas analyzer, designed and created for this work (containing an NDIR, and O₂ electrochemical cells). The three tubes were placed approximately 0.1 m from the ceiling pointing upwards and were approximately 0.3 m across the doorway, shown in Figure 1.

The air velocity in and out of the door was monitored using bi-directional McCaffrey probes (McC) with a differential pressure transducer at the end. The probes were placed in the doorway at set heights, shown in Figure 1. The probes were placed approximately 0.2 m into the doorway for each test alongside a thermocouple tree.

The ISO 9705 test was modified by using 1 to 2 SBI test rigs placed on the load cell of the ISO room. The rig(s) were placed on the load cell in the room to enable mass loss measurements and were ignited using 7 kg heptane placed in burners as in the SBI test. The burners used were calibrated prior to conducting tests. Three tests of differing configurations using OSB were conducted; using no restriction of ventilation with normal fuel loading (1x SBI no door), using a door to restrict ventilation with normal fuel loading (1x SBI with door) and no restriction of ventilation with double fuel loading (2x SBI). The OSB was mounted (with a 4 mm) air gap to an SBI rig, and placed inside the room on the scale. Gas measurements (CO, CO₂ and O₂) were taken in the doorway of the test room and the exhaust duct, and the equivalence ratio was measured in the door by using a phi-meter.

Figure 1. Layout of sampling set up for monitoring the equivalence ratio and gasses in the door during testing (left) and the placement of McCaffrey probes and thermocouple tree for air velocity and temperature measurements (right).

Results and discussion

The heat release, equivalence ratio and CO concentrations were compared between the three tests in the following subsections. The data is shown in Table 1. The use of 1x SBI rig with no door meant that the fire had enough ventilation and fuel to burn well-ventilated. This was evidenced by the equivalence ratio of 0.7. The heat release from the test was relatively high, with a peak heat release of 990 kW being measured. The CO yield obtained were representative of well-ventilated flaming. The measurements taken in the exhaust duct were very dilute. This was the case for most of the gas

measurements taken in the duct when compared to the door measurements.

Table 1: A summary of the data obtained from the ISO room testing.

Test set up	Aimed test condition	Max ϕ	PHRR /kW	Max CO %	
				Door	Duct
1x SBI with no door	Well-ventilated	0.70	990	0.48	0.12*
1x SBI with door	Under-ventilated	0.95	760	0.36	0.09*
2x SBI with no door	Under-ventilated	1.50	4500	5.1	0.9

*Indicates value measured in the exhaust duct

The HRR curves for 1 x SBI where the doorway was fully open and shut off show remarkable similarity, including a similar peak occurring at 640 seconds. This was presumably when both sides of the OSB were burning at the same time. However, the peak HR for the partially blocked doorway is around 660 kW, rather than 990 kW for the open doorway. This demonstrates the effect of partially blocking the door to the ISO room is slowing the rate of burning.

Comparatively, the addition of a door to the test room did not force the fire to transition to under-ventilated flaming. Despite the restriction on the ventilation, the maximum equivalence ratio reached was only 0.95. The peak heat release measured decreased with the addition of the door on the test room.

When using 2x SBI rigs with no door, there was sufficient fuel for the fire to transition to under-ventilated flaming. The equivalence ratio was measured to be 1.5 at its peak, which is representative of under-ventilated conditions. However, the sampling did take place inside of the flame as the fire became so vigorous that the flames poured out of the test room for a significant portion of the test. This means that the equivalence ratio was 1.5 within the flame zone, and is less indicative of the actual fire condition in the room.

Conclusions

In large-scale testing, particularly when using the ISO room, fuel loading and test geometry has more significant impact on the fire condition than restricting the ventilation.

While imposing restrictions on the test rooms ventilation did increase the equivalence ratio, it was not sufficient enough to force the transition into under-ventilated flaming. This is evidenced by the equivalence ratio measured, and the CO concentrations measured.

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Enhancing Fire Dynamics Education: A New Laboratory to Evaluate Models for Enclosure Fires

Nils Johansson

Faculty of Engineering,
Fire Safety Engineering
Lund University
Lund, Sweden

Dan Madsen

Faculty of Engineering, Fire
Safety Engineering
Lund University
Lund, Sweden

Keywords:

Fire lab, fire dynamics, fire engineering, education, corridor fire.

Abstract

This presentation introduces a new laboratory experiment incorporated into a course on fire dynamics at Lund University. The lab is aimed at providing students with practical insights into the behaviour of fires in confined spaces. The laboratory setting comprises a 60-meter-long corridor connected to a room, facilitating the emulation of real-world fire scenarios. The primary objective of this laboratory is to let the students experience a full-scale enclosure fire and evaluate the performance of various fire models by comparing their predictions with laboratory data.

Background

The fire engineering education at Lund University has undergone significant expansion and enhancement during the last years, with the revision of old courses and introduction of new course and subjects. The underlying reason for the expansion is the establishment of a new five-year program in fire safety engineering at the university. Furthermore, a new fire research facility in Revinge close to Lund allows for new and cutting-edge student laboratories.

The new fire safety engineering program aims to meet society's need for engineers engaged in professional activities related to fire protection and accident prevention in both public services and private businesses. The education has a clear focus on managing the consequences of acute accidents, especially fire, explosion, and the release of hazardous substances. This includes having a great knowledge about fire dynamics and smoke spread in enclosed spaces.

Laboratory Setup

The fire research facility in Revinge is owned and managed by the division of fire safety engineering at Lund University. The facility consists of a 60-meter-long corridor constructed from repurposed shipping containers (see figure 1), which have an interior that is partly lined with lightweight concrete.

Figure 1. The 60 m long corridor with a connected room constructed with shipping containers.

The facility is equipped with thermocouples and plate thermometers that are positioned to monitor and record temperature at various points during tests. Additionally, to accurately measure the mass loss rate the fire source is placed atop a load cell, providing data regarding the fuel consumption over time. Measurements of smoke density and gas flow are also available in the corridor. This comprehensive instrumentation setup ensures careful data collection.

In the development of a new laboratory in fire dynamics, an important aspect was to create relevant scenarios (i.e., scenarios that could serve as a basis for analytical design or analysis using different models).

In contrast to the previous laboratory exercise in the fire dynamics course conducted in a three-room apartment, this newly introduced laboratory offers a more targeted and relevant approach for aspiring fire safety engineers. By focusing on scenarios that mirror potential real-world situations, the new lab aligns closely with the principles of performance-based fire engineering.

Two scenarios are studied in the laboratory: the first, a room fire scenario where smoke propagates into the corridor, and second, a corridor fire scenario leading to smoke infiltration into the room (see figure 2). Through hands-on experimentation, students gain valuable experience in observing and analysing the complexities of fire dynamics, enhancing their understanding of fire behaviour and the efficacy of different fire models in predicting real-world outcomes. This laboratory exercise fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills essential for future courses in fire safety engineering and related areas.

Scenario 2 - Korridorbrand

Figure 2. One of the two studied scenarios in the laboratory.

Conclusion

Even though the scenarios studied are simplified and conducted in a laboratory environment the student's gain much deeper insight into the complexity of the fire phenomena and the simplifications that fire modelling involves. As an example, exterior conditions like wind speed and wind direction can have a large influence on the smoke spread, and such environmental conditions are hard to model.

By transitioning to this updated laboratory setup, students are better equipped to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios, preparing them for the complexities of modern fire safety engineering practices. This shift underscores the commitment to providing students with hands-on experiences that directly translate to their future roles as fire engineers.

One-dimensional decoupled thermal radiation calculation with different spectral models

Soroush Rashidzadeh
School of Engineering,
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland
soroush.rashidzadeh@aalto.fi

Simo Hostikka
School of Engineering,
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland
simo.hostikka@aalto.fi

Keywords: Thermal radiation, Spectral models, FDS

Abstract

The study compares two spectral radiation models against the accurate spectral calculation method, also known as the Line-By-Line (LBL) method. One-dimensional decoupled radiation calculations are performed using a gray model (RadCal) and the RC-FSK model. The species concentration of H₂O and CO₂ and temperature are sampled from a heptane pool fire CFD simulation conducted by the FDS code.

Introduction

Thermal Radiation plays a significant role in fire simulations [1,2]. Radiation transfer equation, RTE, is a multi-dimensional equation that requires to be solved for three spatial and two angular directions. Moreover, the absorption coefficient, κ , is inherently dependent on wavenumber which make accurate radiation calculations challenging.

In this study the commonly employed gray approach is compared with non-gray radiation model (RC-FSK) [3,4] and the performance of both models are assessed against Line-By-Line Benchmark. Due to the computation limitations, decoupled radiation calculations are conducted with realistic temperature and species concentration obtained from a heptane pool fire simulation carried out by FDS [5].

Pool Fire Simulation and Sampling

To avoid prescribing simplistic/ unrealistic distributions for temperature and species concentration, a CFD model of a heptane pool fire is carried out with FDS code. The current simulation involves a rectangular heptane pool with dimensions of 0.5 m × 0.5 m. The necessary properties are sampled from a series of devices implemented horizontally over the pool.

Figure.1 represents the schematic of the described simulation. The extended domain from one side of the pool allows to investigate thermal radiation in colder regions away from the vicinity of the pool fire.

Figure.2 illustrates sampled concentration species and temperature from the CFD simulation. These properties serve

as an input for running a 1-D finite volume code to solve RTE equation with different spectral models and LBL.

Figure 1. Schematic of pool fire simulation in FDS and the position of sampled data

Figure 2. Sampled temperature and concentration of H₂O and CO₂ over the pool fire at height of 0.5 m

Radiation Transfer Equation, RTE

The spectral form of RTE for non-scattering media can be written as:

$$\frac{dI_\eta}{ds} = \kappa_\eta(I_{b\eta} - I_\eta)$$

Where *I*, *I_b*, *κ* and *η* are radiation Intensity, blackbody intensity, absorption coefficient and wave number respectively. In the case of gray approach, FDS utilizes RadCal to obtain an effective absorption coefficient therefore a single value can represent the whole spectrum. Consequently, only one RTE is solved within the domain of calculation.

In contrast, the non-gray approach, as implied by its name, allows to compute the spectrally integrated intensities which mean that the complex distribution of absorption coefficient over the spectrum is reduced to a limited number of absorption coefficients with their corresponding weights (in current study there are four values for *κ*). The form of RTE does not change but rather it's solved four times then integrated to obtain the intensity field.

Line-By-Line calculation of RTE equation is carried out as a benchmark. This method accounts for all the spectral lines of absorption coefficient and solves RTE up to a million times in the domain.

Result and Discussion

The radiative heat source along the sampling line is depicted in Figure.3

Figure 3. Radiative heat source predicted by gray, RC-FSK and LBL methods.

In order to quantify the bias in each model, a relative error is defined based on maximum value of local radiative heat source. Table.1 illustrates the max and mean values of relative error. Even though the trend is captured by both models, deviation of gray model predictions from benchmark are more significant compared to its non-gray counterpart. Specially at high temperature regions.

Table 1. Mean and Max relative error for radiative heat source

Spectral method	$-\nabla \cdot q_{max}$ (Kw/m ³)	$-\nabla \cdot q_{mean}$ (Kw/m ³)	δ_{max} (%)	δ_{mean} (%)
Gray (RadCal)	-334.4	-45.9	95.6	16.6
RC-FSK	-195.5	-21.1	15.9	2.53
LBL	-178.4	-19.2	-	-

Computation cost and other considerations

Even though in this analysis the RC-FSK yields very similar results to LBL benchmark calculations, there are some important issues that should be taken into consideration. Primarily, as mentioned in previous sections, for RC-FSK the RTE is solved four times whereas in gray method it's solved once. In contrast, LBL benchmark entail about a million RTE calculations. It's not accurate to suggest that RC-FSK is only four times more computationally intensive than gray method, since there are more calculations prior to simulation in order to obtain the desired absorption coefficients. In scenarios involving multi species mixture these processes can incur significant computational cost.

Another concern arises from the performance evaluation of the gray method in this study, which provides subpar results. This however is not reflective of its performance in multi-dimensional CFD cases where a coupled radiation is solved, and thermal radiation is only a fraction of total heat release.

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Visualization of risks by the use of extended reality

Jonatan Gehandler, Sixten Dahlbom & Petter Wannerberg

RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

Borås & Västerås, Sweden

jonatan.gehandler@ri.se

Keywords: *extended reality, virtual reality, risk analysis, hydrogen, bunkering*

Abstract

Cross-border hydrogen valley around the Baltic Sea (BalticSeaH2) is an EU Horizon research project that aims to speed up the clean energy transition, and to provide energy security in the Baltic region. It is a five-year project that was initiated during 2023. In this project, RISE will develop an XR (extended reality) demonstration of a hydrogen bunkering infrastructure for a Swedish upcoming hydrogen ferry. RISE will perform a quantitative risk analysis (QRA) using a digital blueprint of the bunkering site, package learnings into an XR-demonstrator and provide training events and safety/regulatory analysis in the same digital environment. The aim of this abstract centres around the question how QRA and XR can be fruitfully combined.

XR

XR is an umbrella term and covers a spectrum of immersive media from virtual reality (VR) and mixed reality (MR) to augmented reality (AR). The technology is based on game engines which means that the resulting 3D representation of the virtual space can be shown through wearable devices (e.g., glasses) but also be shown on any screen where the visualization is needed.

According to Cavalcanti et al. [1], a VR game environment is full of stimuli which makes it an excellent tool for learning and skill development. Games are flexible and can be consumed in a wide range of locations (e.g., home, school), and they present the opportunity to learn by experimenting and exploring [1]. For instance, Sharma [2] uses VR to improve emergency response training and decision making for rarely occurring scenarios such as shootings or evacuation using both computer-controlled agents and user-controlled agents. VR is also used to test and design way finding systems for evacuation [3], and to communicate risks, for instance to educate students about natural hazards [4]. The focus of this abstract is on combining XR and risk analysis.

Risk analysis

Risk analysis is often carried out in several steps to identify the main risks as early as possible. The further the project goes, the more is known and the more detailed the risk analysis can be. For example, initially it may only be known that a desired operation is hydrogen bunkering. At that relatively undefined point, a risk of explosion can be pointed out. Later, when more is known (e.g., exact volumes, pressures, piping, dimensions, flows, sensors, protection), it is possible to arrive at the likelihood of a release, an estimated size of the release, and a likelihood of ignition. This can indicate whether the risk is acceptable, or not. An initial idea is that XR can have the following functions (where the first two relate to risk analysis):

1. To give participants in the risk analysis the same starting point. You can illustrate a bunkering process (based on the conditions and knowledge that exist at the time).

2. Illustrate risks identified in a risk analysis.
3. Communicate risks between team members and propose design changes for further design iterations.
4. Package learnings and educate for safe operation.

Integrating risk analysis with XR and future work

The 3D environment can import existing laser scans, map data, CAD data, and allow the user to express their thoughts using simpler 3D objects and annotation tools. The resulting 3D environment can then be used to analyze, collaborate, and present different scenarios. For risk assessment, a completely virtual environment (VR) allows the risk assessor to step into the 3D representation of the proposed harbor and bunkering site and use hand controllers to point out detected risks or markup areas of interest for later presentation, be it in XR, via digital conference tools or similar.

A central question is how much information the end user would need in the 3D map to be able to determine or learn from risks. For example, if the map shows a bunkering station (including pipes, a tank, etc.) at a position, that might be enough to determine the risk of an explosion. However, to make any detailed assessment of leakage risks, pipe dimensions, CAD drawings, protection, standard operation procedures, etc. are needed. What the XR developers initially need is to know the user needs and what questions they aim to answer in the virtual environment. For instance, do users want to see pipes? If so, which ones, and at what detail? Do they want to see buildings in the area? If so, at what radius? Do they want to see sea levels? And is there a need to show data over time, such as sea level rise, or which pipes are pressurized at a given time?

This could for instance be a list with all the questions the users want to ask, even if the information is limited initially. Then comes the next step. For example, who design the tank storage and the piping? Do we have a CAD team that will draw the CAD that can be utilized? What is known about different risk exposed groups such as passengers, staff, tourists, and locals, and which of these groups are included in the study (e.g., where they will be, and if there are restricted areas).

The better the basis (which XR can assist with), the better the risk analysis will be. Risk analysis and the design or decision basis is improved iteratively:

1. When an idea exists of what and how to do something (in this case, bunker a passenger ferry with a high flow of hydrogen), a HAZID, i.e., an initial hazard identification workshop, can be carried out. Typically, the risk of explosion, and its causes (e.g., leakage, human error, collision) may be identified.
2. The XR developer takes the results from the first risk analysis into the XR environment. Such a solution should include the intended location, dimensions of equipment, protective measure etc.

3. The risk analysis is updated, especially with planned protections. The 3D environment is used as the reference point.
4. The XR environment is updated with more detail (if definitive obstacles have not been found), flow charts, dimensions, preferably also preliminary instructions, protocols, etc. are included.
5. A more detailed risk analysis is carried out where each process section and possible errors are studied in detail (e.g., what can cause too high pressure in a certain pipeline), one tries to determine probability and consequence quantitatively or semi-quantitatively (preferably also done, at least qualitatively, in 1. and 3.) to determine whether the intended protections are sufficient. For example, in the process industry, CAD (and 3D scanning) may be available to assist at this stage, e.g., to look at health and safety issues (location of sockets, escape routes, etc.).

The work sequence above is iterative and carries on until the QRA and XR is ready, i.e., fulfills the user needs in terms of decision-making, risk illustration, risk communication, and any safety training (e.g., for bunker operators).

Traditionally risk analysis goes hand in hand with any design work. Using XR will take this one step further. The iterations that will be provided by the XR developers depend on how detailed the input material is (e.g., tools needed inside VR and the 3D data available for the environment). The result of a risk analysis is also dependent on the experts who are involved during the risk analysis. Finally, we think that this combination can be fruitful, not least for high-consequence-low-probability risks, but we would be happy to receive any reflections or input to take our future work even further.

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Measurable sustainability indicators for the fire safety community

Francine Amon

Fire and Safety Department

RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

Borås, Sweden

francine.amon@ri.se

Keywords: *Measurable sustainability indicators, fire safety, social impacts, environmental impacts, economic impacts*

Abstract

This pre-study aimed to determine whether developing measurable sustainability indicators (MSI) to assess the sustainability of projects, ideas, and decisions related to fire safety would be useful for fire safety engineers, researchers, municipalities, authorities, policymakers, first responders and other stakeholders. A review of the literature, online sources, project reports and numerous interactions with representatives of several target groups within the fire safety community was conducted to assess their sustainability needs. The results show that the target groups included in this project had some overlapping and some unique sustainability needs. Fire service product suppliers are currently content to self-declare their sustainability status. Fire and rescue services would like MSI to help them make tactical and strategic decisions while responding to fires. They are also interested in MSI to help them convey their sustainability value to the communities they serve. Fire safety engineers would like MSI to support their suggestions for improvements in construction design. Researchers and educators will contribute to the development of MSI that serve the needs of the other target groups. Authorities could use MSI to evaluate progress toward improved sustainability in their jurisdictions and transfer data to other levels of government.

Introduction

Activities, services, products, energy use, and other aspects of life are increasingly being appraised in terms of sustainability, at least partially due to the need to make progress toward achieving the goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development [1] or other sustainability goals. This is a very positive trend in the sense that it forces people to think about the sustainability consequences of their projects, ideas and decisions, but how can these appraisals be done in a meaningful way? How deep or broad should an appraisal be? Does sustainability mean the same thing to everyone? Would measurable sustainability indicators (MSI) help? Is it feasible to create useful, generally accepted MSI that can be used to monitor and compare the sustainability of projects, ideas and decisions? These questions were explored in this pre-study for selected target groups within the fire safety community.

Without MSI it is very difficult to evaluate sustainability in an objective way. A common phrase is “*if you don’t measure it, you can’t manage it*” [2]. On the surface, this

phrase lends itself well to the goals of this work; however, the full statement is “*What gets measured gets managed — even when it’s pointless to measure and manage it, and even if it harms the purpose of the organization to do so*” [3, 4]. This latter statement puts this notion of creating MSI into a more balanced perspective, in the sense that some areas of fire safety might not need MSI while other areas could derive varying amounts of benefit from them.

This pre-study aimed to determine whether developing MSI to assess the sustainability of projects, ideas, and decisions related to fire safety would be useful for fire safety engineers, researchers, municipalities, authorities, policymakers, first responders and other stakeholders. If so, what are the starting points and endpoints of the journey toward creating them? How different are the needs of the target groups? To answer these questions, the sustainability landscape was investigated for a selection of target groups.

Methodology

Much of the information was collected from the project reference group, which represented several target groups, although there was some overlap among and between the target groups. Information was provided by one fire service product supplier, six fire researchers and three standards developers, five fire safety engineers from companies of different sizes, two authority staff members, and one representative of the fire service. The information that these people provided was based on their experiences and opinions, which may not be representative of other members of their target group(s). Input was also collected from the literature, online sources, and reports.

Conclusions

This pre-study investigated the sustainability landscape for fire safety engineers, researchers, municipalities, authorities, policymakers, first responders and other stakeholders. The following conclusions are based on the results of interviews, workshops, literature, online sources and project reports. This work represents the beginning of the process and, hopefully, the results will be useful for continued research in the future.

All the target groups have implemented some form of sustainability as it applies to their standard business operations, e.g., energy efficiency, traveling, consumption, personnel equality and well-being, etc.

Fire service product suppliers

Aside from adapting business operations to be more sustainable, this target group is primarily focused on creating a unique presence among the competition by having a sustainability profile or certification. It is anticipated that customers will eventually require their vendors to have such a profile and therefore it has high marketing value. Related to this, including sustainability in addition to monetary cost in procurement processes could have a large positive impact and therefore should be included in organisation sustainability plans.

For now, a sustainability profile is seen as enough. MSI are not considered to be needed and might even be detrimental to the overall process of improving sustainability, although they could be used as a marketing tool at some point in the future.

Fire and Rescue Services

MSI are needed that can help the public, other municipal organisations and policy makers understand the social and environmental value of the fire and rescue services. MSI could be monitored over time to improve operations and convey those improvements to stakeholders.

MSI that quantify the impacts of firefighting tactics, e.g., fire water run-off and smoke, would help for making tactical decisions.

Fire Safety Engineers

Currently, fire safety engineers don't have much influence in the construction design process in Sweden, so they need as much support as possible to convey their ideas and suggestions for changes.

MSI would help fire safety engineers communicate the need for, and balance between, sustainable and fire safe buildings to designers and other stakeholders in construction projects.

Fire Researchers and Educators

Researchers and educators provide information to other stakeholders that can help them improve their appreciation for sustainability and fire safety and supports their efforts to make innovative changes in their ways of doing business. Researchers can develop MSI and a system for transferring information between various levels of organisations.

MSI that could be used for decision making and monitoring of progress would help resource planning efforts and assist in communication with funding sources and the public.

Authorities

The regional and/or national authorities are able to provide the necessary connections and support if MSI data are required to be collected from lower levels, e.g., municipalities, companies, fire and rescue services, etc. and reported to higher levels of government, e.g., national, European, global levels. It is unknown at this time whether this need will be realised or when it might come to pass. It is also unknown if the situation has been anticipated or, if so, whether work has begun on creating the infrastructure needed to make this process work.

Future work

This project was a pre-study, inferring that the work is intended to continue. There are several directions that will be investigated as opportunities arise:

- Information about the MSI needs of a broader range of target groups will be collected.
- A deeper understanding of the MSI needs of a single target group will be acquired.
- The links between the levels of government concerning reporting and monitoring of sustainability status will be explored further.

Acknowledgements

This pre-study was funded by Brandforsk. Their support and input during the project is greatly appreciated. Some members of the reference group went well beyond the call of duty in providing information and guidance to support this work; they set a high standard of excellence for future reference groups.

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Integrated Biomass Estimation and Modelling using Machine learning and Remote sensing for Wildfire Risk Prediction

Abdul Hanan

Department of Computer Science, Electrical Engineering and Mathematical Sciences, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen, Norway
ahan@hvl.no

Reza Arghandeh

Department of Computer Science, Electrical Engineering and Mathematical Sciences, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen, Norway

Nieves Fernandez-Anez

Department of Safety, Chemistry and Biomedical Laboratory Sciences, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen, Norway

Keywords:

Biomass, Machine Learning, Forestry, Wildfire Prediction, Remote Sensing

Abstract

In the contemporary context of escalating climate change and the increasing incidence of wildfires, the accurate estimation of forest biomass assumes paramount importance for understanding and quantifying Earth's ecosystems. This research endeavors to advance strategies for precise biomass calculation and modeling, with a specific emphasis on developing a highly accurate fire risk map. The integration of biomass estimation and modeling into a broader digital model of the Earth on a global scale represents a significant contribution to environmental science, leveraging innovative techniques that integrate machine learning and remote sensing technologies.

The research unfolds in two primary phases. Firstly, the biomass estimation and calculation phase entail the utilization of advanced LiDAR and Tree Species maps to measure tree height, estimate diameter at breast height (DBH), and accurately calculate biomass. This foundational phase lays the groundwork for subsequent modeling efforts. In the modeling phase, the Multi-Modal Deep Learning Biomass Estimation (MDL-BIO) model emerges as a pivotal tool, employing a multi-modal convolutional neural network to predict biomass as shown in fig 1 using a diverse array of data inputs, including Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), optical imagery, and the Tree Species map [1].

Analytically Biomass Calculation

To construct a comprehensive digital model of Earth, our research leverages state-of-the-art technologies, particularly high-resolution LiDAR, which enables precise mapping of

forest terrain. Through meticulous determination of tree heights and positions, we establish a robust foundation for accurate biomass calculations. This process involves integrating LiDAR data to capture detailed three-dimensional representations of forest structures. Our approach incorporates a comprehensive Tree Species map, which is derived from an enhanced version of the Norwegian forest inventory map with a remarkable 0.5m resolution. This integration significantly enhances the precision of biomass estimation by providing detailed information on the distribution and density of significant tree species across the landscape.

In our analytical methodology, we utilize allometric equations [2] to estimate biomass based on key parameters such as tree height, diameter, and species. These equations are derived from empirical relationships observed between tree dimensions and biomass, facilitating precise estimation of biomass values across diverse forest ecosystems. The resulting biomass estimates serve as labeled data for training our predictive models, allowing us to develop algorithms capable of accurately predicting biomass distribution.

Modelling of MDL-BIO

That machine learning aspect will take tree species data, SAR, and optical data as input and will use labeled data from the analytical part as ground truth to build a machine learning model capable of accurately predicting biomass. By using state-of-the-art MDL-BIO, the model will predict the biomass of the given area. Furthermore, the project synergizes with initiatives like FireRiskMap, making substantial contributions to the monitoring of vast swathes of the Earth's surface. The emphasis on predicting and understanding the spread of wildfires aligns with overarching goals of environmental preservation and risk mitigation.

In conclusion, this research presents a holistic and meticulous approach to precise biomass estimation and modeling, with far-reaching implications for the broader context of developing a highly accurate digital model of the Earth. By seamlessly integrating machine learning and remote sensing technologies, the project not only advances scientific knowledge but also holds practical ramifications for fire safety and wildfire spread prediction, offering invaluable insights for environmental management and risk mitigation strategies. Looking ahead, the research aims to broaden its scope by incorporating additional dimensions such as vegetation moisture and drought indices to enhance the estimation of vegetation health alongside biomass. This expanded scope promises to deepen our understanding of ecosystem dynamics and contribute to more effective wildfire risk prediction and mitigation efforts, further underscoring the relevance and significance of the research endeavor.

Figure 1. The Analytical Biomass Estimation and machine learning biomass prediction Pipeline.

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Fatal fires in Norway from 2015-2020

Characteristics of fatal fires in Norway

Ellen Synnøve Skilbred
RISE Fire Research
Trondheim, Norway
ellen.synnove.skilbred@risefr.no

Edvard Aamodt
RISE Fire Research
Trondheim, Norway

Anne Steen-Hansen
RISE Fire Research
Trondheim, Norway

Keywords:

Fatal fires, residential fires, fire statistics, safety

Abstract

The number of fatal fires in Norway has been decreasing over the last years, but still around 40 people die in fires in Norway every year.

In this study, statistics from The Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (DSB), police reports and medical journals are collected and analyzed to find the characteristics of the fatal fires that occurred in Norway in 2015-2020, and bring to light what can be done to prevent more fatal fires from happening. The study builds upon a previous study on fatal fires in Norway from 2005-2014 [1].

Sampling

206 fatal fires were found in the DSB fire statistics from 2015-2020, and police reports were received for 197 of them. Most of the fires occurred in buildings and the fires that did not occur in a building were not included in the analysis. Some of the police reports concluded that the person was murdered or dead before the fire, and these reports were also excluded. Suicides were not excluded. The number of fires in the statistical analysis was 152, where in total 163 people died.

Are rural places more at risk?

Many Norwegians live in houses with few and distant neighbors, in areas with little traffic. In such areas, it may take longer before a building on fire is noticed by someone passing by who can help with evacuation and call for help. To investigate this factor, the area near the buildings were considered using photos in the police reports or google maps and categorized as rural or urban. The buildings in urban areas were split in two categories according to whether they were in a city, which in Norway is generally defined as urban areas with more than 5000 inhabitants, or not. The statistics in Figure 1 show that most fatal fires occurred in urban areas with more than 5000 inhabitants. In 2023, 83 % of Norway's population lived in urban areas according to Statistics Norway [2]. Although the definition is somewhat different in the two statistics, there seems to be only a slight overrepresentation of fatal fires in rural areas, with 17 % of the population living in rural areas and 23 % of fatal fires occurred in rural areas.

Figure 1. Distribution of fatal fires in urban and rural areas in Norway, for fatal fires in buildings in 2015-2020.

Where did the fatal fires start?

An overview of the number of fatal fires in different types of buildings is given in Table 1. 46 % of the fatal fires happened in single detached dwellings, while 22% happened in apartment buildings and 22% in single attached dwellings or terraced houses. According to Statistics Norway [3], 48 % of Norwegian dwellings were single detached dwellings, 25 % were apartment buildings, and 21 % were terraced house or single attached dwellings, in 2022. It can therefore not be concluded that fatal fires in 2015-2020 were significantly over- or underrepresented in the most common types of dwellings in Norway.

Table 1. Overview of the distribution on types of buildings for the 152 fatal fires analyzed.

Type of building	Number and percentage of fatal fires
Single detached dwellings	70 (46 %)
Apartment buildings	34 (22 %)
Single attached dwellings	25 (16 %)
Terraced houses	9 (5.9 %)
In institution, care home or sheltered accommodation	7 (4.6 %)
Other	7 (4.6 %)

An overview of what rooms the fatal fires started in is given in Figure 2. For 16 % of the fires, the room of the fire origin is not known, but regardless of this uncertainty, the most common origin for fatal fires was the living room, where 39 %

of the fatal fires started. 17 % of the fires started in the kitchen, while bedrooms, hallways, bathrooms, and basements were the origin for 4-6 % of the fires each.

Figure 2. Distribution of rooms where fatal fires in buildings in Norway in 2015-2020 started. N = 152.

Figure 3 shows on what floor the fires started. Most of the fires started on the ground floor. In Norwegian houses, it is very common to have kitchen and living room on the ground floor and bedrooms in higher floors. Since most of the fires started in the living room and kitchen, this may be the reason why most of the fatal fires started on the ground floor. Another possible explanation is that a fire on the ground floor can make evacuation more difficult for people on higher floors, whereas when people are on the ground floor and a fire occurs on a floor above them, the evacuation routes are less likely to be affected.

Figure 3. Number of fatal fires in Norway starting in the basement, ground floor, first floor and higher floors, and number of fatal fires in buildings where it is not known on what floor the fire started.

How did the fires start?

The causes of the fatal fires are shown in Figure 4. 29 % of the fires have unknown causes. For these cases, it is usually hard to exclude open flame and electrical causes due to too large damages. For the cases where the cause of fire is known, open flame is the most common cause. 40 % of the fires were in this category, which includes candles, open fireplaces, and smoking materials. 20 % of the fatal fires were related to smoking. Fires in this category can be ignited directly by a cigarette, cigar or other smoked tobacco products, embers in an ashtray, or unintended ignition of materials when lighting a tobacco product. These fires usually start close to the smoker’s body and can therefore cause great damage to the person even if the fire is small. 13 % of the fires are in the category incorrect use, which includes for example fires starting in textiles placed on top of an oven and unattended, overheated food on a stove top. 12 % of the fires have electrical causes, 5 % were arson, and 1% had other causes.

Figure 4. Causes of fatal fires in Norway in 2015-2020. N = 152.

Personal factors

Several studies of fatal fires have found that men are somewhat overrepresented [1,4,5]. Our analysis found that men were still overrepresented in the fatal fire statistics. 58 % of the deceased were men, 42 % women.

Being under the influence of alcohol or drugs can decrease a person’s ability to detect and extinguish a fire, call for help and evacuate. 31.5 % of the deceased had an alcohol content in their blood which was likely to have affected the fatal outcome. 21 % were under the influence of drugs or strong medications in a dose which was likely to contribute to the fatal outcome. Some of the victims were under the influence of both drugs and alcohol.

The median age of the deceased was 63 which is four years higher than the median age found for fatal fires in Norway in 2005-2014 [1].

The previous study of fatal fires in Norway found that being alone at the time the fire started was a risk factor [1]. In the current study, 124 of the people who died in fires were alone at the start of the fire. This constitutes 76 % of the fatalities and 82 % of the fatal fires. As people who live alone are likely to be alone more often than people who live with others, it is important to target people who live alone in fire preventive work, especially if they also have risk factors that make detection of fire and evacuation challenging.

Acknowledgements

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Estimating egress model parameters for care home occupants from health data

Kristian Kyllönen

Department of Civil
Engineering
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland

Simo Hostikka

Department of Civil Engineering
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland
simo.hostikka@aalto.fi

Jouni Koivuniemi

School of Engineering
Science
LUT University
Lappeenranta, Finland

Minna Pakarinen

Wellbeing services county of
South Karelia
Lemi, Finland

Keywords:

Evacuation model, egress model, health data, Resident Assessment Instrument, experiment

Abstract

This study investigates the fire safety challenges and egress capabilities of elderly individuals in assisted living facilities, employing a novel approach by utilizing Resident Assessment Instrument (RAI) data to model their egress performance. Through comprehensive measurements and statistical analysis, the research identifies key factors influencing egress capabilities and proposes a classification system for assessing residents' ability to respond to fire emergencies.

The findings, despite a small dataset, emphasize the need for specific fire safety measures and the vital role of nursing staff in ensuring the safety of elderly residents. This research paves the way for further studies, calling for larger datasets and greater insight into factors influencing elderly egress.

Background

In recent years, the demographic shift in Finland towards an aging population has been accompanied by a significant increase in the number of elderly individuals unable to live independently [1]. Consequently, various forms of assisted living facilities have emerged to meet this growing need [2].

However, this shift highlights fire safety concerns for elderly residents with physical and cognitive challenges. This study aims to enhance safety in assisted living facilities by modeling elderly egress performance and devising a methodology to derive model parameters from health data, ensuring vulnerable individuals' protection.

The research utilizes data from the Resident Assessment Instrument (RAI), addressing the lack of datasets on the varied capabilities of care facility residents. The RAI, maintained by the international network interRAI, offers up-to-date data for assessing needs and planning services for the elderly. Assessments are updated for significant condition changes or at least biannually to ensure the care plan meets the current needs of the individual. [3]

Methodology

The methodology of this study is anchored in the evacuation timeline, specifically focusing on pre-evacuation and travel. The designed measurements of egress performance are based

on an assumption that they represent actions performed during evacuation process. The method for the timed measurements adhered to a strictly observational approach, with the underlying hypothesis that such non-interventionist observation of daily living activities could adequately capture the physical and cognitive capabilities of elderly individuals.

Measurements were conducted in two selected 24/7 assisted living facilities in South-Eastern Finland (research permit EKHVA/3992/13.01.06/2023). They included travel speed, reaction time to get attention, mobility (time to rise from a chair or a bed), time for getting dressed (footwear and clothes), and the overall time required to exit from personal room. 25 elderly residents participated as test subjects and granted permission for their RAI data to be used in the study.

Interviews with residents and nursing staff complemented the measurements by providing qualitative data on egress capabilities. A specific objective of the interviews was the evaluation of cognitive capabilities that are needed for becoming aware, comprehending, and making decisions in a possible evacuation situation. Residents were interviewed to assess their awareness of fire alarms, anticipated reactions, and confidence in finding an evacuation route from their personal rooms. Nursing staff assessed each resident's ability to locate their evacuation route from their personal rooms, as well as their physical abilities, particularly those necessary for independent evacuation.

The facilities involved in this study used RAI-LTC (RAI-MDS 2.0) instrument that consists of 531 variables. Most of these variables are either categorical or discrete in nature, providing a comprehensive overview of each resident's health and capabilities. [4] The strategy initially involved studying the relationship between the measurements and RAI data without any predefined limits on used RAI variables. Later, a subset of RAI variable was selected based on expert knowledge.

Statistical analysis was used for correlation between observed and RAI variables. A linear regression model was employed for predicting travel speed and time to exit the personal room. For the classification of residents, a logistic regression was used.

Results from observations

A total of 349 timed measurements were collected. Due to the nature of observational approach, measurements may

encompass intermediate actions such as rising from bed during the time of room evacuation. This inclusion reflects a realistic situation, though it complicates the extraction of data for specific actions. Additionally, measurements account for scenarios where the resident received partial or full assistance, and possible use of various walking aids or wheelchair. Results from the measurements, where the resident was not fully assisted, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Timed measurements with number of measured residents (n) and measurements (m), mean, standard deviation, and min and max values for each measurement type, excluding fully assisted travel speeds.

Type	n	m	μ	σ	min	max
Travel speed (m/s)	19	106	0.43	0.16	0.05	0.94
Room exit (s)	23	47	105	89.7	9.98	365
Rise from chair (s)	23	62	18.3	32.6	1.46	164
Rise from bed (s)	22	28	80.6	53.8	17.8	245
Dressing, footwear (s)	19	26	19.9	16.5	6.47	75.3
Dressing, clothes (s)	13	26	57.9	71.1	5.34	382
Reaction time (s)	24	29	1.88	0.75	1.00	3.68

Preliminary analysis of the interviews indicated that most residents cannot evacuate independently and necessitate different types of assistance during evacuation. Reflecting these diverse needs, residents were classified into five classes based on interview data. Class 5 residents are fully independent in evacuation scenarios, whereas class 1 individuals require complete assistance. Classes 2 and 3 need physical support, while classes 2 and 4 require help in reacting to evacuation need and/or identifying egress routes.

Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted applying thresholds of absolute correlation >0.4 and p-value <0.05. We identified 155 RAI variables from the full dataset correlating with at least one timed measurement, and 41 from the reduced set.

The time to exit personal room and travel speed were focused on, guided by their straightforward integration into the evacuation timeline as a pre-evacuation time and the speed of movement between the personal room and exit. A linear regression analysis was conducted for both measurement types for predicting egress performance.

For travel speed, a linear model with RAI variables G1dA (Walk in corridor – Self-performance) and G5b (Wheeled self) was developed, yielding an R² value of 0.67 and F-statistic of 20.47 with 2 and 20 degrees of freedom and p<0.01. For time to exit room, a linear model with RAI variable ADL-28 was developed, yielding an R² value of 0.57 and F-statistic of 27.79 with 1 and 21 degrees of freedom and p<0.01. The independent variables for both models were statistically significant.

For resident classification, logistic regression models were employed. In numerous instances, logistic regression models failed to converge due to insufficient data across various combinations of RAI variables. Consequently, this paucity of data also precluded the rejection of the null hypothesis for independent variables within the tested logistic models. Finally, a multinomial logistic model with RAI variables CPS and ADL-28 was developed, yielding a pseudo-R² of 0.61, sensitivity of 0.72, and specificity of 0.95 with full model. Figure 1 presents normalized aggregated confusion

matrix from leave-one-out cross-validation stage of model development.

Both correlation and regression analyses utilized data with mean values per resident from timed measurements.

Figure 1. A normalized confusion matrix of multinomial logistic regression classification of residents.

Conclusions

The study revealed significant variability in resident capabilities, underscoring the complexity of modeling evacuation for the elderly in assisted living. It notably highlighted the nursing staff’s critical role in such scenarios, which proved more significant than previously anticipated. However, the conclusions drawn are primarily indicative due to the small dataset, emphasizing the necessity for further research with more extensive data. Nevertheless, found correlations indicate a promising route for estimating evacuation parameters from existing health data.

Additionally, the study identified a need for deeper investigation into how the capabilities and roles of the nursing staff can be accurately reflected in evacuation modeling.

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Fire Safety Enhancement of Post-War High-Rise Residential Buildings

The Case Study of Social Housing in Brussels-Capital Region (Belgium)

Anass Rahouti

Fire & Emergency Management Team
VK Architects+Engineers, part of Sweco
Brussels, Belgium

anass.rahouti@vk-architects-engineers.com

Andrés Rodríguez

Fire & Emergency Management Team
VK Architects+Engineers, part of Sweco
Brussels, Belgium

andres.rodriquez@vk-architects-engineers.com

Yves Dechamps

Fire & Emergency Management Team
VK Architects+Engineers, part of Sweco
Brussels, Belgium

yves.dechamps@vk-architects-engineers.com

Keywords: *Fire, Safety, High-Rise, Residential, Building.*

Introduction

From the Second World War until 1972, numerous high-rise buildings (over 25 m high) were constructed in the Brussels-Capital Region to accommodate a steadily growing population. However, the fire safety level of these buildings, is often inadequate to today's standards and norms.

Indeed, while new residential towers have to meet stringent safety requirements, in Belgium, there is no legislation targeting the older residential buildings, whose retrofitting seems virtually impossible. Their high population density, poor construction quality and inadequate maintenance all combined together increases the risk of fire occurrence and may result to tragic consequences if a fire should occur.

Therefore, the main objective of this paper is to determine the most cost-effective measures to be put in place to protect the occupants of these old residential buildings against the risk of fire and to ensure their safe evacuation in the case of one.

Background

Prior to 1972, for all public buildings, there was no legal requirement for fire prevention measures in Belgium. It was only after the terrible Innovation Store fire (Figure 1 [1]), which claimed 251 lives in May 1967, that a legal framework was established leading to the publication of the Royal Decree of April 4, 1972 on fire protection in high-rise buildings [2]. It was the deadliest fire in Belgium's history.

The Innovation disaster was the catalyst. Strict regulations were applied not only to industry and worker protection, but also to nursing homes and stores. The requirements for new buildings have been extended to include stores, hotels, cafés and offices. They are regularly updated and adapted in line with innovations and lessons learned from incidents.

The 1972 Royal Decree made a series of fire resistance provisions mandatory, such as 2-hours fire stability requirements. Building owners were required to provide separate compartments to prevent fire spreading easily from one floor to another. This decree has since been repealed and replaced by a more modern legal framework. However, since

it has been enshrined in planning permission, firefighters can still refer to it.

It was followed in 1994 by the so-called "*AR Normes de base*", which means Basis Standards [3]. These regulations were based on the regulations from 1972, but introduced additional measures for high-rise buildings such as, for example, overpressure in interior stairwells.

Figure 1. *The Innovation Fire*

In the case of new high-rise buildings, minimum requirements have been imposed to achieve an acceptable residual risk. Nowadays, for example, building owners must first submit their plans to the fire department for approval. In the event of an unfavorable judgement, no building permit is issued.

For renovations of existing high-rise buildings, the Brussels Fire Brigade applies the safety principles of current regulations.

In summary, the following legal fire safety requirements apply to buildings of more than 25m in height (high-rise) :

- Before 1972: no legal fire safety requirements apply;
- Permit applications between 1972 and 05/25/1995: Royal Decree of April 4, 1972 laying down the general provisions of standard NBN 713-010 [4] relating to fire protection in high-rise buildings;
- Permit applications from 05/26/1995: annexes 1, 4/1, 5/1 and 7 of the Royal Decree of July 7, 1994, as amended by all subsequent Royal Decrees, setting the

basic standards for fire safety and explosion prevention.

Generally speaking, it can be said that high-rise buildings constructed from 1972 onwards present an acceptable fire risk, although this largely depends on the maintenance of the buildings and their equipment.

However, even recently constructed buildings do not necessarily offer an infallible guarantee of fire and life safety. Even in these buildings, installations and equipment such as elevators, fire doors, heating systems, etc. need to be inspected and maintained periodically to ensure that they do not undermine the fire and life safety strategy of the building, resulting in a higher residual risk than anticipated.

Methodology

The current study will only focus on residential high-rise buildings or at least those in which the main part is residential, specifically on social housing. The high-rise buildings, for which the main activities present are offices or industry, will not be taken into account in this study.

As illustrated in Figure 2, this study will be carried out in 4 steps:

1. Benchmarking of the fire safety rules that apply to high-rise buildings in other regions of Belgium, as well as in other countries/cities;
2. Inventory of the major safety issues encountered in high-rise buildings built before 1972 and not yet renovated in the region of Brussels-Capital;
3. Assessment of the applicability of the rules studied at the benchmarking stage to the context of high-rise residential buildings in Brussels, and identification of areas for improvement in current legislation in the Brussels-Capital Region;
4. Proposal of solutions based on the current situation and the rules studied during the benchmarking stage, and including indications of the costs of compliance (new technical installations, administrative and organizational procedures, maintenance, etc.).

Figure 2. The methodology followed in this study

As mentioned previously, the conditions and compliance status of the buildings studied are not yet known at this time. The remedial solutions (Step 4) should be designed keeping in mind a restricted budget on the part of the Owner and the durability of technical equipment put in place.

Results

As this study is still an ongoing project, the exclusive results will be presented at the NFSD.

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The influence of experimental conditions in the MCC for PMMA and fire-retardant Listolaan

Karen De Lannoye
Institute for Advanced
Simulations (IAS-7)
Forschungszentrum Jülich,
Jülich, Germany
k.de.lannoye@fz-juelich.de

Alexander Belt
Institute for Advanced
Simulations (IAS-7)
Forschungszentrum Jülich,
Jülich, Germany
a.belt@fz-juelich.de

Lukas Arnold
Institute for Advanced Simulations (IAS-7)/
Computational Civil Engineering (CCE).
Forschungszentrum Jülich/ University of Wuppertal,
Jülich/ Wuppertal, Germany
l.arnold@fz-juelich.de

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Micro-scale combustion calorimeter (MCC), polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), Listolan, Heat release rate (HRR)

Abstract

In fire safety science, milligram scale experiments are used to determine kinetic and thermophysical properties for flame spread modelling. Two of the most often used devices are the thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) and the micro-scale combustion calorimeter (MCC).

The MCC [1] was developed by the Federal Aviation Agency to study the flammability of fire-retardant materials. A sample of a few milligrams is placed into a sample cup, which is placed into a furnace (the pyrolyser). This furnace is heated at a constant heating rate. The temperature of the sample is monitored by a thermocouple located at the top of the sample carrier. The pyrolysis can be done either under anaerobic or under aerobic conditions. Above the pyrolyser the combustor is kept at a constant temperature. Pyrolysis gases released from the sample are combined with oxygen in the combustor. Based on oxygen calorimetry the heat release rate of the sample as a function of the temperature is measured. Sample preparation and sample conditioning is described in the ASTM-7309 [2], although some degrees of freedom remain, e.g. specimen form or sample mass (between 1 mg and 10 mg).

Previous studies, a.o. [3,4,5], have investigated the effect of experimental parameters in milligram experiments.

Especially, several publications conducted with the TGA are available. Amongst others the effects of heating rate, sample mass, sample preparation and surrounding atmosphere have been studied for PMMA. The number of publications studying the influence of experiment parameters in the MCC is considerably lower. For example, the effect of the heating rate, sample preparation and the pyrolysis atmosphere has been studied for polyurethane [5]. For PMMA the effect of the heating rate and the sample mass has been studied so far [6]. In general, sensitivity studies in the MCC have very low repetition experiments, as is the case with [6].

In this contribution, the influence of several experimental conditions is discussed. Specifically sample mass, heating

rate and sample preparation (solid or powder) will be studied. A first series of experiments will be conducted on black cast polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), since this is an often-used material in fire safety science. A comparison with the available literature will be presented. All experiments will be conducted in triplicate. Additionally, a fire-retardant material, will be studied. This in order to determine whether the conclusions drawn from the PMMA experiments can be generalized to flame-retardant materials, often studied in the MCC. As a flame-retardant material Listolan (from Lakowa) is chosen. This is a fire retardant, Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) based material often used in railway vehicles.

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Fire analysis tools for DEMO fusion power plant

Nikhil Verma
VTT Technical Research
Centre of Finland Ltd,
Espoo, Finland
nikhil.verma@vtt.fi

Timo Korhonen
VTT Technical Research
Centre of Finland Ltd,
Espoo, Finland
timo.korhonen@vtt.fi

Tuula Hakkarainen
VTT Technical Research
Centre of Finland Ltd,
Espoo, Finland
tuula.hakkarainen@vtt.fi

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Abstract

Fusion power plants are inherently safer than fission power plants, posing very low risk to populations in the vicinity and generating no long-lasting waste. However, there are still several safety topics to be studied and confirmed, one of those being fire safety.

This paper describes the work on defining fire zoning principles for the future demonstration fusion power plant DEMO. Analyses were performed utilizing computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations with Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) software, as well as zone fire models and analytical calculation methods. Failure risks of fire sector partitions depending on room dimensions and fire load densities were mapped, and tables and graphs for design were produced. The applicability of different tools with varying levels of complexity for different use cases was also assessed.

Analytical calculation methods

Simple analytical formulas were used to calculate thermal penetration times of fire sector boundaries, heat release rates (leading to dangerous situations), upper gas layer temperatures, and the pressure development. The methods introduced in the NUREG-1805 report [1] were used to develop an Excel sheet for the calculations. The material values for concrete were also according to NUREG-1805 [1].

The concrete material to be used in the fire sector boundaries of the DEMO is not yet known. Therefore, the thermal penetration time with randomized concrete properties was calculated and the probability of thermal penetration time greater than a given time was estimated. The thermal penetration time was calculated for 20000 randomly drawn samples for thicknesses of 0.2 m, 0.4 m, 0.6 m, 0.8 m, and 1.0 m. The probability distribution of various thermal properties of concrete and the related upper and lower bounds (thermal conductivity 0.0014–0.0018 kW/(m K); specific heat capacity 0.6–1.0 kJ/(kg K); density 2100–2500 kg/m³) were taken from ref. [2].

The results of thermal penetration time probability calculations are summarized in Table 1. It can be noted that all the concrete thicknesses have probability of 1 for the thermal penetration time for at least 2 hours.

Table 1. Summary of thermal penetration time probability for various concrete thickness.

Probability : Thermal penetration time is at least greater than	0.2 m thickness	0.4 m thickness	0.6 m thickness	0.8 m thickness	1 m thickness
2 hours	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
4 hours	0.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
6 hours	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
8 hours	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
10 hours	0.0	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.0
12 hours	0.0	0.6	1.0	1.0	1.0
18 hours	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
24 hours	0.0	0.0	0.8	1.0	1.0
36 hours	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.0	1.0
48 hours	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	1.0
72 hours	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7
96 hours	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
120 hours	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

The developed Excel sheet produces multiple outputs, e.g., minimum heat release rate (HRR_{min}) to cause upper gas layer temperature ($T_{g, up}$) to reach 500 °C, time for $T_{g, up}$ to reach 500 °C with HRR_{min} , and total energy released when $T_{g, up}$ reached 500 °C with HRR_{min} . An example of the results is shown in Figure 1. The prime output of the calculations is HRR_{min} to cause $T_{g, up}$ to reach 500 °C. This value is found when the curve of time to cause $T_{g, up}$ to reach 500 °C intersects with the curve of time to consume oxygen as shown in Figure 1: ca. 4800 kW (at ca. 65 s) for a sample compartment calculation (8 m × 7 m × 3 m).

Figure 1. Example of analytical calculation results: Minimum heat release rate to cause upper gas layer temperature to reach 500 °C (a sample compartment 8 m x 7 m x 3 m).

Zone fire models

Zone fire models are relatively simple computer programmes that can be used to simulate the fire induced environment typically in rectangular enclosures. The enclosures are basically treated as two control volumes, a hot layer close to ceiling and a cold layer below. It is known experimentally that the transition from the hot layer to the cold layer is relatively sharp in many compartment fires. Thus, using just the two zones to model the environment in an enclosure is appropriate in many cases.

In this work, zone fire models OZone [2] [3] and CFAST [4] were utilized to study rooms with a relatively simple geometry, such as galleries and the LiPb room. Zone fire models are well suitable for fast screening since they give results in a relatively short time compared to CFD simulations. However, due to certain limitations, zone fire models cannot be reliably used for analyzing rooms and spaces with complex fire scenarios or geometries. The applicability of the zone models for various purposes was assessed by comparisons to the results of FDS simulations.

CFD simulations using FDS software

During 2021–2024, FDS [5] [6] has been used to study the fire safety issues of several rooms and spaces of the DEMO power plant, including the LiPb room, vacuum pumping rooms, galleries and vertical shafts. A part of these can be evaluated sufficiently reliably using zone fire models or analytical calculation methods with conservative assumptions.

In the comparison of the results it was seen, however, that for complex fire scenarios and geometries, FDS simulations are needed. An example of complex geometries are vertical shafts which have a height of ca. 50 m and horizontal cross sections of ca. 5–10 m². A fire scenario for which zone models are not sufficient is a compartment having no open door nor another significant opening to outer space. In this case, zone fire models fail to accurately predict pressure development. However, when it comes to fire-induced pressure in mechanically ventilated compartments with small openings, FDS outperforms zone fire models. FDS leverages its HVAC module, utilizing available ventilation network data and fan characteristics. Remarkably, even in the absence of specific data for the DEMO building's ventilation network and fan characteristics, FDS predictions remain more realistic and both qualitatively and quantitatively indicative. Notably, FDS captures phenomena such as reverse flow and increased outlet flow during significant fire-induced overpressures.

Conclusions

A low-data-based methodology, based on analytical calculation methods, has been developed and implemented as an Excel sheet to conduct fire hazard estimation of various compartments. In this methodology, overconservative assumptions are typically used. Therefore, the lack of detailed DEMO design does not affect significantly. Screening can be done using a variety of inputs, e.g., parametric studies are easy to do. When more accurate data is available, this tool can be used to quickly obtain analysis

results for the updated information of room dimensions, material properties, and other input parameters.

Zone fire models can be used to assess the fire safety of relatively simple room geometries in basic fire scenarios. They are well suitable for fast screening since they are less time consuming and computationally less costly than CFD simulations. For detailed analyses of complex fire scenarios and geometries, however, more sophisticated tools such as FDS software are needed.

The work presented in this paper supports the fire safety analysis of the DEMO fusion power plant when its design is more mature than today. Though several calculations and simulations need to be re-run with updated input parameters, the same tools and principles can be utilized.

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Flame retardants (FRs): balancing the benefits.

What research is needed on flame retardants' impacts in reducing fires, smoke emission and smoke toxicity ?

Adrian Beard, pinfa,
Brussels, Belgium
and Clariant, Knapsack,
Germany
Adrian.Beard@Clariant.com

Chris Thornton,
consultant to pinfa,
Lyon, France
pinfa-consultant@thornton.fr

Thomas Esche,
pinfa, Brussels, Belgium
and BASF Schweiz AG,
Kaisten, Switzerland
thomas.esche@basf.com

Sander Kroon,
pinfa, Brussels, Belgium
and ICL Industrial Products,
The Netherlands
Sander.Kroon@icl-group.com

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flame retardant ; smoke; toxicity ; risk-benefit ; prevention

Abstract

Flame retardants (FRs) are essential to achieve fire safety standards in many applications and materials [1]. There is discussion of their possible impacts on smoke and of firefighter cancer risks.

We present the different modes of action of different types of flame retardant (gas phase, char-forming, heat damping, fire gas dilution, smoke repressants, anti-drip). We summarise scientific publications, regulatory reports and media communications with different conclusions concerning FR effectiveness and their impacts on smoke [2].

The aim is to engage discussion on what research is needed to better assess the risk – benefit balance of using different FRs in different applications.

Do FRs impact smoke toxicity?

Many phosphorus, inorganic and nitrogen (PIN) flame retardants are Low Smoke Zero Halogen, and can meet demanding requirements for applications where limiting smoke emission and smoke corrosivity is essential (e.g. trains, metro systems, aircraft) [3].

Some NGOs suggest that FRs increase smoke toxicity *“The slow burning of furniture materials, especially those containing flame retardant chemicals, results in combustion products including soot, particulate matter, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and a complex gaseous mixture that can include the toxic gases hydrogen cyanide and carbon monoxide”* [4].

Studies funded by industry suggest that in both lab scale tests (72 different polymer – FR formulations) [5] and in full-scale room tests [6], FRs do not significantly impact smoke toxicity. A UK study, based on fire tests of four mock-furniture items, suggested higher smoke toxicity but lower fire growth rate with FRs [7]. This led to dissent and rebuttal [8], [9].

Some studies suggest that different FRs impact smoke toxicity differently [10]: gas phase FRs potentially increase incomplete combustion products, but char-forming FRs reduce toxicity [11], [12]. Other studies suggest that FRs do not increase overall smoke toxicity in real fires [13].

What research is needed to identify and develop FRs which reduce smoke emission and toxicity in real fire conditions in different materials?

FRs and firefighters

Firefighters say that fire safety standards are essential to save lives [14] [15]. Respecting fire safety specifications is not possible in many flammable materials without flame retardants (e.g. polymer compounds and composites, textiles, wood ...), and including non-flammable fire safety barriers into equipment is often not feasible or incompatible with consumer design requirements, cost or light-weighting.

Occupational exposure is recognized as a cancer risk for firefighters [16]. Some firefighters reported in media suggest that FRs are a cause of this risk [17].

What research is needed to clarify whether or not FRs, or which types of FR in which applications, might impact chronic cancer risks of smoke for firefighters?

Risks versus benefits?

There can be confusion over what FRs do and don't do. FRs are intended to prevent fires from being started by heat sources such as electric faults (arcing, overheating), cigarettes or small flames. They also slow initial fire development, allowing more time for extinction (e.g. sprinklers), occupant escape and fire fighter intervention. PIN FRs also have specific functions such as smoke suppression or preventing burning dripping (fire spread). FRs do not prevent flammable materials from burning once a full-scale fire develops (polymers, wood ...).

V. Babrauskas who previously authored a significant 1998 US National Bureau of Standards report demonstrating the fire safety benefits of FRs [18], launched controversy with a 2011 paper [19] suggesting that California's furniture fire safety regulation TB117 *“has not been shown to have a measurable fire safety benefit”*.

This debate continues today with continuing questioning of the effectiveness of FRs [20].

On the other hand, a recent expert review [21] suggests that “*It is a blatant falsehood that flame retardants do not work, and it is something that all fire safety scientists should speak up about. ... It is possible to have fire safety AND environmental safety*”.

The research report supporting the current revision of the UK Furniture Fire Safety Regulations [22] concludes: “*The starkly contrasting conclusions of these studies exemplifies the difficulty in evaluating the relative risks and benefits of FR use in furniture.*” [23].

A further paper suggests that to balance fire safety benefits and possible FR risks, lower fire safety standards may be justified in a few specific furniture types (e.g. small items, items intended for infants) [24].

What approaches to risk-benefit analysis of FR use (use of different FRs, use in certain applications or conditions ...) can be developed to address these conflicting opinions?

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Integrity of intumescent coatings on steel elements subjected to large mechanical deformations

Luisa Giuliani

Civil and Mech. Eng. Dept.
(DTU Construct), Technical
University of Denmark
Byg. 118, Kgs. Lyngby, DK
lugi@dtu.dk

Terese Sløk

Civil and Mech. Eng. Dept.
(DTU Construct), Technical
University of Denmark
Byg. 118, Kgs. Lyngby, DK
tasloek@hotmail.com

Lars R. Olsen

Artelia Denmark
Buddingevej 272
Søborg, DK

lrol@arteliagroup.dk

Andrea Lucherini

Fire-Safe Sustainable Built En-
vironment (FRISSBE)
Slovenian National Build. and
Civil Eng. Inst., Ljubljana, SI
andrea.lucherini@zag.si

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Background and motivation

Intumescent coatings (ICs) represent nowadays a dominant solution for fire protection of steel structures, due to the progressive decrement of the costs, increment of the performance and advantages in comparison to inert protections in term of encumbrance, appearance, weight, and offsite application. Advances in the development of more efficient and less costly ICs extended the market of such type of fire protection well beyond the original use in low-rise steel buildings. Nowadays ICs are used to protect high-rise buildings, car parks, industrial halls, off-shore structures, and even bridge cables [1].

However, the theoretical understanding necessary to predict the behaviour of such ICs and translate it in simple but reliable design methods has not kept up with the development of the building sector. The design of IC insulation is mostly based on experimental assessment of the coating fire resistance rating. Such tests are performed by exposing unloaded, vertically placed, short steel profile segments to a nominal fire and measure the time, at which a pre-defined critical temperature is reached. The tests do not account for possible cracking or fallout of the fire protection due to the IC expansion on a concave profile or due to large bending or tensile deformation of horizontal members or diagonal bracings.

Therefore, when using the test results for the fire protection design of steel elements, engineers implicitly assume that the intumescent coating can follow the deformation of the steel without cracking or that the cracks are small enough to close during the expansion phase of the coating and do not cause detachment or fallout of the IC between the cracks. The validity of such assumption depends on several parameters, such as the extent of IC expansion [2], the adhesion of the IC on the steel substrate, and the amount of steel deformation, as well as the IC product itself.

The expansion of the coating in particular is subjected to uncertainty, as past research has highlighted its dependency not only on the temperature, but also on the heating rate, which in a real natural fire might be very different from the tests [3].

The adhesion of the coating depends, among other factors, on the substrate surface, thickness of IC, presence of a reinforcing mesh, as well as shape (concave/convex) and orientation (horizontal/vertical) of the profile.

In particular, a minimum 2% tensile deformation should be accounted in the design, if the “effective yielding strength” indicated in the EN1993-1-2 [3] is used as design steel strength in fire condition, as normally done when the Eurocode design methods are followed. In addition, larger deformations (at least up to 5%) can be sustained by steel elements and joints of buildings erected in earthquake-prone area. In case of a fire immediately following the earthquake, the fire resistance of the building and the safety of the fire-fighters could be compromised, if the fire protection applied on the steel elements is damaged as a consequence of large drift and element deformation [4].

Previous studies conducted on different inert types of sprayed fire resistant materials (SFRM) [5] indicated that cracking and even detachment of such protective materials might occur at strain as low as three times the steel yielding value. Similar results have been obtained by a previous preliminary study carried out at DTU [6], where rectangular steel plates protected with 3 different intumescent coatings have been subjected to uniaxial tensile deformations at ambient temperature. The results indicated that the onset of IC cracking occurs shortly after the steel yielding and that significant cracks and, in some cases, detachment of the IC layer are visible before 2% or 5% deformation in the steel. Furthermore, the amount of cracking or detachment increases with the thickness of the IC. However, these tests were limited to few samples and to epoxy-based ICs only. Furthermore, since they were all carried out at ambient temperature, they cannot enlighten on the possible closure and recovery of the IC cracks during heating, owed to the expansion of the IC.

Research objectives and methodology

The present experimental study is aimed at extending the previous experimental campaign on the mechanical resistance of IC at ambient temperature, by also including water-based IC (which are mostly used in the built environment) and circular hollow profiles and by considering the effects of high temperature heating on the damaged samples. In particular, the experimental campaign included two different steel profiles (1 m long bars with 4mmx50mm rectangular section and 1 m long pipes with hollow circular section having external diameter 26.9 mm and thickness 2.3mm), four different ICs (two epoxy-based and two water-based) and two different thicknesses for each IC.

Four identical samples were painted for each type of IC, thickness, and profile: three were tensile tested in an actuator imposing different deformation levels in the range 2-8.5%, while the fourth sample was not tensile tested, to serve as reference for the behaviour in fire of an undamaged protected sample. Then, the three damaged sample and the undamaged one of each set were placed in an electric furnace and heated up to 600°C at a heating rate of ca. 8°C/min. Due to technical issues, three rectangular plates samples (R) coated with IC type A had to be excluded from the testing. Thus, the total number of tested samples (as listed in Tab.1) is 37. Of these, the tests on the plates protected by IC type A and D have been fully completed, while the remaining tests are ongoing.

Tab. 1: List of performed tests and sample nomenclature

IC name	Profile	Target IC thick.	Sample label	Tensile deform.
A water-based	Plate (R)	1.5 mm	R-A1.5_1	excluded
			R-A1.5_2	excluded
			R-A1.5_3	4.5%
			R-A1.5_4	0.0%
	Plate (R)	2.5 mm	R-A2.5_1	excluded
			R-A2.5_2	3.5%
			R-A2.5_3	8.5%
			R-A2.5_4	0.0%
	Pipe (P)	1.4 mm	P-A1.4_1	5.6%
			P-A1.4_2	5.6%
P-A1.4_3			5.3%	
P-A1.4_4			0.0%	
B water-based	Plate (R)	2.0 mm	R-B2_1	---
			R-B2_2	7.2%
			R-B2_3	6.0%
			R-B2_4	0.0%
	Plate (R)	4.0 mm	R-B4_1	2.0%
			R-B4_2	6.4%
			R-B4_3	7.8%
			R-B4_4	0.0%
C epoxy-based	Plate (R)	4.0 mm	R-C4_1	4.3%
			R-C4_2	5.0%
			R-C4_3	5.0%
			R-C4_4	0.0%
	Plate (R)	10 mm	R-C10_1	8.4%
			R-C10_2	4.5%
			R-C10_3	5.4%
			R-C10_4	0.0%
Pipe	6.5 mm	P-C6.5_1	<i>ongoing</i>	
		P-C6.5_2		
		P-C6.5_3		
		P-C6.5_4		
D epoxy-based	Plate (R)	4.0 mm	R-D4_1	6.0%
			R-D4_2	8.5%
			R-D4_3	5.9%
			R-D4_4	0.0%
	Plate (R)	10 mm	R-D10_1	7.0%
			R-D10_2	6.1%
			R-D10_3	6.9%
			R-D10_4	0.0%

Results and conclusions

From the visual inspection of the tensile tested samples, it is seen that deformation larger than 5% can induce a significant damage in the IC, which can lead to higher temperatures than

those of a sample protected with undamaged IC. This is the case for sample R-D10_2 (Fig. 1), which presented a large detachment of the IC on the bottom surface after the test sample.

However, a similar loss of the IC and steel temperature increment is not visible in samples R-D10_1 and 3, despite they had similar plastic deformation and similar damage level. This indicates that the amount of IC loss during the heating is not only depended on the damage level of the paint caused by the tensile deformation, but also influenced by other factors, such as different types of damage (number, size, position of the cracks), as well as variability of the IC thickness on the sample and other uncertainties.

Fig. 1: measured averaged temperatures in the furnace test of samples R-D10_1-4 as well as temperature of the oven (red) and calculated uninsulated steel temperature (black).

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Towards a more sustainable method for testing of intumescent coatings

Beril Oguz

CoaST, Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), 2800 Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
berog@kt.dtu.dk

Emil O. Lidman Olsson

CoaST, Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), 2800 Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark

Jochen A.H. Dreyer

CoaST, Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), 2800 Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark

Kim Dam-Johansen

CoaST, Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), 2800 Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark

Keywords:

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Abstract

Steel structures require protection from high-temperature exposure to prevent loss of strength, which can result in structural failures and collapses. While intumescent coatings represent a common solution for steel protection, their commercialization presents challenges, notably due to their high cost and energy requirements for compliance with industry standards. This leads researchers to use lab-scale methods, however a big challenge remains: there is no direct link between these methods and the industrial scale method. In this work, we explore different factors in lab-scale testing, such as steel section factor, sample shape and size, and insulation materials, to find the optimal lab-scale testing method that matches the industrial-scale results.

Introduction

Steel is a widely used material alongside concrete in the building sector, offering a relatively cost-effective solution. While inherently non-flammable, steel undergoes significant strength reduction when subjected to high temperatures, particularly beyond critical thresholds like 500-550°C. This susceptibility poses a risk of structural failure and building collapse[1]–[3]. Therefore, implementing effective fire protection measures is imperative to save lives.

Intumescent coatings are a promising solution due to their easy application using rollers, brushes, or airless sprays, as well as their pleasing aesthetics. These coatings can expand up to 100 times their original thickness and can therefore create an insulation layer between the fire and the substrate. This layer helps prolong the time to steel structure failure, providing people with additional time to evacuate the buildings[3], [4].

Intumescent coatings are commercialized according to national and international standards such as ISO 834, UL 1709, ASTM E119-18c, EN 1363-2. These standards require the use of hydrocarbon fired industrial furnaces which are both energy-intensive and expensive. Consequently, researchers rely on the use of lab-scale methods in the phase of development of new formulations[5]. Nonetheless, these

methods are not standardized, often employing flat plates as samples, and various insulation materials across institutions further complicate matters.

In this study, several parameters including sample size and shape, section factor and insulation materials were examined to assess their impact on fire protection performance. Although the lab-scale results are not aligned with the industrial-scale results, key insights depending on these parameters were shown in this series of experiments.

Experimental

Samples were tested in lab-scale and industrial-scale furnaces. All samples were coated with a commercially available hydrocarbon fire coating, applied at a DFT of 5 mm, and were exposed to hydrocarbon fire EN 1363-2 in both furnaces. All tests were stopped upon reaching a critical temperature of 550°C.

Panel samples with 5 x 200 x 300 mm³ and 1 m columns with HEA 300 steel profile were tested in an industrial-scale furnace at Hempel, Spain. Panel samples and column samples had a section factor of 200 m⁻¹ and 153 m⁻¹, respectively. The gas-fired industrial furnace with a volume of 7.5 m³ accommodated 4 panel samples simultaneously through 4 openings. The panel samples were coated on one side (exposed to fire), while the other side was thermally insulated using a 5 cm thick ceramic fiber blanket. Both sample temperatures and furnace temperatures were monitored using K-type thermocouples during the tests.

Test samples of square blocks measuring 50 mm in length and with sides of 30 mm, as well as round discs with a thickness of 5 mm and a diameter of 90 mm were tested in a lab-scale furnace named CoaST-Fire, developed at the Technical University of Denmark[6]. The dimensions of the block samples were chosen to align with the section factor of columns in the industrial furnace (153 m⁻¹), while the round discs matched the panels in the industrial furnace (200 m⁻¹). The samples were placed in a sample cup (Fig.1) that moved vertically upwards in the furnace with a temperature gradient. The movement was controlled such that the temperature at the sample followed the fire curve. Sample temperatures were measured using a K-type thermocouple. To ensure stability of the expanded char, a ring (made of either metal or ceramic fiber) was employed around the coated samples.

Figure 1. Side view of sample cup arrangement in CoaST-Fire.

Results and Discussion

The tests investigate the effect of sample size and shape in different equipment as presented in Figure 2.

Experiments were conducted in both CoaST-Fire and an industrial furnace using samples with different section factors and shapes. Tests in the industrial furnace reveal that using 3 different shapes results in different critical times, despite two of them having the same section factor. The column sample with a section factor of 153 m^{-1} reached a critical time of 64 minutes whereas the block sample with a section factor of 153 m^{-1} reached a critical time of 21 minutes within the same equipment. Moreover, the round disc sample with a section factor of 200 m^{-1} reached a critical time of 18 minutes while the block sample reached a critical time of 15 minutes.

Figure 2. Temperature of steel samples with different shapes tested in CoaST-Fire and an industrial furnace.

Another aspect of the study involved investigating the effect of changes in the insulation materials and/or arrangement used. The results are shown in Figure 3. The experiments show that using a metal ring could cause heat conduction on the expanded char resulting in the shortest critical time. To tackle this issue, a ceramic fiber ring was used, demonstrating an improvement in fire protection performance. Furthermore, a significant impact was seen when using an insulation material with lower thermal conductivity. However, the most notable outcome was obtained by using a sample that was coated on the sides as well, yielding the longest critical time observed in CoaST-Fire.

Figure 3. Temperature of steel samples with different sample cup arrangements tested in CoaST-Fire.

Conclusion

Based on these findings, a flat plate used in a lab-scale equipment is not directly representative of the samples tested in industrial scale. Additionally, the tests show that section factor is not the only key parameter affecting the results, other factors such as sample size and shape are also important.

The experiments conducted in CoaST-Fire show the importance of enhanced insulation on the uncoated side of the sample, revealing a correlation with improved fire protection performance. This is due to samples in lab-scale equipment are usually flat plates and coated only on one side as the uncoated side needs to be well-insulated. In contrast, the columns to be tested in industrial furnaces are coated all around and do not require insulation.

Overall, while various lab-scale methods are utilized in research, they fall short in representing the real-size elements in industrial furnaces. Consequently, further research is necessary to identify optimal testing conditions.

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Predicting the performance of thin intumescent coatings using a small-scale electric furnace

Initial experimental results compared to data from full-scale fire resistance tests

Emil O. Lidman Olsson Beril Oguz Jochen A.H. Dreyer Peter Arendt Jensen Kim Dam-Johansen
 CoaST, Technical CoaST, Technical CoaST, Technical CHEC, Technical CoaST, Technical
 University of Denmark, University of Denmark, University of Denmark, University of Denmark, University of Denmark,
 Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
eliol@kt.dtu.dk

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Abstract

Intumescent coatings can prolong the fire resistance time of structural steel. To certify an intumescent coating, fire-resistance tests in large hydrocarbon-fired furnaces have to be carried out, which is expensive and time-consuming. Efficient and reliable laboratory-scale testing methods are therefore required such that screening of new coating formulations can be done at an early stage. In this work, commercial coatings were tested in a small-scale electric furnace to determine an effective thermal conductivity. The result was used in a simple heat transfer model to predict the coating performance in full-scale fire resistance tests. The predictions agreed well with the data based on full-scale tests over a wide range of dry film thicknesses and section factors. This methodology may provide an efficient way to predict the coating performance through a quick test in a laboratory-scale electric furnace, using only a small sample.

Introduction

The fire resistance of structures can be improved by applying intumescent coatings to the surface of construction elements. When exposed to heat, intumescent coatings expand to form an insulating char layer that reduces the heat flux from the fire to the construction element. Intumescent coatings are used on a wide range of structures, ranging from residential buildings to heavy chemical industries. Testing and certifying intumescent coatings according to standards such as EN 13381-8 (Test methods for determining the contribution to the fire resistance of structural members – Part 8: Applied reactive protection to steel members) [1] is expensive and time-consuming. Numerous laboratory-scale methods have been developed to provide cheaper and faster screening methods to complement full-scale fire resistance tests [2]. However, there appears to be no efficient and reliable laboratory-scale method available to predict how a coating formulation will perform in a full-scale fire resistance test.

At the Hempel Foundation Coatings Science and Technology Centre (CoaST), Technical University of Denmark, a small scale electric furnace was previously

developed for testing of intumescent coatings [3]. However, the current design has some limitations. For example, the sample holder is causing radiation shadow effects, and may physically hinder the char expansion process. Also, a method to allow for comparison with results from full-scale fire resistance tests is needed. In this work, an alternative sample arrangement was tested, and a method to predict the fire resistance performance in full-scale tests was developed.

Materials and Method

Test specimens were prepared by embedding 60x60x3 mm³ steel panels in a 5 mm thick inorganic fiber insulation frame. The steel panel and fiber frame were coated with commercially available intumescent coatings with a target dry film thickness (DFT) of 1.5 mm. The fiber frame and steel panel were placed horizontally on top of 5 cm of insulating calcium silicate based wool blanket. The temperature of the steel panels was measured using a type K copper-disk thermocouple positioned on the back of the steel panel. The sample arrangement is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A section view of the sample arrangement.

A small electric furnace, LHT 01/17D from Nabertherm, was used to test the samples. The furnace was set to follow the standard temperature-time curve for cellulosic fires (ISO 834 / EN 1363-1). Because the furnace is controlled using a type S thermocouple protected by a ceramic tube, which may cause some delay in the temperature measurement, the gas temperature in the furnace was also measured using a sheeted type K thermocouple. During a blank run, the heat flux in the furnace was measured using a water-cooled heat flux sensor. The heat flux was found to be in the range of what others have measured in full-scale fire resistance tests.

In full scale fire resistance tests, a wide range of section factors and coating DFTs are tested. To enable prediction of

the coating performance at other section factors and DFTs than those used here (333 m^{-1} and 1.5 mm , respectively), a method based on effective thermal conductivity was therefore adopted. The method is based on a simple heat transfer model, in which the effective thermal conductivity of the char is calculated using the temperature increase of the steel panel. Similar methodologies have previously been used to assess the performance of intumescent coatings [4–7]. The effective thermal conductivity was then used to calculate a predicted steel temperature for other section factors and DFTs.

The predicted fire resistance was compared to data based on results from full-scale fire resistance tests. Linear interpolation of the data was performed in order to obtain the fire resistance time for a certain DFT, design temperature, and section factor.

Results and Discussion

The predicted fire resistance time as a function of DFT and section factor is shown together with data based on full-scale fire resistance tests in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. Generally, there is a good agreement between the prediction and the data based on full scale tests. Considering that intumescence is a complex process, the methodology should be used with some caution, especially for DFTs and section factors deviating much from the tested sample. Additionally, the methodology does not take factors such as stickability properties into account, which may have a major influence on the performance in a full-scale test. In the current layout, the sample was positioned horizontally, so the char would remain on top of the steel, whereas poor stickability may cause the char to detach and fall off in a full-scale test. It should also be noted that this method predicts the performance of a coating applied to sections similar to plates, for example hollow sections such as circular or rectangular columns. For shapes such as I- or H-sections, the performance is normally quite different, which is probably due to effects of char expansion in corners and heat transfer (radiation) shadows in the web. However, if aware of the limitations of the methodology, it may prove a useful tool in the assessment of intumescent coating performance.

Conclusions

The performance of a thin intumescent coating in a full-scale fire resistance test could be predicted accurately using the test methodology described in this work. The results show that the fire resistance time of a steel member protected by the intumescent coating can be predicted over a wide range of section factors and DFTs. The current methodology seems promising, and it appears worth developing the testing method, for example to also cover hydrocarbon temperature-time curves. The described testing method can provide an efficient and reliable way of screening different coating formulations. It may therefore prove useful in coating development.

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Figure 2. Fire resistance time as a function of DFT for a commercial coating. Data based on full scale fire resistance tests using hollow section columns shown together with the prediction obtained in this work. Section factor: 150 m^{-1} .

Figure 3. Fire resistance time as a function of section factor for a commercial coating. Data based on full scale fire resistance tests using hollow section columns shown together with the prediction obtained in this work. DFT: 1.5 mm .

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Calculating gas emissivities using HITEMP, and engineering approximations of the results

Andrea Correa
Division of Structural and
Fire Engineering, Luleå
University of Technology
Luleå, Sweden
andrea.correa@ltu.se

Paul Otxoterena
Department of Fire and
Safety, RISE Research
Institutes of Sweden
Borås, Sweden
paul.otxoterena@ri.se

Michael Försth
Division of Structural and
Fire Engineering, Luleå
University of Technology and
RISE Research Institutes of
Sweden
Luleå, Sweden
michael.forsth@ltu.se

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Introduction

Fires release energy by convective heating and by emission of electromagnetic radiation. Radiative heat transfer typically corresponds to 1/3 of the energy release from fires, the other ~2/3 of the energy being released as convective heating to the fire plume [1]. Radiative heat transfer differs from convective heat transfer in many respects. For example, convective heat transfer is directed upwards from the fire, due to buoyant forces acting on the hot, low density fire plume. On the other hand, radiative heat transfer is isotropic and the photons are released in arbitrary directions. Therefore, radiative heat transfer is an important contributor to horizontal flame spread, e.g. from one façade to an opposing façade, where the convective heat transfer has no, or very low, component horizontally from the burning façade to the threatened façade, whereas the threatened façade is exposed without limitations by the radiation emitted from the burning façade.

The electromagnetic radiation from flames mainly originates from soot particles and the non-symmetric major species CO₂ and H₂O. Minor species such as CO and intermediates such as OH radicals also contribute to the radiation from flames.

Hydrogen is receiving more and more interest as an energy carrier, for example in fuel cell vehicles and in fossil-free production of steel. From a safety perspective the large-scale introduction of hydrogen infrastructures is a challenge. Accidental releases might result in explosions and jet flames, with severe implications for lives, properties, as well as for continuity of critical societal functions.

Accidental release from a hydrogen pipeline, resulting in a large hydrogen jet flame, is a very realistic scenario. The radiation from the flame will affect objects such as humans, vehicles, and buildings, if they are positioned sufficiently near the flame. Most research in this area have been focused on fossil gases such as propane for example. Interestingly, the radiation from hydrogen jet flames is more tractable for fundamental combustion physics studies than what is the case for fossil gases. The reason is the absence of carbon in the fuel which removes all soot kinetics as well as the very complex combustion gas phase reaction mechanisms involving carbon [2]. In particular, since no soot nor CO₂ is available in the flame or in the fire effluents the molecular physics calculation of radiation is also simplified, since it can be assumed that most of the radiation originates from H₂O. Another effect of the lack of carbon in hydrogen jet flames is that they are not, or hardly, visible to the human eye. This is a major safety concern since the visual warning that appears from fossil flames, issued mainly from incandescent soot particles, is lacking.

The radiation from large scale hydrogen jet flames is relatively little researched, as compared to e.g. propane flames [3]. Comparison of the radiative fraction, that is the fraction of the total energy release from the jet fire that is emitted as radiation, varies from less than half of those for hydrocarbon fire [4] to values similar to hydrocarbon flames [3], despite the lack of soot and CO₂ in hydrogen flames. In order to develop evidence-based safety distances in guidelines, standards and regulations it is necessary to improve the accuracy of prediction of radiation from these flames. This, together with the fact that hydrogen jet flames are tractable for fundamental chemical kinetic and molecular radiation studies is the background for the research performed in this project.

Method

The amount of heat radiation from hydrogen jet flames and plumes, with H₂O mixed in non-radiating gases (such as N₂, O₂, Ar), have been calculated using the HITEMP2010 database [5]. A literature study has been performed and the calculated results was compared to available experimental data.

Results

For optically thin gas volumes the Planck mean absorption coefficient can be used to calculate the emissivity of the flame [6]. Optically thin means that the gas, i.e. H₂O, participating in the radiative exchange does contribute to the radiation but is not so dense, or the volume is not so large, that reabsorption of the emitted radiation in the gas volume is significant [7]. The Planck mean absorption coefficient has been studied experimentally and numerically by many authors, e.g [8, 9]. In this study we have calculated the Planck mean absorption coefficient for H₂O using the latest update of the HITEMP database, HITEMP2010 [5], where a significant number of transitions has been added as compared to previous databases and calculations. The major findings are that the updated table of transitions impacts the calculated results, but also that there still remains uncertainties as compared to experimental measurements.

In order to make emissivity calculations simple we have also suggested engineering approximations of the results, expressed as closed-form analytical functions dependent on temperature and H₂O-concentration (by volume). The total pressure is assumed to be 1 bar in all calculations.

Finally, we discuss the assumption of an optically thin gas layer, when this is valid, and ways forward when the assumption is not valid.

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Minimizing contaminated extinguishing water through performance-based design

Eric Gard
Brandskyddslaget AB
Malmö, Sweden
eric.gard@bsl.se

Thomas de Korostenski
Brandskyddslaget AB
Stockholm, Sweden
thomas.korostenski@bsl.se

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Introduction

Due to its potential to absorb a lot of energy in combination with its availability, water is the most common extinguishing agent [1]. When water is used in fires it will most likely come in contact with pollutants that contaminates it. This can happen by washing away substances present on the site, by mixing with combustion products, or by washing down gases etc. [2]. The level of contamination depends on factors such as the burning material, the physical properties and chemical composition of the contaminating substance as well as its concentration and polarity, or the time of contact between the water and the substance [3]. After an intervention from the fire service, the level of contamination or pollutants is very variable. For most fires the extinguishing water is considered like a binary number i.e., either contaminated or not. If contaminated extinguishing water has been collected, testing can be performed to analyze the level of contamination to decide whether the water can be released out to the public mains or if it should be destroyed.

Contaminated extinguishing water from fires can be hazardous to human health and the environment [4], as well as expensive from an economical perspective [5] and potentially depraved public relations. The cost is associated with everything from destroyed property to downtime or destruction of the contaminated water, and the public relations are affected by environmental harm or impact on e.g. the drinking water (which is especially common when firefighting is carried out with foam). During the last two years, the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency and Environmental Protection Agency carried out a joint project that included collecting several hundred tons of fire extinguishing foam containing PFAS from fire and rescue services. The goal was to reduce the future risk of contaminating the environment in a cost-efficient way, and it was considered successful [6].

Many studies show the potential impact of the toxic substances in the run-off extinguishing water, however, the knowledge in the field lags in the development of the built environment. The Swedish regulations are not up to date with what an acceptable level of contamination is and regulations of potential environmental harm are not applied in a

preventative way in the construction process but rather focused in the environmental permitting process, which isn't necessarily applied or prioritized early enough. Thus, it's unclear what requirements must be fulfilled, and the requirements are usually set too late in the building process.

Proposed approach

To adopt a principle that entails both the construction phase and the environmental permit process in a project, the authors suggest a methodology that illustrates the challenges and emphasizes the interconnection between the different processes. This methodology should be adapted based on the specific conditions of the project to simplify the incorporation of extinguishing water management as something that is a natural part of the design process. Based on the timeline of the project, the methodology should also be incorporated differently at different stages to be as feasible and cost-effective as possible. This could mean a win-win situation for the environment, both in reduced need of extinguishing water and the management of the contaminated water. In the long run there are also other potential profits, for example the operational reliability of a business or its resilience to fires and its consequences.

Focus shift

Furthermore, many of the handbooks and guidelines on the topic focuses on the fire and rescue services' response rather than preventative fire safety design (for example, [6], [7] and [8]). This is especially important when considering the technological progress of society in general and new fire risks that are becoming increasingly more common [9], such as batteries or buildings with a lot of timber or cellular plastics. Both batteries, and the components for these, pose a special kind of threat [10], [11], [12] that is previously not considered enough when designing the fire safety and extinguishing water preparedness. The level of contamination in the extinguishing water are usually higher from fires involving batteries or other electronics compared to "traditional" fires, in dwellings and such [13]. The same can be said about timber and cellular plastics since it radically changes the amount of combustible material and potential fire growth in buildings [14], [15]. This emphasizes the importance that the industry itself needs to take responsibility for minimizing the risk of

releasing contaminated extinguishing water through proactive fire safety engineering.

New challenges

There are numerous relationships between the size of a fire (m^2 , kW, etc.) and how much extinguishing water that is required [16], [5]. Simplified, many models assume that the size of a fire grows exponentially with time (models such as " α^2 -fires" or similar) [17]. This also means that the required amount of extinguishing water also increases exponentially with time. If the objective is to limit the amount of extinguishing water, this correlation highlights the importance of not allowing a fire to become too large. Historically, exceptionally fast fire growth rates, complicated response conditions and the presence of environmentally hazardous materials have mainly been associated with large scale industries.

With technical development, new fire risks have been introduced in parts of the built environment where they previously didn't exist. The presence of more batteries in buildings (and their properties regarding fire dynamics) tears apart the traditional view of α^2 -fires [18]. Similarly, the reintroduction of timber as a popular building material reveals that the building regulations are not necessarily written with this in mind [19]. Also, many products containing plastics are designed to pass the standardized test methods to fulfill certain fire ratings while their performance when installed in a real-life building can differ a lot from the tests. Another important factor is the classifications of "*Green buildings*", which can introduce materials with unknown fire behavior, especially over long-term periods. The test certificate and protocols can show that a product fulfills the requirements, but it may be unclear how the product behaves after a prolonged exposure. Features such as green roofs or solar panels may be important components of a building's life cycle assessment when it comes to carbon footprint, but their impact during fire is rarely considered in that context.

Thus, the fire size and the required amount of extinguishing water isn't as predictable as before. As stated earlier, both batteries, timber and plastics potentially mean higher degrees of contamination of the extinguishing water. To minimize the impact to human health, the environment, the economy, and public relations, these new challenges, and uncertainties should be considered through fire safety engineering and involve all types of buildings – dwellings, offices, parking garages etc. To make the process feasible it is also necessary to introduce the requirements at an early phase in the project.

Applied fire safety engineering

This leads to the question of how fire safety engineering and performance-based design with a risk-based approach can be used to enable continued technological development without increasing the risk of environmental impact from extinguishing water. Depending on what identified risk that is present, different approaches can be adopted. The design could focus on reducing the size of fire compartments, early detection to enable an effort to extinguish a fire early or separating high-risk objects within their own fire compartment so they don't get involved in a major fire.

Notable in this case is sprinkler systems, since they can result in water being applied without someone actively deciding to initiate water application. This can be a problem if e.g., the containment of the water depends on someone shutting off a valve. However, installation of sprinkler systems usually results in a heavily reduced fire size, which, as mentioned earlier, is of great importance. The fire-technical part of the design should then be combined with assessments of other parts of the project's planning to ensure that the product is good enough compared to the project's requirements. The design can also focus on the unknown, i.e., to design something that's flexible enough to be easily adapted for future adjustments that's not yet known. Though, one of the main challenges when designing for the unknown is the justification of the cost of the design since the gain regarding e.g., insurance, is usually uncertain.

Conclusion

The main approach for handling extinguishing water is to make sure it doesn't reach a sensitive recipient. This is normally done by e.g., managing the water either inside a building, keep it on an open impermeable area, or gathering it within a collection pond. These approaches are often required and adapted to industrial sites, but the adaptation is somewhat of a challenge when it comes to premises located in other parts of the built environment, especially when considering the technological development and presence of new fire risks.

Also, all mentioned approaches are focused on collecting the water and not reducing the amount of water to begin with. Therefore, measures to reduce the amount of extinguishing water through performance-based fire safety design and a methodology incorporating this earlier in the project phase are proposed. To minimize the amount of extinguishing water, limiting the fire size is key. This can be achieved by early detection, fire compartmentation, smoke management systems, etc. These fire-technical measures must then be combined with the above-mentioned measures of managing the water. To ensure that the impact of contaminated extinguishing water is minimized, a design flow-chart is suggested. This will involve the environmental permit process, the design- and construction process and the intended use of the building.

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Overpressure Estimation from Vented Hydrogen Deflagration in Homogeneous Mixtures

Javier I. Camacho^{1,2}, Adina Arymbayeva¹, Juan Carlos Lopez Santiago¹

¹ The Danish Institute of Fire and Security Technology (DBI) Hvidovre, Denmark, jic@dbigroup.dk

² Division of Fire Safety Engineering, Lund University, Lund, Sweden

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Abstract

In this study, it is performed simulations that assess different scenarios of hydrogen vented deflagration. A sensitivity analysis was conducted to examine domain expansion. The comparison of the different user approaches reveals that the simulations consistently performed well with respect to experimental data. Findings indicate that an increment of the domain size, up to three times in function of the test chamber dimensions, in this case does not significantly exert any influence in the estimated peak overpressure. Consistent model performance was observed across different user.

Introduction

Hydrogen, known for its zero carbon emissions, is valued for advancing environmental sustainability and addressing the rise in global energy needs. Progress in Power-to-X (P2X) technologies has shifted hydrogen storage from remote industrial sites to urban areas.

In hydrogen production and storage, confined spaces are commonly utilised, emphasising the importance of proper venting to mitigate the consequences of flammable cloud explosions. The importance of accurately assessing explosion effects in these circumstances cannot be overstated, as it directly impacts risks management to individuals and assets. Simulations utilised for risk assessment serve as a versatile tool, facilitating the analysis of a wide range of explosion scenarios.

In this study, EXSIM software (version 6.0) [1] is employed to perform simulations, examining a range of hydrogen deflagration scenarios within a vented room. This investigation is a part of a comprehensive sequence of simulations that will be conducted on diverse software platforms.

Selected explosion experiments

A set of 18 experiments (without obstacles) conducted by Bauwens et al. [2] has been selected from a series of vented deflagration experiments with different homogenous H₂-air mixture concentration (12-19 % vol), vent opening size (5.4 or 2.7 m²), ignition location (centre or the back wall).

The explosion test was conducted on a chamber comprised by an enclosure of 63.7 m³ (4.6 x 4.6 x 3 m) with a square vent located at the centre of one of the vertical walls initially sealed by a polypropylene sheet. The pressure within the chamber was monitored by four pressure transducers positioned at various locations.

Methodology - Numerical Simulations

EXSIM use a finite volume method on a structured Cartesian grid using the Porosity/Distributed Resistance Method to represent the geometry, with a k-ε turbulence model and Eddy Dissipation Concept Model by Magnussen [3] for combustion. The test chamber is modelled as simple empty box with an opening and was used for simulations with varied hydrogen-air mixtures creating a uniform hydrogen cloud throughout. The method involves two steps to assess simulation aspects that might impact on the estimated peak overpressure: assessment of domain expansion impact and a cross-comparison on different user results. The following described procedure is based on user 1 systematic approach, while the two other users have also conducted similar analyses.

The first step involved evaluating the impact of calculation domain dimensions (beyond the region of interest) on the maximum pressure within the chamber (region of interest), following established hydrogen simulation guidelines [4]. Through a systematic expansion of the domain beyond the test chamber, it is possible to determine the simulation domain dimension that effectively reduces boundary effects on the estimated maximum overpressure inside the region of interest.

Two scenarios were simulated involving hydrogen concentration of 18% and central ignition. The simulations differed in vent sizes (5.4 m² and 2.7 m²), and pressure was monitored at sensor 1, which is centrally located on a side wall. A constant number of cells in the region of interest was maintained (approx. cubic cell and 0.4 m size). By applying integer factors ranging from 1 to 4, the simulation domain was uniformly scaled up, depending on the axis dimension of the region of interest. To provide an example, with a chamber length of 4.6 m in the x-direction, "Domain I" was created by extending 4.6 m in each direction from the region of interest. Once all simulations have been executed, a comparative analysis of the peak overpressure is performed. In this analysis, the relative percent difference (RPD) is compared to "Domain I", which is the minimum domain size as suggested in the EXSIM user manual. The selected domain, considered the most suitable, was utilised for the remaining simulations, facilitating cross-comparison analysis among the users.

The cross-comparison analysis of three users and DNV results from "validation summary" of EXSIM (version 6.0) is conducted following the protocol outlined by Hisken [5]. The justification for employing this method is based on the utilisation of statistical performance measures (SPMs) such as MG (geometric mean bias) and VG (geometric mean

variance), which assess both systematic and random errors. The performance benchmarks for the comparison have been defined as $0.7 \leq MG \leq 1.3$ for excellent performance and $0.5 \leq MG \leq 2$ for acceptable performance.

Preliminary results and discussion

Figure 1 Domain Expansion – (A) 5.4 m² vent, (B) 2.7 m² vent.

Domain sensitivity analyses have been performed by all users, although the study solely presents the findings for user 1. The results of the vented deflagration scenario with the larger of the two openings is shown in figure 1(a1-4). Regarding the maximum pressure, A1 is estimated to reach a peak pressure of 0.0394 bar at 203 ms, while A2 exhibits an RPD of 6.8% compared to A1 at 205 ms. The relative RPDs with respect to A1 of A3 and A4 are 8.4% at 213 ms and 8.8% at 214 ms, respectively. These findings suggest a decrease with each subsequent domain expansion while a delay in the pressure peak occurrence.

A fluctuating pattern has been detected, although it seems to have no effect on the overall impulse. The origin of this oscillation remains uncertain, necessitating further analysis of the entire pressure time series to determine if it is a potential numerical issue or if it is associated with physical phenomena. Considering that expanding the domain in function of the region interest 3 times with respect to 4 times did not show any evidence of a significant increment or reduction (0.4%) of the estimate peak pressure. It is possible to assume in this case, that expanding the domain beyond a factor of 3 with respect to the region of interest will not have any significant effect on mitigating the boundary interaction.

By examining the second scenario, where a smaller vent is utilized, as illustrated in figure 1(B1-4), it is determined that the peak pressure for B1 is estimated to be 0.2148 bar, occurring at 307 ms. The RPD observed in all domain expansion simulations remains below 0.5%, and there are no significant differences in the timing of occurrence, exhibiting variations in the order of 1 ms. A reduced oscillation is detected, implying that the scenario with the smaller vent demonstrates a lower level of sensitivity to domain expansion than the previous case.

The cross-comparison aims to assess the contribution of users' approach to the simulations. Each user has been using the same number of cell divisions in the region of interest with a 12x12x8 cells in each axis direction with 1152 cells in total as recommended in EXSIM manual, with a mesh expansion factor of 1. Anomalies have been observed in the behaviour of certain pressure monitors when positioned precisely at the boundary of the region of interest. These anomalies appear to result from numerical tolerances, as the sensors need to be within the region of interest. In response to this, users adopt various approaches to counteract the effect, either by expanding the region of interest by 1 mm

(user 1), or by positioning the sensors with a small offset of 10 - 20 mm (user 2 and DNV), or by a 1 mm sensor offset (user 3). Each user has different domain dimensions. The expansion of user 1 is increased by a factor of 3, resulting in a total length of 32.2 m in the x and y directions, and 9 m in the z direction above the test chamber. Users 2 and 3 have utilised identical domain dimensions, measuring 44.6 m in both the x and y directions, and 20 m in the z direction. DNV has been employing a relatively compact domain spanning 10 m in all directions, except for the z-direction.

The comparison of user simulations to experimental data and DNV's EXSIM validation in Figure 3 and table 1 demonstrates consistent model performance. The discrepancies observed among users were not significant (all are inside the perfect performance region $MG \pm 30\%$ and $VG < 1.6$), although DNV's results exhibited slight deviation, possibly attributable to a comparatively smaller computational domain.

Considering the deviation of user 2, with respect to user 3, since both are using the same domain, it found that the difference come from a slightly miss place of the ignition source (ignition location back wall) in the x-coordinate, where it should at 0.25 m but was placed quite close to the wall (0.01m). The results from users 2 and 3 align after the ignition source location was adjusted.

Figure 2 Users cross-comparison results.

Table 1 Summary of SPMs user cross-comparison					
	MG [-]	95 % CI	VG [-]	95 % CI	FAC2
DNV	0.78	[0.66, 0.92]	1.21	[1.12, 1.31]	0.94
User #1	0.99	[0.87, 1.15]	1.10	[1.05, 1.17]	1
User #2	1.08	[0.92, 1.26]	1.12	[1.06, 1.20]	1
User #2*	0.99	[0.87, 1.16]	1.10	[1.05, 1.17]	1
User #3	0.99	[0.86, 1.15]	1.10	[1.05, 1.18]	1

* Corrected Ignition Location

Conclusions

The sensitivity analysis of the domain suggests that increasing the domain size by a factor of three in relation to the test chamber in this specific case effectively mitigates any potential adverse interactions that could have a substantial impact on the accuracy of the predicted overpressure. The minor discrepancies observed in the results underscore the importance of selecting the domain size and placing the ignition source with care.

The subsequent investigations will focus on conducting mesh sensitivity analysis to improve the resolution of the region of interest and assess the impact of uncertainties in hydrogen concentration on the estimated peak pressure. The

assessments will utilize platforms including GASFLOW, OpenFOAM, and EXSIM as well.

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Perceived Research Needs for Battery and Hydrogen Safety – A Nordic Perspective

Marcus Runefors
Div. of Fire Safety Engineering,
Lund University
Sweden
marcus.runefors@brand.lth.se

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Abstract

This presentation will provide an overview of research needs for battery and hydrogen safety. The mapping is based on the views of both researchers and other actors in the Nordic countries with both interviews and a quantitative survey for prioritization.

Introduction

The new energy landscape, with a steadily increasing share of intermittent energy sources such as wind and solar, has put the question of energy storage high on the agenda. Two of the main candidates for balancing need and supply are batteries and hydrogen.

Hydrogen has been used for a long time in the chemical and petrochemical sector, and much can be learned from the research and experience in these areas. However, many of the current projects differ quite significantly from the industrial area with much higher pressures (up to 1000 bar(g)), more indoor installations, and installations closer to densely populated areas. All these factors put extra emphasis on safety and also introduce additional knowledge needs for safe operation.

Batteries, specifically lithium-ion batteries, on the other hand, is a significantly newer technology where the level of knowledge can be expected to be lower. On the other hand, there are many ongoing research projects covering various aspects of battery safety from cell- to system-level.

In this presentation, a project regarding perceived research needs for hydrogen and battery safety will be presented where the needs from both a researcher and application perspective will be mapped and prioritized. The word “perceived” is important since the, relatively small, project will not be able to perform a systematic investigation of the published literature. Therefore, it is likely that several topics have already been extensively investigated in the literature, but mapping the state-of-the-art needs to be performed after this project.

At the time of submission of this extended abstract, the project is not finalized (the deadline is mid-March 2024), but at the time of the conference, more detailed information will be available in the final report of the project [1].

Method

The mapping of research needs was based on a series of interviews, 20 in total, with both researchers (n=12) and non-researchers (e.g. authorities, companies) (n=8). Of the interviews, 12 focused on hydrogen and 8 on batteries.

The respondents were selected from the different Nordic countries based on convenience sampling to have variation in type of company, research area etc. The interviews were semi-structured based on the overarching question, “*What knowledge do you think is missing in the [hydrogen/battery] safety area?*”. As themes emerged during the analysis, several probing questions were added so that if the respondent did not talk about, for example, rescue service intervention, a question regarding that would be added to the interview.

The interviews, a total of ten hours, were transcribed and coded in NVivo version 14 to investigate the various themes brought up by the respondents. A similar coding exercise was also done for previous reports focusing on research needs, e.g., the HySafe 2022 Research Priorities workshop [2]. The different areas from the interviews and report were then described qualitatively in a chapter in the report.

Figure 1. Outline of method for research need mapping.

As shown in figure 1, the themes were then brought into a quantitative survey to allow for prioritization between areas. In this step, this description was also combined with results from ChatGPT-3.5 based on the prompt “*What research are needed for safety of [Hydrogen/Batteries/BESS]?*”. The survey was widely distributed with a request for the respondent to forward it to other people who might be interested, but the survey was not published on social media to prevent uncontrolled mass distribution.

Research needs – Hydrogen

There were nine major themes for research needs for hydrogen safety and hundreds of sub-themes. The main themes were;

1. *Gaseous hydrogen* – e.g. lean ignition, ground diffusion, DDT.
2. *Liquid hydrogen* – e.g. release and evaporation, auto-ignition, BLEVE.
3. *Material and storage methods* – e.g. composites, gaskets, and hydrides.
4. *Mitigation* – e.g. ventilation, detection, barriers
5. *Risk analysis* – e.g. failure frequencies, reliability of mitigation.
6. *Consequence models* – e.g. engineering model for DDT and round-robin validation
7. *Rescue service interventions* – e.g. leak detection and tactics.
8. *Applications* – e.g. blending, underground storage and pipelines.
9. *Non-technical* – e.g. safety culture and social acceptance.

Research needs – Batteries

Similar to hydrogen, a number of overarching themes for battery safety were identified;

1. *Thermal runaway* – e.g. propagation, modeling
2. *Battery technology* – e.g. solid state, aged batteries
3. *Gassing* – e.g. effect of initiation and chemistry
4. *Consequences* – e.g. fire and gas explosion
5. *Risk analysis* – e.g. statistics
6. *Mitigation* – e.g. ventilation, detection, suppression
7. *Rescue service interventions* – e.g. tactics, safety
8. *Explorative experiments* – e.g. full-scale tests, aged batteries
9. *Applications* – e.g. Battery swapping, ships
10. *End-of-life* – e.g. second life, recovery, recycling

Priorities

At the time of submission of this abstract, the survey for hydrogen research has just been sent out, and the survey on battery safety is still under development. Priorities for both research and non-research actors will be presented at the conference and, at that time, be available in the final report [1].

Conclusion

A number of research topics for battery and hydrogen safety has been identified through a series of interviews and document analysis and a second step regarding prioritization is currently ongoing.

This is expected to be useful for both researchers as they define future research projects as well as research programs being developed at funding agencies. It is also encouraged that the funding agencies fund literature reviews in identified areas to define the current state-of-the-art. This will show whether it is a question of summarizing and disseminating previously published research or if new empirical research is needed.

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Hydrogen safety

Explosion risks of hydrogen transport and storage infrastructure

Lucas Andersson, PhD-Student
Department of Structural and Fire
engineering
Luleå University of Technology
Luleå, Sweden
lucas.andersson@ltu.se

Michael Försth
Department of Structural and Fire
engineering
Luleå University of Technology and
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
Luleå, Sweden
michael.forsth@ltu.se

Joakim Sandström
Department of Structural and Fire
engineering
Luleå University of Technology
Luleå, Sweden
joakim.sandstrom@ltu.se

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Hydrogen, safety, explosions, dynamic loading, FSI,

Abstract

Awareness of global climate change is increasing. One consequence of this is that industrial expansions are taking place in Norrbotten in Sweden that will utilize vast quantities of hydrogen gas, e.g. for steel production with reduced environmental impact. Hydrogen-air mixtures are commonly highly reactive and are prone to rapid combustion. In cases when hydrogen-air mixtures deflagrate and in some cases transitions to a detonation, damage to structures and people can be significant magnitude.

Within the FINAST research project structural response from explosions have been studied. Initially simplified modelling which includes linking computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and finite element models (FEM) has been used. The results have demonstrated the possibility of studying the stresses and strains on a building following a hydrogen gas explosion. The study highlights important key factors that need to be addressed in the continuation of the research project.

Introduction

Awareness of global climate change is increasing in society and is more prioritized on the political agenda. One consequence of this is that hydrogen is used more frequently as an energy carrier and is expected to be used more in the coming decades [1].

An everyday example of hydrogen gas is that it is used in vehicles as fuel, but on a larger scale, industrial expansions are taking place in e.g. Norrbotten that will utilize hydrogen gas. The company Hybrit was created by Vattenfall, LKAB and SSAB to develop the steelmaking process to cut back on CO₂-emissions. One of the main sources of CO₂-emissions comes from the production of iron where traditional methods where coke and carbon dioxide are used for reduction of the iron ore. If hydrogen is used as a reducing agent instead of the carbon-based reduction agents, the CO₂-emissions is eliminated.

Hybrit has recently also shown that the process works [2]. The companies SSAB and H₂-Green Steel are expected to

adapt to usage of the hydrogen reduced iron in the steel making using the technology on an industrial scale to reduce dependence on fossil fuels and thus reduce CO₂-emissions.

Luleå University of Technology runs the project FINAST (Research and Innovation in Norrbotten for Advanced Green Steelmaking and Manufacturing) in collaboration with Swerim and SSAB. The project deals with issues related to the steel manufacturing process, but also overall logistics for the process and the infrastructure for transport and storage of the hydrogen needed.

One part of this project is safety issues related to the new infrastructure for transport and storage of hydrogen. What risks arise when constructing a pipeline through a community or industrial area, or when constructing a large-scale gas storage facility, when the energy carrier being transported is hydrogen instead of, e.g. natural gas?

Hydrogen gas explosive properties

Hydrogen is in many ways different in its properties in relation to other combustible gases. Properties that relate to safety are large flammability range, high flame velocity, low minimum activation energy etc. Hydrogen gas is the smallest molecule in nature, which creates leakage problems as it easily permeates through materials [3].

One of the issues is the consequences of leakage where combustible hydrogen-air mixtures can form. If a delayed ignition of these mixtures occurs it can deflagrate and in some scenarios the deflagration transitions into a detonation (DDT). In cases where a DDT occurs, damage to structures and people can increase significantly due to the large overpressures generated by detonations [4].

A deflagration can generally affect nearby people, but if a DDT occurs, there is a risk that nearby infrastructure or buildings could partially or completely collapse providing an indirect effect on people not in the vicinity of the explosion origin. In such a scenario, the consequences can increase drastically in terms of the expected number of fatalities, but also in terms of structural damage.

If deflagration of hydrogen-air mixtures occurs, but also more importantly in cases of DDT, it is of particular interest to gain fundamental understanding of the mechanisms related to the interaction between shock waves and infrastructure/buildings.

Method

Initially the project has studied simplified modelling of information exchange between different models as prestudy before looking into true Fluid Structure Interaction (FSI) modelling, which includes fully two-way coupling of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models and finite element method (FEM) models.

In this prestudy, modelling of the entire process from ignition and propagation of the shock wave from the explosion (CFD) to the dynamic loading of the structural elements (FEM), where results from the CFD-simulation are used as indata in the FEM-simulation.

In the CFD computer programme FLACS-CFD [5] a hydrogen-air stoichiometric gas cloud of longitudinal ellipsoid shape with a size of 4x2x2 meters (semiaxes) are used to mimic a partly momentum driven leakage is placed 8 meters from an 20x26x6 m large hexahedron. Ignition is arbitrarily placed 1 m above ground within the gas cloud. The surfaces of the building obstruction are divided into larger parts for pressure measurements which were placed in relation to the loading zones on the main frame of the structure.

In the FEM computer programme COMSOL Multiphysics [6] a beam-element based steel structure were set up to represent the main frame and horizontal and vertical bracing of the hexahedron set up in FLACS-CFD. Transient line loads on the main frame were used to mimic the dynamic loading from the shockwave. The line load recalculation was conducted in relation to the areas of the corresponding pressure zones in FLACS-CFD.

Results

The first models have successfully produced structural response from the explosion shock wave. The results have thereby demonstrated a possible way of studying the stresses and strains produced from the dynamic loading, see figure 1 below.

Figure 1 Structural response from the dynamic loads caused by the shockwave from the hydrogen gas explosion.

Even so, a range of simplifications are done, and more work is needed to evaluate these simplifications to justify if the quantified results hold any merit. One of the prominent simplifications is that the method does not provide two-way communication in each time step (FSI), e.g. the structural deflection and shockwave reflection interplay as the shock wave hits the building is not captured. The shockwave in in the CFD-simulation interacts with a perfectly stiff and rigid body will not be affected by the deflection that is later shown by the FEM-simulation.

This might be a valid assumption from some structures, such as thicker reinforced concrete walls with strong foundations where deflections can be minimal, but what about other building materials, such as steel or even timber, where deflections can be larger? There are theoretical indications that the impulse should be larger and the lower pressure peak, but what are the magnitudes?

Conclusions

The prestudy of information exchange between models as a method has shown important key factors that need to be addressed in the continuation of the research project and development of more complicated FSI-models.

Although not the all mechanisms of shockwave-structure interplay are not captured in the prestudy, the initial simulations have provided valuable insight into the shockwave-structure interaction phenomena.

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A holistic approach on the transition to fluorine free firefighting foams

Firefighting performance and PFAS decontamination

Sixten Dahlbom & Tove Mallin

*RISE Research Institute of Sweden, Division Safety and Transport, Fire and Safety Department, Box 857, 501 15, Borås, Sweden
sixten.dahlbom@ri.se*

Keywords: *Firefighting foam, Fluorine free, PFAS, Firefighting performance, PFAS decontamination*

Abstract

Health and environmental concerns about per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances, as well as upcoming stricter regulations on PFAS trigger the transition to fluorine free firefighting foams. In the transition it is important to consider firefighting performance of the replacement product as well as clean out of the existing firefighting equipment; PFAS rebound must be considered and thorough decontamination is required to avoid cross contamination. Eleven fluorine free firefighting foams have been evaluated. The impact of water quality, bubble size distribution and type of fuel was found to have a significant impact on the performance of the replacement foams. In the clean out, the impact of pH of the cleaning agent was found to have an effect on the extraction of specific PFAS species and a general trend of enhanced desorption at higher temperatures was observed.

Introduction

To extinguish large pool fires with flammable liquids, firefighting foam is the most common, or even the only practicable, agent to use [1]. During the 1960's addition of per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) to firefighting foams was discovered to drastically improve the firefighting performance of the foams, this marks the discovery of aqueous film forming foams (AFFFs) which were the prevalent type of foam used for several decades [2].

Owing to rising concerns regarding the environmental and health implications linked with PFAS, compounded by increasingly stringent regulatory protocols, there is a notable trend towards the adoption of fluorine free foams (FFFs). For example, perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), a prominent constituent of historically used firefighting foams, is classified as a reproductive toxicant and a suspected carcinogen [3]. Various PFAS compounds have exhibited adverse effects, encompassing reproductive and developmental anomalies, hepatic and renal dysfunction, immunological impacts, and tumorigenesis in studies with animals [4].

When transitioning from AFFFs (with PFAS) to FFFs (fluorine free), the objective is to maintain firefighting performance at an unaltered level to ensure the safety standards are upheld, but also to minimize investment expenses. A firefighting foam works by preventing fuel

vaporization, separating oxygen from the fuel and cooling the fuel surface and surroundings [5]. The firefighting performance of eleven PFAS-free firefighting foams was assessed across various fuel types (Jet A1, commercial heptane, and diesel) and water compositions (freshwater and synthetic seawater). Additionally, different foam generation techniques i.e., aspirated and compressed air foam (CAF), and application methods were scrutinized.

Another aspect to consider in the transition to FFFs is cross-contamination from existing firefighting equipment. This has been exemplified in previous work; after a dual flush with water, sampling conducted one year after the transition to an FFF revealed a PFAS concentration (post-TOP) of up to 1.6 g/l [6, 7]. In another study, 34 µg/l of PFAS22 was detected four months after a comprehensive cleanout. Research suggests that PFAS adsorbs onto surfaces of equipment, followed by diffusion into both macro and micro pores [8, 9]. This slow diffusion from pores during cleaning complicates the decontamination process, and the persistence of contamination over extended periods exacerbates the challenge, given the desired decontamination timeframe of hours to days. Moreover, PFAS can form bilayers or bilayer aggregates, such as micelles, further complicating decontamination efforts [10, 11].

Firefighting performance

The firefighting performance of eleven PFAS-free firefighting foams was assessed across various parameters including different fuels (Jet A1, commercial heptane, and diesel) and water types (freshwater and synthetic seawater). Additionally, diverse foam generation techniques and application methods were scrutinized, involving the generation of foams as aspirated foams or as compressed air foams (CAFs).

The results highlight that CAF exhibited superior performance in terms of extinction time and burn-back resistance compared to foam generated using an aspirated UNI 86 nozzle. Furthermore, the study revealed that the time required for fire knockdown decreased with decreasing foam viscosity. Despite the involvement of the entire fuel surface in the fire, the heat flux was found to be relatively small. It was observed that the performance of the evaluated foams varied depending on the type of fuel used, indicating a dependence on fuel type. Tests conducted using seawater indicated that the addition of salt to the foam solution generally prolonged the extinction time, although one firefighting foam exhibited a

shorter extinction time. Importantly, none of the eleven evaluated PFAS-free products outperformed the rest in all aspects. Instead, each product appeared to have different strengths, performing best in specific conditions such as with different types of fuel or water.

PFAS decontamination

To evaluate decontamination of firefighting equipment that has been exposed to PFAS containing firefighting foams, contaminated materials from different installations were sampled. In lab scale tests one commercially available decontamination product was compared to water, following the same test protocol. Further, seven different agents were evaluated according to another protocol. A general trend of enhanced desorption at higher temperatures was observed. Additionally, the pH of the cleaning agent was found to have a noticeable effect on the extraction of specific PFAS species, highlighting the significance of chemical environment in the extraction process. Investigation into PFAS rebound over a period of up to 157 days revealed a gradual increase in PFAS₂₂ levels, indicating a prolonged desorption mechanism. Interestingly, PFAS with shorter carbon chains (C4–C6) demonstrated higher desorption efficiency compared to longer congeners, suggesting a chain-length-dependent decontamination capability. A comparative analysis between a commercially available cleaning product, involving multiple washing and flushing steps, and a water-only treatment regimen emphasized the potential effectiveness of the former.

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The effects of leakage for gas-fire suppression systems

Xiaoqin Hu

Faculty of Engineering and Sciences, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL)

Haugesund 5528, Norway

Xiaoqin.Hu@hvl.no

Keywords:

Gas fire suppression, Inert gas agent, Leakage, Opening, extended discharge.

Abstract

Leakage might cause a large uncertainty for gas-fire suppression systems. This study first summarized our previous study on leakage effects and the method to compensate the leakage by extending gas discharge. Then numerical simulations were conducted to investigate the leakage effects and evaluate the extended discharge method in an apartment.

Introduction

Compared with water-based fire suppression systems, gas-based systems are advantageous for extinguishing deep-rooted smoldering fires or corner fires or fires in hidden areas where water from sprinkler systems cannot easily reach. Inert gas-based systems achieve fire suppression by lowering the ambient oxygen concentration below the threshold necessary for the combustion process. The threshold level is normally in a range from 12 % to 15 % for diffusion flames according to the experiments [1].

Gas-fire suppression systems are normally designed for enclosures that are sealed, without significant leaks. However, possible un-closable openings, e.g. conveyor belts penetrating an enclosure wall, opening doors, cracks, and ventilation systems, are present in protected enclosures. Leakage might cause a large uncertainty. Under-discharge of inert gas agent fails to extinguish fires while over-discharge leads to hypoxia effects in occupied areas. Therefore, it is crucial to achieve and maintain a design oxygen concentration in the protected enclosures where leakage presents.

Effects of leakage

The inert gas agent discharged into an enclosure will result in a pressure increase. As the pressure in the enclosure is positive relative to ambient throughout the discharge, the agent-air mixture leaks from the enclosure through openings or cracks. If small openings/cracks are present or ventilation systems exhaust the agent-air mixture only, the agent-air mixture is pressed out. The fresh air flowing into the enclosure could be neglected during discharge period. In our

previous study [2-3], the oxygen mass fraction at time t can be calculated as:

$$Y_{O_2}(t) = Y_{O_2}^0 e^{-\int_0^t \frac{\dot{m}_i}{m} d\xi} \quad (1)$$

where $Y_{O_2}^0$ is the mass fraction of oxygen initially in the enclosure, e.g., $Y_{O_2}^0 = 0.23$ for fresh air. \dot{m}_i (kg/s) is the discharge rate of inert gas and m (kg) is the total mass of mixture in the enclosure. If the exit flow rate of mixture equals the discharge flow rate, Eq. 1 matches the expression which is widely used in gas-based systems [4].

If openings allow the heavier agent-air mixture to flow out and the lighter outside air to flow in during discharge period, Eq. 1 is not valid anymore. According to the tests conducted in an 80 m³ compartment with one door open (0.78 m width) [5], the oxygen concentration decreased to around the design level at the end of the discharge except the locations which were close to the open door. When the discharge stopped, the oxygen concentration increased slowly and was over 15% in 1-2 minutes at most locations. If the opening was extremely large (e.g. two opposite opening doors), it failed to dilute the oxygen concentration to the design level, which means gas-fire suppression systems are not suitable in these enclosures.

Compensation for leakage

Even the oxygen concentration can reach the design level at the end of the discharge if the opening size is not very large, it faces a challenge that fire events might resurge once the oxygen concentration increases over the extinction range in the post-discharge time. To prevent a resurgence of fire events, the design oxygen level should be maintained for a sufficient time, which is known as hold time. Normally the hold time should be now less than 10 minutes [6].

To maintain the oxygen level, a typical way is to extend discharge time. Some specific release valve can be used to create a constant rate of gas supply for the additional gas cylinders [7]. To compensate the leakage of agent-air mixture, our study [5] suggests extending the discharge at a rate of:

$$\dot{m}_i = \frac{2}{3} C_d W \rho_a \left(\frac{Y_{O_2}^0}{Y_{O_2}^*} - 1 \right) \sqrt{\frac{2g(\rho_{mix} - \rho_a)}{\rho_a}} h_u^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where W and H are the width and height of the opening. ρ_a and ρ_{mix} are the densities of air and agent-air mixture in the enclosure. $Y_{O_2}^*$ is the design oxygen mass fraction. C_d is flow

coefficient. h_u is the height of the inflow of fresh air, which can be calculated as:

$$h_u = \frac{H}{1 + \left(\frac{y_{O_2}^0}{y_{O_2}^*} \sqrt{\frac{\rho_a}{\rho_{mix}}} \right)^2} \quad (3)$$

Numerical investigation and results discussion

A series simulations were carried out to investigate the leakage effect in an apartment. Figure 1 shows an apartment which was designed for the people who are struggling with drug abuse and mental disorders in Karmøy municipality in Norway [8]. A project started to investigate if the gas-based fire suppression systems using IG-541 as agent could be implemented in these apartments. The apartment was created numerically using Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) in this study. 95% of two cylinders of inert gas agent IG541 (33.14kg/cylinder) were discharged into the apartment in 180 s. According to the design tool IMT [9], the oxygen concentrations reached 12% at 120 s if no significant leakage occurred. The properties of walls and the mesh solution used in this study are similar to the study in [4]. Three simulations were carried out with door A closed, opened with a width of 0.15cm and fully open (0.8 m) separately.

Figure 1. An apartment created by FDS.

Figure 2 gives the average oxygen mass fraction predicted from the three simulations. It shows that small openings in windows affected the oxygen level slightly while the door opening (at floor level) caused significant leakage especially in post-discharge time. The oxygen mass fraction calculated using Eq. 1 is very close to the predictions. This figure illustrates that the leakage effect is more obvious in the post-discharge time than in discharge time.

Figure 2. Average O_2 mass fraction in the apartment.

To compensate for the leakage, the discharge was extended from 150 s to 750 s at a rate of 0.302 kg/s (calculated from Eq. 2) when door A was fully open. Figure 3 gives the

predicted oxygen concentration at 0.2m, 1.0m and 1.8m above the floor at window E. Before the start of extended discharge (150 s), it had failed to maintain the design oxygen level for about 60 s since the discharge rate was very low in this period. When the extended discharge started, the oxygen fraction decreased slightly first, then it became approximate constant in the rest of the extended discharge time. The oxygen fraction varied between 10.7% and 13.6 % along the height because the inert gas agent was a little heavier than fresh air.

Figure 3. Oxygen concentration at window E when door A was open, and the discharge was extended.

Conclusion

The leakage effect during discharge period is not significant if the opening size at floor level is not very big but becomes clearer in the post-discharge period. The leakage can be compensated by extending the discharge to maintain the oxygen level. Further work is needed to find a more precise relation between oxygen concentration and opening size.

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Use of water mist system for at-risk groups

Sondre Myklatun
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL),
Haugesund, Norway
SondreMyklatun@outlook.com

Amalie Thorsen
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL),
Haugesund, Norway
Amtho@haugnett.no

Maria Birkeland Heitmann
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL),
Haugesund, Norway
Maria.heitmann@icloud.com

Arjen Kraaijeveld
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL),
Haugesund, Norway
Arjen.Kraaijeveld@hvl.no

Keywords: *Water mist systems, At-risk group, Fire suppression, drugs and psychiatry, pilot housing*

Abstract

In Karmøy municipality, there is an ongoing construction project to build pilot homes for individuals within the field of drug abuse and mental disorder (ROP). The project is partly financed by the Norwegian Research Council [1].

Three different small, detached homes will be finished in October 2024. One of the homes will be equipped with a water mist system and constructed using solid timber (CLT). This particular home will be closely monitored throughout our project.

HVL, through the research project «Builder», has contributed to this project by identifying innovative fire safety solutions [2]. The project is currently in the construction phase. Parts of the project have previously been presented at the Nordic Fire and Safety days [3].

The bachelor project, finished in June 2024, will focus on comparing water mist systems against traditional residential sprinklers. Exploring the advantages and disadvantages of both options is essential. To explore the differences, the group will design a sprinkler system and water mist system for the specific building in detail.

Figure 1. “Architectural design by Snohetta, where the choice fell on solid wood to test a more robust construction than stud walls” [4]

Problem statement

Individuals struggling with drug abuse and psychiatric issues face more problems and challenges than the general population [5]. A significant issue within this community is vandalism to both residences and fire suppression systems. It often happens that the resident deliberately sets their house on fire, smokes indoors, or dismantles the systems designed for extinguishing fires. Therefore, there is a high probability of fire incidents. It is crucial to minimize downtime and damage to the building due to difficulties in providing alternative housing for the residents.

The building has been classified as hazard class 4, and according to regulations (TEK) there is no requirement for an automatic fire suppression system [5]. In these types of residences, individuals often have a hoarding behavior and a tendency to obstruct safety equipment, like portable extinguishers. Portable fire extinguishers are not considered a viable solution. Therefore, a low-pressure water mist system has been chosen as an innovative solution to improve the safety level and avoid severe damage on the building, and protect the resident.

Method

The method used to address this issue is a literature review. It will examine the available information and documentation on low-pressure water mist systems, identify any knowledge gaps, and explore how the new standard NS-EN 14972 operates in practice. Water mist systems are increasingly being installed in the residential market, even though the testing protocol specifically designed for residential use, has not yet been released [6].

An installation based upon water mist and residential sprinkling will be engineered in detail. Afterwards these systems will be compared.

The focus will be on the differences between the systems themselves, including piping networks, nozzles, and how their functionalities are adapted to sloped roofs. What are the actual price differences between the systems for the exact same residence and use? Additionally, what are the environmental differences in the production of the components, and how long can one expect a system to last?

Expected results

Although the building will not be finished in June, the detailed engineering will be completed by then. Based on the knowledge we have accumulated so far; it is expected that a water mist system will be a good solution for this type of building. Factors that contribute to this assumption are the

same degree of difficulty during detailed engineering as sprinkler system, possible a lower total cost due to longer life of the system, lower water volume and the fact that water mist might give a more sustainable solution. These preliminary conclusions are based on literature study, articles and conversations with professionals in the field so far.

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Optimization of active fire protection systems in Road Tunnels: focusing on interaction between water mist and ventilation

Marta Galuppi
Department of Civil, Building
and Environmental Engineering
Sapienza University
Rome, Italy
Marta.galuppi@uniroma1.it

Lars Schiøtt Sørensen
Department of Civil and
Mechanical Engineering
DTU
Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
lssso@dtu.dk

Bjarne P. Husted
Department of Civil and
Mechanical Engineering
DTU
Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
bphu@dtu.dk

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Fire suppression; water mist system; ventilation design; fire dynamics; road tunnel safety.

Abstract

The development of fire protection technologies in underground structures is encouraged by law requirements concerning safety in road tunnels, European Directive 2004/54 [1]. The directive provides for exemptions from mandatory safety requirements when innovative systems are adopted which can guarantee an equivalent or reduced level of risk.

The suitable tool for verifying the performance of safety systems is indicated in quantitative risk analysis, which allows for determining the survivability of users belonging to a given design solution.

The goal is to determine the best way to optimize the use of safety systems to ensure the safety of human life and the structural integrity of the tunnel. Therefore, further research in this direction is needed to provide a clear understanding of individual tunnel models that are reproducible and applicable to existing and future tunnels.

It is essential to underscore the significance of comparing full-scale tests with numerical solutions and subsequently developing a Fire Dynamics Simulation (FDS) model. Full-scale tests provide tangible, real-world data that offer a valuable benchmark for evaluating the accuracy and reliability of computational simulations.

By comparing the outcomes of full-scale tests with numerical solutions, researchers and engineers can validate the predictive capabilities of their simulation models. This process not only enhances confidence in the numerical approach but also identifies potential areas for improvement or calibration.

Safety Systems interaction in Large Tunnel Fires

The creation of an FDS model is used as a powerful tool for simulating fire scenarios in a controlled virtual environment. This computational approach allows for a detailed analysis of complex fire dynamics, including heat transfer, smoke

movement, and the interaction with structural elements.

Developing an FDS model that closely aligns with observed data from full-scale tests ensures that the simulation accurately represents the physical phenomena. In essence, the synergy between full-scale tests and numerical solutions by FDS-modelling, makes a robust framework for advancing fire safety research and engineering practices. This iterative process of validation and refinement contributes to the development of more accurate and reliable fire safety strategies, ultimately fostering safer environments and infrastructure.

The selection and design of a fire suppression system in a tunnel system should be carried out by experienced designers, respecting, and fully applying the available Technical Standards adopted as references.

Hence, those responsible for designing fire-suppression systems in road tunnels should consider the impact of ventilation fans. This consideration extends beyond their role in smoke purging to encompass potential delays in fire suppression, which could worsen overall losses. Additionally, when determining the water-storage capacity, designers must factor in the increased water quantity needed for effective fire suppression when ventilation fans are integrated [2]. Lastly, in establishing the location of the fire-suppression zone, designers should account for the movement of the fire towards the air inlet once ventilation fans are activated.

Testing a fire suppression system should be conducted in accordance with defined Test Protocols, allowing the verification of the attributed performance. The maintenance of a fire suppression system should be scheduled and carried out to ensure the long-term preservation of its performance. The choice of using water mist, as said before is primarily driven by its environmental friendliness, minimal water consumption, and the ability to customize its performance based on specific requirements.

Safety systems play a crucial role in handling fire incidents, aiming to reduce the intensity of the fire and facilitating the evacuation of individuals. Following past incidents, investigations are imperative to identify the root

causes, restore regular traffic flow, and evaluate the extent of fire damage to the structure [3].

Large-scale fires in a confined environment such as a tunnel, where thermo-fluid-dynamic conditions are non-standard, are challenging to model using a simulator like the fire dynamic simulator (FDS) [4].

Accordingly, designers of fire-suppression systems for road tunnels should consider the effect of ventilation fans, not only in terms of smoke purging but also the delay they might cause in suppressing the fire, which can exacerbate the losses. Moreover, when deciding the water-storage volume, the increase in the amount of water required to suppress fire must also be considered if ventilation fans are incorporated [5]. Finally, when determining the location of the fire-suppression zone, designers must consider the movement of the fire toward the air inlet after the ventilation fans are switched on.

Study

A study on the numerical modelling of performances using FDS was conducted.

A fire with a peak thermal power of 250 MW was modelled with a fire load consisting of wood pallets and plastic and including the safety systems. Two cases were compared:

- A free burn (only with longitudinal ventilation)
- A low-pressure water mist was installed

Replicating real-world conditions on a scale that allows for a model adjustable in the future represents a significant challenge. This is crucial to avoid the need for reproducing a real-scale test, which is burdensome both economically and in terms of the tunnel infrastructure used.

Tunnel geometry has been recreated, consisting of a length of 600 meters and a height of 5 meters, resulting in a total free cross-sectional area of approximately 45 m². The Heat Release rate registered in the experimental situation was reproduced in the FDS environment. The comparable result in Figure 1 shows a significant reduction in heat release rate when water mist is applied

Figure 1. Comparison of Heat Release Rate over time in FDS model with the effect of a water mist system on the total heat release rate.

The challenge is the significance of studying temperature evolution during a fire cannot be overstated. Such analysis is pivotal for comprehending the severity of the fire and the thermal impact on both the structure and occupants involved. Additionally, temperatures play a crucial role in investigating

heat flux, contributing to advancements in fire safety and prevention strategies. Understanding the temperature trends during a fire is crucial for various reasons. Temperature is a key indicator of fire severity, aiding in the assessment of potential structural damage and the effectiveness of firefighting measures. A comparison between temperatures is offered in figure 2: the free burn temperature peak reaches over 1000 °C 30 meters downstream of the fire instead of the case with the suppression with water mist, the maximum temperature registered is about 250°C. Temperatures compared between free burn in simulated environment and full scale test registered a gap difference of 400 °C. Simulation results provide a qualitative assessment of the potential impact of employing water mist. However, noteworthy quantitative variations exist between the simulated setting and the actual fire test conducted.

Figure 2. Comparison of Temperature trend over time in the FDS model with the effect of a water mist system on the total heat release rate.

Conclusions

Monitoring temperature patterns provides valuable insights into the fire's behaviour, helping emergency responders anticipate its progression and take timely actions. Additionally, temperature data plays a vital role in validating and refining fire models, contributing to advancements in fire safety and prevention strategies.

Results shows that with the use of water mist in a large fire the Total Heat Release rate is reduced consistently as the overall temperatures over time.

Moreover, this approach enables a better comprehension of the constraints of numerical modeling, which may not always realistically mirror the results obtained on a real scale.

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Tunnel fire exercise in the Northern Link

Lessons learned from planning and conducting a large scale exercise using a real fire

Björn Hedskog
Brandskyddslaget
Stockholm, Sweden
bjorn.hedskog@bsl.se

Emil Persson
Brandskyddslaget
Stockholm, Sweden

Bo Wahlström
Brandskyddslaget
Stockholm, Sweden

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Abstract

A full-scale exercise took place in the Northern Link tunnel network in Stockholm in September 2022. The exercise scenario was dynamic and consisted initially of a traffic incident and was later escalated to involve a real fire in one of the cars involved in the accident. Emergency services taking part in the exercise included the fire brigade, police, the local road assistance unit and tunnel operators.

The outcome from the exercise indicates that there is a great need for future exercises in tunnel environments. The exercise showed that practicing organizations generally have low orientation skills within the tunnel network, the communication and coordination among the organizations was a challenge and improvement can be made regarding the use of the firefighting systems, i.e. ventilation and the fixed firefighting system (FFFS).

Introduction

According to Swedish legislation, full scale tunnel exercises should be conducted at a minimum once every fourth year. With this background, a full-scale exercise was planned and carried out in the Northern Link tunnel network in Stockholm in September 2022.

The Northern Link consists of a road tunnel network with a combined total length of 13 kilometers. The longest tunnel is around 4 kilometers. The network consists of two main tunnels and several shorter tunnels connecting to the main tunnels (figure 1.). The tunnel network is fitted with longitudinal ventilation, CCTV and a fixed fire-fighting system (FFFS). The longitudinal ventilation system consists of jet fans and the FFFS consist of a deluge system with each deluge zone covering 50 meters tunnel length. The Northern Link is provided with emergency exits, i.e., cross passages, every 150 meters.

In accordance with current rescue plans for an incident involving fire, emergency services are not to approach the fire through the incident bore. Instead, the fire location is supposed to be reached through cross-passages between the tunnels.

Since the activation of the FFFS is part of the existing response plan in case of a fire, all systems within the tunnel were available and functioning during the exercise.

Figure 1. Overview of the Northern Link Tunnel Network.

Participating organizations

Since it is very important that the Northern Link tunnel system is always in operation, emergency services rarely get to exercise within such a complex environment. It was therefore important to involve all possible emergency services to be part of the exercise. During the exercise the following organizations participated, the ambulance services, the fire brigade, the police, the local road assistance unit, and the tunnel operators.

Aim of exercise

Except for meeting the legal requirement of recurring full-scale exercises, the aim of the exercise was to confirm that emergency services were able to carry out emergency operations within the tunnel. Therefore, the focus was to conduct a testing, and at the same time a learning, exercise regarding:

- Communication, coordination and cooperation between different emergency services.
- Processes and safety systems being used in the tunnel network including the FFFS.

Each participating organization also developed their own specific objectives to complement and specify the above mentioned.

The planning

Due to the complexity of the exercise the planning started in 2021, close to one year before the exercise was conducted. There was an exercise management group which consisted of representatives from the various organizations that were supposed to participate in the exercise. This group was coordinated by the authors of this article. Further there was a

steering group consisted of appointed representatives from the Swedish Transport Administration.

During the planning phase the specific exercise scenario was developed and design so that it would meet the overall aim as well as the specific objectives from the participating organizations. In addition to developing the exercise scenario the work done by management group included site visits, management tabletop exercise as well as development of guiding and steering documents and plans.

Exercise scenario

To make the scenario as realistic as possible it was constructed as an escalating and dynamic scenario using a real fire (figure 2.). The initial event was a traffic accident without fire, involving three passenger cars. One of these three cars was set-up so that a fire could be arranged some time into the exercise. Fire incidents in tunnels have shown that despite being instructed not to, several drivers pass a vehicle on fire. Hence, at a later stage the extent of the exercise increased further when two vehicles which had passed the initial site of the accident crashed downstream due to limited visibility.

Figure 2. Fire location before activation of FFFS. ©Brandskyddslaget

The purpose of planning the scenario so that it initially only consisted of a traffic accident was to let all organizations start acting according to the SOP's for traffic accident, allowing different rescue teams to approach the incident in the affected tunnel bore. When the first responders were on their way to the accident the command center received additional information about fire in one vehicle making it necessary to change strategy and SOP's, i.e. to approach the accident from the unaffected tunnel bore.

The escalating scenario, leading to the need of changing the strategy from a traffic accident to a tunnel fire, was expected to highlight potential issues regarding efficient communication among the emergency services. In addition, the situation would give the emergency services an opportunity to practice their knowledge of the tunnel network including the layout of the cross passages.

The fire was arranged by using an already burned-out passenger car. Wooden pallets were placed within the car, allowing for the fire to be shielded. Despite the fire being shielded, the FFFS was expected to be operating sufficiently, leading to the fire decaying. Since the number of electric vehicles is steadily increasing, and there is a risk of re-ignition in electric vehicles due to the battery configuration, the fire was simulated in a such a vehicle. Re-ignition of the vehicle

was arranged after the first attempt from the fire brigade to extinguish the fire.

This set-up gave the emergency personnel an opportunity to practice in conditions that mimic real life as closely as possible. Responsible emergency personnel had to practice leading and operating during a full-scale incident. Further, the set-up with a real fire gave the tunnel owner an insight regarding the efficiency of the FFFS and visualized the difference within the tunnel environment with and without an operating FFFS.

Outcome and evaluation

The execution of the exercise was considered to fulfil the overall purpose and the objectives. Some main conclusions from the performed evaluations include:

- Full-scale exercises of this size are appreciated.
- Units at the outer command post found it challenging to obtain an overall picture of the situation inside the tunnel.
- Orientability in the tunnel is generally low.
- It was difficult for the rescue personnel to understand that the car on fire was an electric vehicle. This affected the actions by the rescue units.
- The FFFS was able to lower the size of the flames and decrease the temperature of the smoke but as expected, not able to fully extinguish the shielded car fire.
- As expected, once the ventilation system was running, even not at full capacity, no back layering was visualized.

Lessons learned

Some of the generic lessons learned from planning and conducting this specific exercise are:

- Establish a management group with the right competence and skills in the very beginning of the planning process.
- Determine each practicing organization's objectives early.
- Discuss and agree on the exercise scenario in the very beginning of the planning process.
- Determine what resources different organizations will provide.
- To the greatest extent possible, allow practicing units to act with as little interference as possible from exercise management.
- In advance of a full-scale exercises, launch smaller drills and/or tabletop exercises to practice specific parts of a rescue operation.

Some of the more specific lessons learned from this exercise are:

- There is a need for clarifying responsibilities of recognition and research regarding type of vehicles involved in accidents and fires.
- Orientation skills need to be practiced continuously.
- There is need to collaboratively continue to practice the use of FFFS and ventilation during a fire.

TUSC handbook for fire safe tunnelling work

Jonatan Gehandler
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
Borås, Sweden
jonatan.gehandler@ri.se

Keywords: health and safety, fire safety, tunnel, underground, work.

Abstract

In Sweden, several tunnelling projects are underway. In several of these, shortcomings regarding fire protection during the construction phase have been identified. The basis is that Swedish law applies, where fire protection is regulated in several legislations and regulations. Despite this, both owners and contractors may experience uncertainty about what a reasonable level of preventive fire protection is. One reason is that the stipulated requirements sometimes are vague and open for different interpretations. There is further a value in exchanging experiences with other owners in the area. At present, experience is often exchanged sporadically through the consultants who have assignments for the various owners.

Therefore, a project was launched within the Tunnel Underground and Safety Center (TUSC) aimed to create a handbook to support both the owner and the contractor regarding fire protection during the construction period for Swedish tunnels and underground facilities. The project builds on previous research in the area, e.g., Ingason, Lönnemark, Frantzieh, and Kumm [1] and Bengtson, Dittmer, Rohlén, and Östman [2], as well as similar handbooks, e.g., GRAMKO [3] for fire safe mining and Brandskyddsöreningen [4] for fire safe workplaces above ground.

Figure 1 Tunnel drilling, blasting and excavation phase (RISE).

Work as done

The work described herein is based on the concept “work as imagined (WAI) versus work as done (WAD)”. This is a concept developed within in the Human Factors-field, stating that how work is described in theory (imagined) differs from how it actually works in practice (WAD) [5]. To better understand the challenges of work as done, two workshops were carried out, with the aim to identify risks and challenges that owners, contractors and rescue services have experienced in reality. Another purpose with the workshops was to gather good examples of handling these risks and challenges. Two workshops were conducted, depending on the construction phase:

1. Design and Procurement phase
2. Construction phase (such as excavation, tunnelling, and installation)

According to terminology from the Human Factors-field the first phase is the “blunt end” and the second phase is the “sharp end”. The preconditions for safety in practice (i.e., sharp end) are affected by decisions and actions made by actors at the blunt end (Cook & Woods, 2018), or stated in this context, decisions and actions made in the design and procurement phase (blunt end) affect the possibilities to achieve a fire safe working place during construction (sharp end).

A user group was identified for each of the two phases. In addition, rescue service planners were invited to both groups. The group size varied between 6 and 8 excluding the two authors who facilitated the workshops.

Tunnel construction phases

The first workshop task was to identify important phases during tunnel construction work that alter the risk picture.

Important such risk-changing phases are:

- A preparation phase before production begins where the organisation is created. Sub-contractors are being procured, who may have different safety-cultures and diverging ways of working with health and safety.
- A pre-cut phase above ground. The radio used at the beginning by the above ground working team might not work with the (often different) radio system that is being used later underground.
- When you go from being above ground to being below ground with rock above your head. This phase may fall between the cracks in the sense that the risk-thinking needs to go from above ground to below ground with different organisations being responsible for the two different working cultures.

- When the work tunnel length creates problems for rescue service intervention and workers evacuation. As there will only be one way for evacuation there is a need for a rescue chamber, see Figure 2.
- When a breakthrough is made such that two independent evacuation routes is achieved.
- When the tunnel excavation is completed, and the project enters the installation phase. Building products may increase the fire risk and different organisations will now be working in the tunnel system.

Another important issue concern one of the key fire sources during the initial stages, vehicles, and whether they can park safely in the workplace and whether trucks can turn around so that they do not have to reverse into the tunnel.

In addition, it was argued that the rescue service must be included early in the project during the planning and design phase. It is their capability that sets the boundary limits for fire safety measures and strategies used during the construction phase. At the same time, standard equipment that all rescue services use should be specified from the start, without any need to re-invent solutions for each tunnel project.

One learning, perhaps in particular for the authors, is that there is no definite point in time when procurement ends. Procurement continues throughout the project when more information about the actual design is learned, or systems are added, or changes are being made to the original design. The construction phase has a distinct starting time after documents have been signed and a start meeting has been held, however, it can be unclear when construction becomes underground work.

Example risks and challenges

Both workshops identified common risks and example solutions. One of these concerns communication. Radio communication systems seem to be a surprisingly difficult and complex issue. During the initial stages the above-ground-workforce have their own radio system that work up to 50 m inside the tunnel. The radio that is next used by the tunneling entrepreneurs might not communicate with this initial system. Furthermore, due to high noise levels alarm systems might not be heard, which could be solved by an integrated system where the alarms is integrated into the radio. In addition, the positioning system could be connected with the radio (reduce the risks that tags are left inside the tunnels in e.g., jackets). In addition, radio systems (and fire extinguishing systems) may be required by the rescue service.

A comment from the workshops was that the latest risk analysis does not always match the risks corresponding to the current production phase. Continuous work is needed within risk management and a challenge for the entrepreneur is to ensure that the risk analysis is updated as the tunnel construction evolves. In addition, a comment from the workshop was that it is sometimes unclear how additional risks should be handled with regards to the contract. What is the financial agreement regarding the management of new risks? To keep the fire risk management work relevant and of a good quality also requires a sufficient level of fire protection knowledge on behalf of the entrepreneur.

Figure 2 Unprotected membrane and wooden planks (Photo: Jens Årlebrant).

Another issue that was debated at the workshops, concerns the use of plastic membrane. The function of plastic membrane in tunnel constructions is to divert water from the tunnel. Due to several functional requirements, including a lifetime of 120 years, the membranes on the market today are fire rated with Euroclass E according to EN13501-1. The Swedish Transport Administration further test that the membrane is self-extinguished if lighted by a small candle flame. However, during tunnel production, the membrane is mounted in long tunnel sections before it is sprayed (and hence protected from fire) with shotcrete. Considering that for example wood is a Euroclass D material, a larger fire initiator, e.g., a vehicle, could result in a very large tunnel fire that only is limited by the availability of oxygen. Thus, several fire professionals are arguing that this is a substantial fire risk that needs to be treated, for example through limiting the allowable length of unprotected membrane. From a tunnel production point-of-view it is argued that it is impractical to put up membrane and apply shotcrete simultaneously.

TUSC handbook

A handbook has been developed [7] that should assist both owners and contractors with these and other issues concerning fire protection during tunneling work. The aim of the handbook is not foremost to answer these questions, but to highlight challenges and relevant knowledge in order to form a common discussion basis for the actors.

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Façades with living plants or solar cells

Fire safety of ventilated façades

Reidar Stølen
Norwegian University of Science and
Technology (NTNU) and RISE Fire
Research, Trondheim, Norway
reidar.stolen@ntnu.no,
reidar.stolen@risefr.no

Janne Siren Fjærestad
RISE Fire Research
Trondheim, Norway
janne.siren.fjarestad@risefr.no

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Introduction

The rapid development of new façade constructions includes vertical greenery systems (VGS) and photovoltaic (PV) installations. These systems share some of the same challenges related to fire safety in building façades when it comes to ventilated cavities and combustible materials. Combustible materials in combination with ventilated cavities represent a potential for rapid fire spread in modern façades [1,2].

Many different design selections need to be made when installing such complex systems on or in building façades related to architectural, technical, and functional requirements. Some of these selections will also influence the fire safety of the building and can make the difference between a catastrophic fire, like the Grenfell fire [3], or a small and localized fire. An ongoing project at RISE Fire Research, funded by the Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (DSB) and the Norwegian Building Authority (DiBK), will be studying these systems during 2024 and aim to shed light on which parameters should be considered in order to build façades with living plants or PV installations without compromising the fire safety of the building.

Vertical greenery systems (VGS)

VGS can be divided into green façades (GF), where the plants are planted in the ground and climb on a supporting structure on the façade and living walls (LW), where the plants are growing in a substrate in a structure on the façade, and can include combustible plastics and growing media in addition to the plants [4]. Fire testing of façades with living plants is challenging, as a number of parameters, like plant and growing media moisture content and plant mass and growth stage, may result in completely different fire development [5].

From a Nordic perspective, the selection of plants needs to be made with respect to the local harsh winter conditions and may eliminate many of the plants used in living walls in warmer climates. Automatic watering systems may also have to be shut off during cold winter months to prevent ice

formation. This may influence the reaction to fire properties of the façade in different ways than similar systems installed in warmer climates.

Photovoltaic (PV) installations

PV installations can be divided into building attached photovoltaics (BAPV), where the PV modules are installed on the outside of a complete building envelope and building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV), where the PV modules are used as a functional part of the building envelope [6]. PV installations usually contain approximately 14 % combustible plastic materials [7,8]. Despite this relatively low amount of combustible materials, PV installations on façades can cause self-sustained flame propagation in ventilated cavities [9].

PV modules are commonly made with aluminium frames and glass fronts with either plastic or glass on the backside [10]. The majority of BIPV modules on the market are only listed to comply with the standard IEC 61730, which does not include any fire testing relevant to building applications and leave it to the installers to make sure they comply with local building codes [11]. Still, national regulations and standards do not yet including the relevant measures needed to mitigate the hazards specific to PV installations [12].

Planned experimental study

A review of relevant systems for VGS and PV installations for use in Nordic countries will provide the basis for an experimental study of some of the most critical parameters related to fire safety of façades. Reaction to fire properties of the materials used in the construction, ventilation conditions in the cavity, different types of growing media and plants, and PV modules with or without glass on the back.

Figure 1: Sketch of planned experimental setup with medium-scale façades with vertical greenery systems (left) and PV installations (right)

The experiments are planned to be made during the spring of 2024 in a medium scale, approximately 1 x 2 m (w x h), to be able to investigate enough parameters with several repetitions. Parallel panels with a gas burner as an ignition source are suggested to simulate the building envelope, ventilated cavity and attached façade system with plants or PV modules. A sketch of the planned experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. The thermal exposure and conduction of heat into the wall construction can be measured and will provide a relevant measure of the required fire resistance needed to prevent the fire from spreading into the building. Vertical fire spread rates and burnout times will be observed and measured to quantify how fast the fire would be expected to spread up the façade of a building. Radiative heat transfer will also be measured with plate thermocouples or heat flux meters at a relevant distance from the building to compare the risk of fire spread to adjacent buildings.

The results of the study will hopefully be able to illustrate how different design choices will influence important aspects of fire safety in facades with living plants or PV modules and can give important input to fire safety engineers who are responsible for the fire safety design of buildings with such facades. Further development of building regulations and testing standards will also benefit from knowledge on which parameters are most important for the fire safety of these modern façades.

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Fire safety of Building integrated Photovoltaics in facade

Comparing a building integrated PV facade system with a “normal” facade system through fire test.

Karina N. Pedersen
Western Norway University
of Applied Science (HVL)
Haugesund, Norway
karina-nistov@hotmail.com

Anniken L. Sagli
Western Norway
University of Applied
Science (HVL)
Haugesund, Norway

Agnes A. Slotvik
Western Norway
University of Applied
Science (HVL)
Haugesund, Norway

Einar A. Kolstad
Western Norway
University of Applied
Science (HVL)
Haugesund, Norway

Keywords: *BIPV, Cavities, Facade System, Energy Efficient Buildings*

Abstract

This research is a bachelor’s thesis focusing on an experiment involving a facade wall. The objective of the thesis is to investigate whether there is a difference in the behaviour of fire spread between a regular facade wall and a facade wall with Building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV). The research will contain complementary theory along with earlier studies to provide knowledge for the experiment.

Introduction

The demand for sustainable solutions has significantly increased in terms of electricity supply. With an increasing focus on sustainability and renewable energy, it is expected that BIPV will play a larger role in future building designs. BIPV are currently not widespread, but there seems to be a growing trend. Several projects, such as the ZEB Laboratory in Trondheim and Sofienberg School in Oslo, have adopted this technology. This indicates a positive development in the use of PV integration in buildings.

Our bachelor’s thesis investigates the increased fire risk associated with integrated PV, also known as solar panels, in facade.

BIPV offer architectural advantages and replace building materials while serving as energy sources [1]. Mounting PV vertically on facade avoids snow-related issues and optimizes the utilization of solar energy to make the most of solar energy and architectural design while addressing specific regional challenges.

In northern regions, the sun is lower in the sky. Therefore, facades in these areas will be a better alternative to attached solar panel, compared to on roofs. The climate up north also has advantages for PVs. Because of the cooler weather the efficiency of the solar panels is higher, and there is a lower risk of overheating [2].

However, despite the benefits, this bachelor work focuses on investigating the increased fire risk associated with integrated PV in facades. This research is conducted in collaboration with Rambøll and the Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, aiming to compare the fire safety of facades with integrated PV against regular facade.

Problem statement

PV installations are considered building installations and consequently pose a certain fire risk. The PV installations themselves will not be able to contribute to the actual fire development due to the materials but may influence fire spread. The thesis aims to investigate whether there are differences in the fire behaviour behind integrated PV compared to a facade without such installations. The focus is on evaluating potential differences in fire spread, heat development, and other factors, with the overarching goal of better understanding fire safety related to integrated solar solutions in buildings.

Figure 1. The picture shows the PV panels that is going to be used in the project.

Method

The experiment is based on the principles of the SP FIRE 105 [3]. The choice of material and setup are limited by the available time and resources of the bachelor thesis. This is currently ongoing work which is not concluded. The tests will take place at Maersk training centre in Haugesund in week 9-10, 2024.

Two large-scale facade experiments are planned: with PV, and one facade wall without PV. The heat source for the experiment will be a pool fire containing heptane, simulating room flashover spreading to the facade. Additionally, smaller test experiments will be conducted to support the results.

The results from the facade tests will be compared and give information about the main differences is how the fire behave. The thesis is still in progress, and the group aims to present our work at the Nordic Fire & Safety Days.

When the experiment is conducted, it will be recorded, and measurements will be taken with thermocouples. Thermocouples provide a good indication of the effect of combustion on the wall, but flames are unpredictable, making it difficult to determine their exact location. Therefore, it is unlikely that the flames will have the greatest impact where the thermocouples are positioned. This is why cameras will be used to better visualize the flames.

The expected outcome of the study

It is assumed that there will be differences in fire behaviour between a facade wall with BIPV and one without. The way the PV are integrated into the facade and how they are attached create a cavity, which may potentially impact fire spread.

This hypothesis will be tested through experiments, with results providing insights into the fire safety associated with integrated solar solutions in buildings.

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Experimental simulation of external fires on a solar flat roof

Study on the influence of the type of insulation and the importance of end-use testing

Author 1 Nele Ameye
International Technical
Department
Recticel Insulation
Wevelgem, Belgium
Ameye.nele@recticel.com

Author 2 Mikael Jonsson
Technical Manager Sweden,
Technical Expert Nordics
Recticel Insulation
Mäntsälä, Finland
Jonsson.mikael@recticel.com

Author 3 Antti Viitanen
Project and Specification
Engineer
Recticel Insulation
Mäntsälä, Finland
Viitanen.antti@recticel.com

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Fire behavior, end-use testing, PV-panels, PIR, Mineral Wool.

Abstract

There is a global increasing attention in the building industry regarding fire safety on the one hand, and reduction of Green House Gas emissions on the other hand. The first aspect leading to the promotion of non-combustible insulation materials, the latter resulting in an increased number of PV-installations on flat roofs and the growing interest in highly insulating, combustible synthetic foams such as PIR. The question is then how these trends can be combined. Do we need non-combustible insulation in a flat roof with PV-panels on top? Or does PIR perform equally as good in such an application?

There is still a lot of unclarity on how to assess the fire safety of flat roof build-ups with PV-panels on top. There are concerns that there might be an intensified fire due to re-radiation by the PV-panels. Even more, they might be an extra ignition source, they complicate firefighting and they add an extra fire load to the roof. Reason enough for PU Europe to simulate this application in an end-use configuration, rather than to focus on the reaction to fire of some composing parts as such.

Figure 1. Arrangement of PV system on the roof assemblies [1]

Test setup [1]

Two test rigs, 6m x 6m each, were tested on their behavior in case a fire ignites between the PV-panels and the waterproofing membrane. The build-up of both platforms was identical, apart from the insulation layer. To ensure the same insulation value on the roof, one rig consisted of 1 layer of 142 mm PIR versus 2 layers of 130 mm Mineral Wool (i.e. 260 mm in total) for the other rig. The insulation was covered with a PVC waterproofing membrane and supported by a steel deck structure. A vapor barrier was foreseen in the form of a PE-foil in between the insulation and the steel deck. Both build-ups were FM Approved [2].

A common East-West configuration of PV-panels was simulated by putting four panels (3.2 m x 1.84 m in total) back-to-back with an inclination of 13° relative to the roof plane. The panels had a foil back sheet and were rated fire class C according to IEC 61730-2[3].

In order to simulate an external fire starting below a PV array on top of a flat roof, an ignition was forced by means of a gas burner as suggested by CENELEC CLC/TR 50670:2016 [4]. The burner was removed after 15 minutes, resulting in a fire exposure comparable to what is achieved in a CEN/TS 1187 t1-test [5]. Opposed to the aforementioned standardized t1-test, the test under consideration took place outdoors, consequently being submitted to the outdoor climate conditions such as temperature, relative humidity and wind at the moment of testing. As the rigs were tested one after the other, these conditions varied slightly. The most significant change was observed in terms of wind direction.

Observations

The analysis of the burned test rigs was limited to visual observations and temperature loggings in and between the several layers of the build-up.

The area which was attacked by flames was not confined to the perimeter of the PV-panels. The flame spread was comparable for both test rigs, reaching the outer periphery of the test setup, without however covering the complete area. As the wind direction changed in between both tests, its influence could be clearly observed. The type of insulation

seemed to have little influence in this flame spread, nor in the time until the flames self-extinguished (32 minutes in case of PIR, 28 minutes in case of Mineral Wool).

Temperatures were measured below and in the middle of the insulation layer (within and outside the perimeter of the PV panel configuration). The temperature curves were registered and clearly showed a different tendency regarding the temperature in the middle of the insulation layer within the perimeter of the PV configuration. A peak temperature of 155°C was reached after 23 minutes in case of the PIR build-up, after which the temperature started to decrease again. At about 80 minutes after the start of the test, the complete test rig, including the steel deck, started to cool down. This fast increase and decrease of the internal temperature could not be detected in case of the Mineral Wool build-up. A steady increase in temperature was observed after the start of the test, leading to 35°C after 30 minutes, 290°C after 80 minutes and 440°C after 4 hours. The temperature was continuously recorded, showing a temperature of the steel deck of 190°C overnight.

The overall visual damage pattern of the burned test rigs appeared to be similar for both setups.

Both test rigs were dismantled to enable visual observations in the different layers of the build-up. No burning through was determined for the PIR-insulation. Only 25% of the thickness of the insulation was charred in this case. The PE-foil underneath remained undamaged. On the other hand, the high temperatures in the Mineral Wool layers caused the underlying PE-foil to melt away. Both insulation layers were affected by the heat.

Conclusions

A comparative fire test was set up by PU Europe in order to gain insights in the fire behavior of a flat roof structure covered with PV-panels on the one hand, and to evaluate the impact of the type of insulation layer on the other hand. A large scale end-use test setup was foreseen with a PIR (combustible) and Mineral Wool (non-combustible) insulation layer. Both assemblies being fully FM Approved. An external fire was simulated by adding an ignition source between the PV-panels and the waterproofing membrane.

By testing the insulation materials in an end-use configuration, it was noticed that the fire performance of the boards as such did not have a significant influence on the overall fire behavior of the roof in this specific test setup. The fire spread to the same extent in both situations, mainly determined by the presence and direction of the wind. Both test assemblies self-extinguished after about half an hour and none of the test rigs was completely burned out.

A difference was observed in temperature profile inside the insulation layer. Whereas there was a rather fast increase, moderate peak (155°C) and constant cool down of the PIR-insulation, the temperature curve increased steadily up to 440°C (4 hours after the start of the test) in the Mineral Wool layers. This high temperature has caused the PE-foil underneath to melt away, whereas this layer remained undamaged for the PIR-build-up.

The test has shown that, taking into account the specific test settings and boundary conditions as described above, the combustible PIR-insulation did not perform worse than the

non-combustible Mineral Wool in the tested end-use configuration.

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Anne Dederichs (RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Technical University of Denmark)

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